

Democratic and Popular Republic of Algeria
Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research
National School of Statistics and Applied Economics (ENSSEA)
Department of Applied Statistics and Econometrics
Laboratory of Modeling Stochastic Phenomena (Lamops)

The thesis is for the degree of Doctor of Science in
Statistics and Applied Economics
Option: Applied Statistics

Theme:
Bayesian Estimation and Prediction of the Wind
Power by Using the Bimodal Mixture Weibull and
the Weibull-Length-Biased Distributions

Mr. Brahim Taoussi

Thesis Committee:

Prof. Henry Medjden Kherchi (ENSSEA)	President
The late Prof. Naima Boudrissa (ENSSEA)	Supervisor
Dr. Sidi Mohammed Boudia (CDER)	Co-Supervisor
Prof. Nadjia El-Saadi (ENSSEA)	Examiner
Prof. Ghania Saidi (ENSSEA)	Examiner
Prof. Lazhar Chine (University of Boumerdes UMBB)	Examiner
Prof. Djelloul Ben Anaya (University of Khemis Miliana)	Examiner

2021/2022

To my late father, my late supervisor and to my family

Abstract

One of the most challenging aspects of using wind as a power source is its intermittency. A small change in the wind speed impacts greatly the wind turbine power output, given the cubic dependency of the wind power to the wind speed. Thus it is primordial to accurately model the wind speed. It is common practice to use a probabilistic distribution to model the stochastic variation in wind speed. This is usually done using the two-parameter Weibull probability distribution function (PDF). However, it cannot fit all wind regimes especially in large countries with different climates and topography such as Algeria. This study suggests altering the two-parameter Weibull to overcome its inefficiency. This can be done by either adding a location parameter to W2 to become the three-parameter Weibull distribution (W3), mixing it with another W2 to get the bimodal Weibull distribution (WW) or using another form of W2 i.e. the Weibull-length-biased distribution (WLB). Seeking an alternative to the two-parameter Weibull inside the Weibull family might ensure preserving the features that attracted wind energy experts to use it since the 1970s. Bayesian and Frequentist methods were used to estimate the parameters of these PDFs. The originality of this work stems from the fact that the bimodal Weibull distribution and the Bayesian method were never been applied for wind power assessment In Algeria, and that in our knowledge the Weibull-length-biased distribution was never utilized in wind power applications. The site of In-Salah was chosen to conduct this comparative study for two reasons. The results revealed that the bimodal Weibull estimated by the Bayesian approach is the most accurate model according to the root mean squared error, the mean absolute error, and the wind power error metrics, followed by the Weibull-length-biased, the three-parameter Weibull, and lastly the two-parameter Weibull. In addition, the Bayesian method outperformed the frequentist methods. An advantage of using the Bayesian approach over the frequentist methods is the ability to deploy the posterior predictive distribution. The posterior predictive distribution of the annual mean wind speed in In-Salah at 10 m height has a mean of 7.11 m/s and 95% credible interval of [2.35, 11.95] while the annual mean power density has a mean of 331.68 W/m² and 95% credible interval of [301.98, 360.67].

Keywords

Wind power; Weibull distribution; Bayesian method; Goodness-of-fit analysis.

الملخص

احد اهم تحديات استعمال الرياح كمصدر طاقة هو التغير الشديد في سرعتها. يؤثر التغيير الطفيف في سرعة الرياح بشكل كبير على ناتج طاقة توربينات الرياح ، بالنظر إلى ان طاقة الرياح هي دالة خطية لمكعب سرعة الرياح. وبالتالي فمن الأساسي أن تتم نمذجة سرعة الرياح بدقة. من الشائع استخدام التوزيع الاحتمالي لنمذجة العشوائية في سرعة الرياح. يتم ذلك عادةً باستخدام الدالة الاحتمالية لتوزيع Weibull ذي المعلمتين. ومع ذلك، لا يمكن أن نتوقع ان يناسب هذا التوزيع الاحتمالي جميع أنظمة الرياح خاصة في البلدان الكبيرة ذات مناخات وطبوغرافيا مختلفة مثل الجزائر. تقترح هذه الدراسة تغيير Weibull ذو المعلمتين للتغلب على عدم كفاءته إما عن طريق إضافة معلمة موقع إلى $W2$ لتصبح توزيع Weibull ذات المعلمات الثلاثة ($W3$) ، عن طريق مزجه مع $W2$ آخر للحصول على توزيع Weibull المختلط (WW) أو باستخدام شكل آخر من $W2$ ، أي توزيع Weibull المنحاز للطول (WLB). تم اعتماد طريقة بايز لتقدير معلمات التوزيعات المذكورة أعلاه. أصالة هذا العمل تنبع من حقيقة انه لم يتم استعمال توزيع Weibull المختلط وطريقة بايز على الإطلاق لتقييم طاقة الرياح في الجزائر، وعلى حد علمنا، لم يتم استخدام توزيع Weibull المنحاز للطول مطلقاً لنمذجة سرعة الرياح. تم اختيار موقع عين صالح لإجراء دراسة مقارنة بين التوزيعات الاحتمالية المذكورة أعلاه من جهة وبين طريقي التقدير الكلاسيكية وطريقة التقدير البايزية من جهة أخرى. كشفت النتائج أن نموذج Weibull المختلط المقدره معالمه بالطريقة البايزية هو النموذج الأكثر دقة وفقاً لخطأ متوسط الجذر التربيعي، ومتوسط الخطأ المطلق، ومقياس الخطأ في تقدير متوسط طاقة الرياح متبوعاً بتوزيع Weibull منحاز الطول، يليه توزيع Weibull المكون من ثلاث معلمات، ثم أخيراً توزيع Weibull ذي المعلمتين المستخدم على نطاق واسع. أشارت الدراسة المقارنة إلى تفوق طريقة بايز على الطرق الكلاسيكية في جميع اختبارات جودة الملائمة المستخدمة. ميزة أخرى لاستخدام نهج بايز على الطرق الكلاسيكية هي القدرة على نشر التوزيع التنبئي اللاحق. التوزيع التنبئي اللاحق السنوي لمتوسط سرعة الرياح في عين صالح بمتوسط 7.11 م / ث و 95٪ مجال الثقة [2.35، 11.95] بينما متوسط كثافة قدرة سنوي يبلغ متوسطه 331.68 وات / م² و 95٪ مجال الثقة [301.98، 360.67].

الكلمات المفتاحية

طاقة الرياح، توزيع وايبيل، طريقة بايز، تحليل جودة الملاءمة.

Acknowledgments

I would like to thank my supervisor the late Prof. Naima Boudrissa who I knew since 2009, back when I was an undergrad student. I had quite the journey with her during my engineering, my masters, and my PhD. This journey led me to consider her as family, rest in peace dear supervisor. Many thanks to my co-supervisor Dr. Sidi Mohammed Boudia, I feel like I gained you as a friend throughout this PhD. This research would not have been accomplished without your guidance, patience, and continuous support. I would like to show my deep gratitude to Prof. Aoife Foley from Queen's University Belfast for hosting, guiding, and helping me grow as a researcher.

I would like to thank the Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research for granting me the PNE scholarship and the National School of Commerce Koléa (ESC) for accepting and qualifying me for this scholarship. Thanks also to the Renewable Energy Development Center (CDER) at Algiers, the School of Aerospace and Mechanical Engineering at Belfast for their contribution to this work.

Table of Contents

Chapter 1 Introduction	17
Chapter 2 Wind energy and the power system in Algeria.....	28
2.1 Sourcing power from the wind	28
2.2 Wind variability	29
2.3 Wind energy conversion system.....	31
2.4 Wind turbines mechanics	35
2.5 Wind shear	36
2.6 Power variability	37
2.7 Electricity production and the national power grid.....	38
2.8 Economics of wind energy	41
2.9 Algerian Establishments to develop the renewable energies	44
Chapter 3 Modeling the wind speed	46
3.1 Probability density functions	46
3.1.1 The two-parameter Weibull distribution (W2).....	46
3.1.2 The three-parameter Weibull (W3)	49
3.1.3 The five-parameter bimodal Weibull mixture (WW)	50
3.1.4 The Weibull – length – biased distribution (WLB)	51
3.2 Frequentist estimation methods	54
3.2.1 The maximum likelihood method (MLM).....	54
3.2.2 The least-squares estimation method (LSE)	56
3.2.3 The moments method (MOM)	57
3.2.4 The linear moments method (LMOM)	57
3.2.5 The power density method (PDM).....	58

Table of Contents

3.3 Bayesian estimation methods.....	59
3.3.1 The prior density function	60
3.3.2 The loss function.....	62
3.3.3 Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) and Gibbs sampling.....	62
3.4 Goodness-of-fit metrics	63
Chapter 4 Results and interpretation	65
4.1 Statistical description of the data	65
4.2 Analysis of the Bayesian estimates.....	67
4.3 Analysis of the Weibull parameters.....	72
4.4 Fitness evaluation of the chosen probability distribution functions.....	77
4.5 Assessing the wind power density.....	82
4.6 Wind power indicators.....	85
4.7 Limitations of the study	90
4.8 Discussion.....	91
Chapter 5 General conclusion.....	95
References	
Appendix	

List of Tables

Table 1 Weights (W_{Ec}) attributed to the criteria considered in the calculation of the total study weight (W_E) including the number of time series (NTS), time series length (LTS), temporal resolution (TR), measurement height (h), number of goodness-of-fit metrics ($NGoF$), and number of evaluated distributions (ND).....21

Table 2 Information on the Algerian evaluated studies including year of publication, number of evaluated time series (NTS), time series length (LTS), temporal resolution (TR), measurement height (h), number of evaluated distributions (ND), and number of goodness-of-fit metrics ($NGoF$).22

Table 3 Gamesa G52 wind turbine parameters34

Table 4 Roughness length (Z_0) according to the geography condition in Algeria37

Table 5 Range of specific cost of wind turbines based on the rated power42

Table 6 The capacity factor (C_f) and the levelized cost of electricity ($LCOE$) for wind energy in Algeria44

Table 7 Probabilistic properties of for the two- and the three- parameter Weibull distributions (W_2 and W_3).....48

Table 8 Probabilistic properties of the five-parameter homogeneous bimodal Weibull (WW).....51

Table 9 probabilistic properties of the two-parameter Weibull-length-biased distribution (WLB).53

Table 10 Maximum likelihood method (MLM) to estimate the parameters of the two-parameter and the three-parameter Weibull distributions55

Table 11 Modified maximum likelihood (MML) and modified moments (MM) methods to estimate the parameters of the three-parameter Weibull distributions.....56

Table 12 Least-squares estimation (LSE) method to estimate the parameters of the two-parameter, the three-parameter Weibull and the Weibull-length-biased distributions.....57

Table 13 the method of moments (MOM) to estimate the parameters of the two-parameter Weibull and the Weibull-length-biased distributions57

Table 14 the method of l-moments (LMOM) to estimate the parameters of the two-parameter Weibull distribution58

Table 15 the power density method (PDM) to estimate the parameters of the two-parameter Weibull and the Weibull-length-biased distributions59

Table 16 candidate distribution models for the prior distributions of their parameters60

Table 17 classical goodness-of-fit metrics63

Table 18 geographical coordinates, and measurement information of In-Salah station66

List of Tables

Table 19 monthly and annual descriptive statistics of In-Salah for the period from 01/01/2015 to 31/12/2016 at 10 m AGL	67
Table 20 Frequentist and Bayesian estimation of the two-parameter Weibull scale parameter (α_{W2}) using the wind speed data in In-Salah at 10 m AGL.	72
Table 21 Frequentist and Bayesian estimation of the two-parameter Weibull shape parameter (β_{W2}) using the wind speed data in In-Salah at 10 m AGL.	73
Table 22 Frequentist and Bayesian estimation of the Weibull-length-biased scale parameter (α_{WLB}) using the wind speed data in In-Salah at 10 m AGL.	73
Table 23 Frequentist and Bayesian estimation of the Weibull-length-biased scale parameter (β_{WLB}) using the wind speed data in In-Salah at 10 m AGL.	74
Table 24 Frequentist and Bayesian estimation of the three-parameter Weibull scale parameter (α_{W3}) using the wind speed data in In-Salah at 10 m AGL.	75
Table 25 Frequentist and Bayesian estimation of the three-parameter Weibull shape parameter (β_{W3}) using the wind speed data in In-Salah at 10 m AGL.	75
Table 26 Frequentist and Bayesian estimation of the three-parameter Weibull shift parameter (τ_{W3}) using the wind speed data in In-Salah at 10 m AGL.	76
Table 27 Bayesian estimation of the bimodal Weibull parameters using the wind speed data in In-Salah at 10 m AGL	76
Table 28 goodness-of-fit metrics to evaluate the fitness of W2, WLB and WW to model the wind speed data in In-Salah measured at 10 m AGL.	77
Table 29 Ranking of the best models.....	85
Table 30 Wind power indicators.....	89
Table 31 Posterior predictive distribution of the mean wind speed and the mean wind power density in In-Salah at 10 m AGL	89

List of Figures

Figure 1 (A) The share of renewables by type in the installed power capacity vs. (B) the share of renewable electricity in the world by power type (%) in 2018 [6], [7]	17
Figure 2 Renewable energy (A) targeted installed capacity vs. (B) realized capacity in 2018 [8]	19
Figure 3 Installed power capacity in Algeria by technology (%) in 2018 [9]	20
Figure 4 Partition of the total study weight (WE) according to number of time series (NTS), length of time series (LTS), temporal resolution (TR), measurement height (h), number of GoF metrics ($NGoF$), and number of distributions (ND) in (A) Jung and Schindler’s review article and [23] (B) in the evaluated Algerian studies	24
Figure 5 Share of the parameter estimation methods (PEM) in (A) Jung and Schindler’s review article and [23] (B) in the evaluated Algerian studies	25
Figure 6 Wind Spectrum Farm Brookhaven Based on Work by van der Hoven [45].....	29
Figure 7 Cup anemometer (left) and wind vane (right) [49].	30
Figure 8 Distribution of meteorological stations over Algeria [15].	31
Figure 9 Swept area of wind turbine blades [53].	32
Figure 10 Power curve for Gamesa G52 0.85 MW wind turbine [27].	34
Figure 11 Classification of wind turbines [61]	35
Figure 12 Major wind turbine components [44].	36
Figure 13 Electricity production between 1985 and 2020 in Algeria [68]	39
Figure 14 The national interconnected power grid (RIN), 220 and 400 kV transmission lines [69]	40
Figure 15 (A) Global weighted average utility scale capacity factor by technology 2010-2020 in the world and (B) Global weighted average utility scale LCOE by technology 2010-2020 in the world [8]	43
Figure 16 Two-parameter Weibull (W2) probability distribution.....	47
Figure 17 Three-parameter Weibull (W2) probability distribution	49
Figure 18 Five-parameter bimodal Weibull (W2) probability distribution	51
Figure 19 Length-biased-Weibull (WLB) vs. two-parameter Weibull (W2) probability distribution	54
Figure 20 The distribution of annual shape factor (β) in Algeria at 10 m height (dimensionless) [15].....	61
Figure 21 Share of goodness-of-fit (GoF) metrics used in the evaluated studies [23]	64

List of Figures

Figure 22 The location of In-Salah in Algeria.	66
Figure 23 Trace diagnostic plot for (A and B) scale and shape parameters of W2 and (C and D) scale and shape parameters of WLB using the wind speed data measured at In-Salah at 10 m AGL. Chains 1 and 2 are represented by red and blue lines respectively	68
Figure 24 BGR convergence diagnostics plotting for (A) W2 parameters and (B) WLB parameters using the wind speed data in In-Salah at 10 m AGL.....	68
Figure 25 Trace diagnostic plot of WW scale, shape, and mixing parameters using the wind speed data in In-Salah at 10 m AGL. Chains 1 and 2 are represented by red and blue lines respectively.....	69
Figure 26 BGR convergence diagnostics plotting for (two left) W2 parameters and (two right) WLB parameters using the wind speed data in In-Salah at 10 m AGL.	70
Figure 27 The posterior densities of the scale (α) and the shape (β) parameters of W2 (top) and WLB (bottom) using the wind speed data in In-Salah at 10 m AGL.	71
Figure 28 The posterior densities of the scale (α_1 and α_2), the shape (β_1 and β_2) and the mixing (ω , $1 - \omega$) parameters of WW using the wind speed data in In-Salah at 10 m AGL.....	71
Figure 29 Boxplots of BIC values related to the employed combination PDF/PEM for the wind speed data in In-Salah measured at 10 m AGL.....	78
Figure 30 Boxplots of (A) the used PDFs, (B) the frequentist and the Bayesian PEMs ordered by ascending median BIC to the wind speed data in In-Salah measured at 10 m AGL.	79
Figure 31 Boxplots of (A) $RMSE_{PP}$ (B) $RMSE_{PDF}$ values related to the models based on the combination PDF/PEM for the wind speed data in In-Salah measured at 10 m AGL.	80
Figure 32 Boxplots of (A, C) the used PDFs, (B, D) the frequentist and the Bayesian PEMs ordered by ascending median $RMSE_{PP}$ and ascending median $RMSE_{PDF}$ to the wind speed data in In-Salah measured at 10 m AGL.	80
Figure 33 Boxplots of (A) MAE_{PP} (B) MAE_{PDF} values related to the models based on the combination PDF/PEM for the wind speed data in In-Salah measured at 10 m AGL.....	81
Figure 34 Boxplots of (A, C) the used PDFs, (B, D) the frequentist and the Bayesian PEMs ordered by ascending median MAE_{PP} and ascending median MAE_{PDF} to the wind speed data in In-Salah measured at 10 m AGL.....	82
Figure 35 Boxplots of WPE values related to the models based on the combination PDF/PEM for the wind speed data in In-Salah measured at 10 m AGL.....	83
Figure 36 Boxplots of (A) the used PDFs, (B) the frequentist and the Bayesian PEMs ordered by ascending median WPE to the wind speed data in In-Salah measured at 10 m AGL.	84

List of Figures

Figure 37 Scatterplots of WPD computed values via W2, WLB, W3 and WW versus those computed by the wind speed data in In-Salah measured at 10 m height ranked by descending R^2	84
Figure 38 Histogram with the best fitted models for the used annual wind speed data	86
Figure 39 Histograms with the best fitted models for the wind speed data of (A) January, (B) February, (C) March and (D) April.....	87
Figure 40 Histograms with the best fitted models for the data of (A) May, (B) June, (C) July and (D) August.....	87
Figure 41 Histograms with the best fitted models for the data of (A) September, (B) October, (C) November and (D) December	88
Figure 42 Posterior predictive distribution of the annual mean wind speed V in In-Salah at 10 m AGL	90
Figure 43 Posterior predictive distribution of the annual mean wind power density WPD in In-Salah at 10 m AGL	90

Nomenclature

Abbreviation

$\pi(\theta)$	The prior density function
$\pi(\theta; v)$	The posterior density
$f(\cdot)$	Probability density function
$F(\cdot)$	Cumulative distribution function
$\Gamma(\cdot)$	Gamma function
$E(\cdot)$	Expected value
$Q(\cdot)$	Quantile function
C	Combination
E_{pf}	Empirical energy pattern factor
k	Number of parameters
Kr	Empirical kurtosis
l_i	Empirical L-moments
$L(v; \theta)$	Likelihood function
$l(\hat{\theta}, \theta)$	Loss function
$LL(v; \theta)$	Log-likelihood function
Me	Median (m/s)
Mo	Mode (m/s)
n	Size of the sample
P_r	The rated power
P_{out}	The actual power produced for a specific time period
R^2	Coefficient of determination
S^2	Empirical variance (m/s) ²
S	Empirical standard deviation (m/s)
Sk	Empirical skewness
V	Random variable designates the wind velocity
\bar{v}	Empirical mean wind speed (m/s)
\bar{v}^3	Empirical third raw moment (m/s) ³

$v_{(i)}$	Order statistics of v
$v_{(1)}$	Empirical minimum wind speed (m/s)
$v_{(n)}$	Empirical maximum wind speed (m/s)
v_{ci}	Cut-in wind speed (m/s)
v_{co}	Cut-out wind speed (m/s)
v_{Me}	Empirical median (m/s)
v_{MO}	Empirical mode (m/s)
v_{maxE}	The maximum energy-carrying wind speed
v_{mp}	The most probable wind speed
v_r	Rated wind speed (m/s)
Z_0	The terrain roughness length (m)

Acronyms

BIC	Bayesian information criterion
BGR	Brooks-Gelman-Rubin statistic
CDF	Cumulative density function
CPU	Cost per unit
CV	Coefficient of variation
GoF	Goodness-of-fit
LMOM	linear moments method
LSE	Least-squares estimation
MAE	Mean absolute error (m/s)
MCMC	Markov Chain Monte Carlo
MLM	Maximum likelihood method
MML	Modified maximum likelihood
MM	Modified moments
MOM	moments method
PDF	Probability density function
PDM	Power density method

Nomenclature

PEM	Parameter estimation method
PIAT	In-Salah – Adrar – Timimoun Pole
PVC	Present value cost
RMSE	Root mean squared error (m/s)
RPE	Relative percentage error
W2	The two-parameter Weibull distribution
W3	The three-parameter Weibull distribution
WLB	The Weibull-length-biased distribution
WW	The bimodal Weibull distribution
WECS	Wind energy conversion system

Symbols

α	Scale parameter (m/s)
β	Shape parameter (–)
γ_1	Population skewness
γ_2	Population kurtosis
δ	Population standard deviation (m/s)
θ	Parameters of the model
λ	Combination parameter equals to α^β
ρ	Air density (kg/m^3)
τ	Shift parameter (m/s)
ρ	Air density (kg/m^3)
ω	Mixing parameter

Units

m/s	Meters per second
m	Meter
kg/m^3	Kilograms per meter cube
W/m^2	Watts per metre square

Chapter 1 Introduction

The rise of the emitted greenhouse gases has led to global warming [1]. Climate change characterized by global warming is a stable and durable change in weather patterns [2]. The impacts of climate change involve increase surface temperatures, changes in water and wind availability, and frequent extreme weather events [3]. Expanding the share of renewable energies in electricity generation will be the key to decarbonizing electricity systems and mitigating the negative effects of global warming [4], [5]. Renewable energies accounted for 17.9% of the total final energy consumption and generated 26.2% of the world’s electrical needs in 2018. Figure 1 depicts (A) the share of renewables by type in the installed power capacity vs. (B) the share of renewable electricity in the world by power type [6], [7]. It was remarked that wind is the 2nd largest renewable resource in the world after the traditional hydropower energy.

Figure 1 (A) The share of renewables by type in the installed power capacity vs. (B) the share of renewable electricity in the world by power type (%) in 2018 [6], [7]

Wind energy is becoming among the cheapest power resources in numerous countries around the world as its cost per kilowatt-hour is falling rapidly [6]. In just a decade the installed capacity from wind moved from 121 GW in 2008 to 591 GW in 2018. Most of these installations are located in China (35%), the US (16%), Germany (10%), India (6%), and Spain (4%) [6]. Denmark is a worldwide role model when it comes to effectively utilizing wind as an energy resource because 41% of the Danish electrical consumption in 2018 is met using wind [6].

Just like the other regions around the world, deploying renewable energy in North Africa is growing. Figure 2 shows the targeted renewables capacity to be installed and the realized renewables capacity in 2018 [8]. Egypt and Algeria have higher aims as they want to rump up the renewable capacity beyond 20 GW [8]. However, until the end of 2018 only Egypt and Morocco realized substantial renewable capacity of 4.8 and 3.2 GW respectively [8]. Installed renewable power capacity is progressing swiftly in Morocco as the country installed nearly 30% of the targeted capacity, followed by Egypt (9%), Tunisia (8%), Algeria (3%) then Libya (0.13%). Having one of the highest oil and natural gas reserves in the region and the capability to secure the energy needs locally seem to hinder the development of renewable energies in Algeria, however, this comfortable situation will change as soon as these recourses deplete. The ambitious plan to install 22 GW of renewable electricity by 2030 was pushed back to be realized between 2035 and 2040 [9]. The major challenges that faced this ambitious program are related to funding and incentivizing mechanisms, plus Algeria aims to domicile and nationalize the renewable energy industry, no incentives to encourage the local renewable energy industry, high cost of financing, weak of support infrastructures for renewables such as skilled labor, local spare part manufacturing, laboratories testing, absence of the study of renewables major in the undergrad program [9], [10].

Figure 2 Renewable energy (A) targeted installed capacity vs. (B) realized capacity in 2018 [8]

Algeria is looking to increase the renewable electricity generation to export it to South Europe, meet its own domestic energy needs, decarbonize its electricity system and minimize natural gas dependency. Currently, solar energy has been prioritized in the government's renewable energy plans due to the vast solar resource in the Sahara desert. Most of the Algerian installed renewable capacity comes from photovoltaic (PV) as it reached 344.1 MW by June 2018 [10]. However, Algeria has the fifth-highest wind energy potential in Africa [11] and its wind energy potential was assessed to be around 35 TWh/year [12]. Moreover, the wind velocity exceeds 3 m/s in 78% of the Algerian surface especially in the Southwest [13]. Furthermore, the regions of Adrar [14], Hassi-R'mel [13], Mechria [15], and In-Salah [16] have been identified as strong candidates in Algeria to site large-scale wind farms. Yet, in terms of employing wind as a power source, Algeria is lagging far behind its neighbors as the installed capacity from wind in the North African countries in descending order is 1220 MW (Morocco), 1125 MW (Egypt), 245 MW (Tunisia), 34 MW (Mauritania) and 10.2 MW (Algeria) by the end of 2018 [8].

Figure 3 shows the installed power capacity in Algeria by technology (%) in 2018 [9]. It can be noticed that natural gas powers most of the generated electricity and renewable energy is still lowly penetrated (around 4%) in the national electrical system.

Figure 3 Installed power capacity in Algeria by technology (%) in 2018 [9]

Integrating effectively sustainable resources such as solar PV and wind to the power grid can be challenging for the grid operators as they are characterized by their uncertainty and variability problems [17]. The stochastic nature of wind power comes from its dependency on factors like geographic region, topography, and weather conditions such as wind speed, temperature, and direction [17], [18]. Wind speed is the factor that affects the most the wind energy conversion system (WECS) as the wind power is proportional to the cube of wind speed thus it is vital to describe the wind speed variations to optimize the design of WECS and effectively utilize the wind energy [19], [20]. The probabilistic approach proved to be an effective tool to describe the wind speed variations [21]. This is usually done using the two-parameter Weibull (W2) as the preliminary probability distribution function (PDF) following the recommendation of the International Electro-technical Commission [22].

Even though W2 is the most used PDF to model the wind speed data yet it inadequately fit wind regimes that are bimodal, have a low speed, or have a small range of variation [23]. Therefore several alternatives for W2 have been sought in the literature and in the industry to develop better wind energy resources estimation tools. In their literature review article, Jung and Schindler (2018) [23] thoroughly analyzed statistical and probabilistic means used in the wind energy field. This includes PDFs used to model the wind speed, parameter estimation methods (PEMs), and goodness-of-fit (GoF) metrics used to judge the quality of these estimates. They reviewed 46 articles published between 2010 and 2018 in a peer-reviewed periodical listed by SCImago [23]. Some of these studies were conducted on a worldwide scale, while others were conducted in 19 countries and others in the Mediterranean Sea. These papers evaluated in total 115 different PDFs at least once, their number of parameters ranges between one and seven. This includes homogeneous and heterogeneous bimodal PDFs. Jung and Schindler assessed these 46 papers by given them weights (WE_c) that range between 0 and 1 and depend to the number of times series (NTS), the time series length (LTS) expressed in years, the temporal resolution (TR) in hours, the measurement height (h) in meters, the number of GoF metrics ($NGoF$) and the number of evaluated PDFs (ND) as described in Table 1 [23]; then the sum of these six weights form a total weight (WE).

Table 1 Weights (WE_c) attributed to the criteria considered in the calculation of the total study weight (WE) including the number of time series (NTS), time series length (LTS), temporal resolution (TR), measurement height (h), number of goodness-of-fit metrics ($NGoF$), and number of evaluated distributions (ND) [23].

WE_c	NTS	LTS (years)	TR (h)	h (m)	$NGoF$	ND
0		≤ 4	≥ 1	≤ 50	≤ 4	
0.05	1					2
0.1	2 – 5					3 – 5
0.15	6 – 10					
0.25	11 – 99					6 – 10
0.5	100 – 250	> 4	< 1	> 50	> 4	11 – 20
1	> 250					> 20

Similar to Jung and Schindler [23], 16 non-exhaustive studies that assessed the wind power potential in Algeria were evaluated, key information from these papers are given in Table 2. These studies were published since 2008 and onwards in the following journals *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* [11], [13], [24]–[26], *Energy* [16], [27], [28], *Energy Conversion and Management* [29], [30]; and one each in *Energy Procedia* [14], *Energy Sources, Part A: Recovery, Utilization, and Environmental Effects* [31], *International Journal of Green Energy* [32], *Renewable Energy* [33], *Sustainable Cities and Society* [15] and *Sustainable Energy Technologies and Assessments* [34]. Most of these 16 studies that assessed Algeria’s wind power potential were conducted by S. M. Boudia [15], [27], [29]–[32]; O. Guerri [16], [24], [30], [31]; N.K. Merzouk [14], [33], [34]; S. Himri [11], [26], [34] and Y. Himri [11], [26], [34]. Furthermore, the list of contributors also includes foreigners like A. A. Setiawan from Australia [26], J. A. Santos from Portugal [27], and S. Rehman from Saudi Arabia [10], [26]. Most of the mentioned studies (54%) were conducted by the Renewable Energy Development Center (CDER).

Table 2 Information on the Algerian evaluated studies including year of publication, number of evaluated time series (*NTS*), time series length (*LTS*), temporal resolution (*TR*), measurement height (*h*), number of evaluated distributions (*ND*), and number of goodness-of-fit metrics (*NGoF*).

Study	Year	<i>NTS</i>	<i>LTS</i> (years)	<i>TR</i>	<i>h</i> (m)	<i>ND</i>	<i>NGoF</i>
Abdeslame <i>et al.</i> [33]	2017	4	10	3h	10	1	0
Aries <i>et al.</i> [29]	2018	4	2 – 5	5 – 30 min	10	8	3
Belabes <i>et al.</i> [24]	2015	6	10	3h	10	1	0
Boudia <i>et al.</i> [32]	2012	1	5	24h	10	1	0
Boudia <i>et al.</i> [30]	2015	1	10	3h	10	1	0
Boudia <i>et al.</i> [15]	2016	87	2 – 10	24h	10	1	0
Boudia <i>et al.</i> [27]	2019	42	33	6h – 24h	10	1	0
Chellali <i>et al.</i> [13]	2011	37	6	24h	10	1	0
Chellali <i>et al.</i> [25]	2012	6	2	1h	10	3	2
Daaou <i>et al.</i> [16]	2018	74	5 – 10	30 min – 3h	10	1	0
Djamai <i>et al.</i> [14]	2011	1	5	3h	10	1	0
Himri <i>et al.</i> [11]	2008	3	10	3h	10	1	0
Himri <i>et al.</i> [26]	2012	1	8	3h	10	0	0
Himri <i>et al.</i> [34]	2020	1	6	1h	10	1	0
Mezidi <i>et al.</i> [31]	2020	2	12	3h	10	1	0
Saheb Koussa <i>et al.</i> [28]	2016	13	10	1h	10	1	0

It can be remarked from Table 2 that the number of time-series (*NTS*) varies between 1 ([14], [26], [30], [32], [34]) and 87 [15]. Moreover, the studies [13], [15], [16], [27] analyzed over 30 time series as their conducted studies were on the national scale. Furthermore, most of these time series have length $LTS > 4$ years except for [25]. These studies used a variety of wind speed data such as wind velocity that was averaged every 5 minutes [29] to every day [24] but what they all have in common is being measured at 10 m above the ground level (AGL). The National Meteorological Office (ONM) is the primary provider of the wind speed datasets. However, some of the analyzed papers got their data from the Renewable Energy Development Center (CDER) [28], [29]; ERA-Interim reanalysis (European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts Re-Analysis Interim) [27], and Meteonorme 7 resource website [28]. As forecasted, most of the evaluated studies used just a single PDF to assess the wind power potential in Algeria and it is mainly the two-parameter Weibull (W2) PDF [11], [13]–[16], [24], [28], [30]–[34]; in exception to Boudia *et al.* [27] who utilized the three-parameter generalized extreme value for two reasons, the first is the fact that this distribution is a generalization of W2 and the second is that it outperformed W2, Gamma, Inverse Gaussian, Log-Normal, Gumbel, Nakagami and Generalized Logistic PDFs in a previous study conducted by the same author [29]. Furthermore, Chellali *et al.* [25] is the only study that used the maximum principle entropy which is a non-parametric PDF. Most of these evaluated studies did not do a comparative study to investigate which PDF models best the wind speed data in Algeria's climate and topography thus *NGoF* is mostly zero.

The partition of the total study weight (*WE*) from Jung and Schindler's paper, and the total study weight (*WE*) applied on the 16 Algerian studies are shown in Figure 4 (A and B) in respective order. It can be noticed that Aries *et al.* [29] study has the highest *WE*, yet none of the evaluated Algerian papers exceeds $WE > 1$. This is due to the single use of W2, the wind speed data is averaged every hour at best and mostly not measured at higher altitudes than 10 m, and the lack of comparative studies. However, the silver lining is that these papers mainly employed a decade of wind speed observations.

Figure 4 Partition of the total study weight (WE) according to number of time series (NTS), length of time series (LTS), temporal resolution (TR), measurement height (h), number of GoF metrics ($NGoF$), and number of distributions (ND) in (A) Jung and Schindler's review article and [23] (B) in the evaluated Algerian studies

Parameter estimation methods (PEM) play a drastic role in determining the ability of the selected PDF to properly model the wind speed data. Jung and Schindler [23] found that the

employed PEMs fall under two categories numerical methods such as the maximum likelihood method (MLM), the least-squares estimation method (LSE), the method of moments (MOM), the L-moments method (LMOM), and the modified maximum likelihood method (MMLM); and artificial intelligence algorithms like the cuckoo search (CS) and the expectation maximum (EM). However, the frequently deployed PEMs are the maximum likelihood method (MLM), the least-squares estimation method (LSE), the method of moments (MOM), and the L-moments method (LMOM) as displayed in Figure 5 (A). Correspondingly the maximum likelihood method dominates (43.75%) the utilized PEMs in the 16 evaluated Algerian studies [13], [15], [16], [25], [29], [30], [32]; followed by the L-moments method [29], the moments method [29] plus other PEMs like the power density method (PDM) [29] and the energy equivalent method (EEM) [31] as it is shown in Figure 5 (B). It should be mentioned that it was ambiguous to identify the used PEM in [11], [14], [24], [26]–[28], [33], [34]. Moreover, it can be noticed that the Bayesian method is absent in these studies as all the PEMs in Figure 5 are frequentist methods.

Figure 5 Share of the parameter estimation methods (PEM) in (A) Jung and Schindler's review article and [23] (B) in the evaluated Algerian studies

The Bayesian approach recently gained quite the momentum in the field of wind energy because of its ability to achieve accurate and reliable wind resource estimation and short-term

forecasts [35], yet it remains underused [35], [36]. Pang *et al.* [37] compared the maximum likelihood method with the Bayesian method using wind speed data from Hong Kong and found that the latter is extremely flexible. Erto *et al.* [38] demonstrated that using Bayesian estimates for W2 based on one month sample is as accurate as using maximum likelihood method estimators based on one year in assessing the characteristics of the wind speed in an Italian site, this might be useful when large wind speed sample is hard to obtain. The disability to provide large wind speed datasets was also tackled by Carta *et al.* [39] where the Bayesian networks were employed to estimate long-term wind speed frequency histograms for a site with few wind speed measurements in the Canary islands using long-term wind speed data from neighboring sites. According to Li *et al.* [35] and Adedipe *et al.* [40], various Bayesian techniques can serve different purposes in the wind energy industry. These applications include improving wind resource estimation, enhancing short-term wind speed and wind power generation forecasting, assessing the reliability and the fatigue life of the wind turbine systems, and improving decision-making about operations and management.

Several commercial software that evaluates the wind power potential and helps design an optimal WECS base their results on W2 [29]. This is due to its flexibility, simplicity, and ability to produce positive skewness [29], [41] which favors moderate wind speeds [42]. Yet several comparative studies highlighted W2's inability to represent all wind regimes. It was advised to substitute W2 with the five-parameter Wakeby, the four-parameter Kappa, and the four-parameter Johnson SB distributions [23]. However, their high number of parameters sophisticates the estimation process. This study suggests modifying W2 to overcome its poor performance. This can be done by either adding a location parameter to W2 to become the three-parameter Weibull distribution (W3) or mixing it with another W2 to get the bimodal Weibull distribution (WW) or using another form of W2 i.e. the Weibull-length-biased distribution (WLB). Seeking an alternative to W2 inside the Weibull family will ensure that the alternative PDFs are not complicated and familiar to physicists who are more involved in the field of wind energy than statisticians.

What distinguishes this study from the other works is using similar PDFs to W2 like the three-parameter Weibull distribution and the bimodal Weibull distribution as an alternative when it is incapable of accurately modeling the wind speed; investigate the capability of the Weibull-length-biased distribution in providing a better fit to the wind velocity data. In our knowledge, the Weibull-length-biased distribution was never used in this domain; and enhancing the parameter estimation process by employing the Bayesian method, that remains underused in this field. This is meant to help wind energy experts by providing them with better yet familiar probabilistic tools that can help enhance the wind power assessment.

The thesis was organized as follows; Chapter 2 discusses wind as a power source by defining the wind as a stochastic phenomenon, the conversion of the kinetic energy in the wind to electricity using wind energy conversion systems, and the power system in Algeria. Chapter 3 presents the probabilistic tools needed to model the wind speed. This involves the two-parameter Weibull, the three-parameter Weibull, the Weibull-length-biased, and probability density functions, the maximum likelihood, the least-squares, the moments, the L-moments, the power density, the modified maximum likelihood, and the modified moments as frequentist estimation methods; in addition to the Bayesian approach of estimation and the goodness-of-fit metrics. The results of the assessment of the wind power potential of In-Salah by applying the aforementioned methods are presented in chapter 4, and lastly, Chapter 5 summarizes the main results of this study.

Chapter 2 Wind energy and the power system in Algeria

Introduction

In this chapter, the stochastic phenomena wind is explained. The questions of what is wind and how it occurs are answered. The intermittent nature of wind was discussed both temporally and spatially. The annual, seasonal, diurnal, and even seconds to seconds fluctuations compose the temporal side of the intermittent nature of wind while the spatial part is caused by the difference in the geography, the topography, the altitude, and the sunshine. Mathematical explanation on how the kinetic energy of the wind can be converted to electrical power then the mechanics of the wind energy conversion system are discussed too in this chapter. As the wind turbines usually operate at a higher altitude than the height of which the wind speed was measured, wind shear is discussed with emphasizing the laws used to express it in Algeria. Finally, The Algerian electricity market was presented.

2.1 Sourcing power from the wind

Wind energy is an indirect form of solar energy. The sun heats more strongly the air in the equatorial regions than in other altitudes, thus the air becomes lighter and less dense. This warm air ascends and constitutes a low-pressure zone then it flows towards the poles where air near the surfaces is cooler. This movement makes the air cool and sinks forming a high-pressure zone. This horizontal pressure gradient drives the flow of air from high to low pressure, which determines the speed and the initial direction of wind motion [43].

The process by which the kinetic energy in the wind is converted to mechanical power is called wind energy or wind power. This mechanical power can be used for simple tasks like grinding grain or pumping water; or for more sophisticated tasks like generating electricity using a generator [44]. The use of wind as a power source is growing and spreading all over the globe, this is mainly because of the attractive features of this power source. These advantages are, the wind is a clean source of energy as it delivers electricity without producing carbon dioxide or sulfur dioxide who are linked to pollution, global warming, acid rain, and climate change; the wind is a sustainable, abundant power source and compatible with other land uses; wind can

Chapter 2 Wind energy and the power system in Algeria

boost the share of energy produced locally and diverse it, this will ensure national security. The factors that inhibit the growth of wind power are strongly linked to the intermittency nature of wind and the sites with good wind potential are often far from where electricity demand is; the sound of rotating wind turbine can be irritating; the rotating blades can endanger wildlife.

2.2 Wind variability

The most challenging aspect of wind is its high variability, both geographically and temporally. The spatial variability of wind makes some locations windier than others. Offshore and onshore winds, mountain and valley breezes result from the variation in the altitude, the proportion of land and sea, the size of landmasses, and the type of vegetation. The temporal variability of wind includes the annual, seasonal, synoptic, diurnal, turbulence changes that occur from year to year, with the season, with passing weather systems, daily, and from second to second respectively. Figure 6 shows the temporal variation of the wind speed at Brookhaven, New York constructed by Van der Hoven in 1957 [45]. Accurate prediction of these variations is primordial to ensure the reliability of the wind turbine electrical production [43]. To investigate the suitability of a site for a wind-based resource project, the wind-related properties must be identified to the fullest extent [46]. It is a common practice to use a probabilistic distribution to model the stochastic variation of wind this can facilitate the calculation of the amount of the annual power generation for a specific area [44]. The Weibull distribution in particular has been giving a good representation of the temporal variation of the wind speed [45].

Figure 6 Wind Spectrum Farm Brookhaven Based on Work by van der Hoven [45].

Chapter 2 Wind energy and the power system in Algeria

The following meteorological instruments are used for wind energy applications: anemometers to measure wind velocity, wind vanes to measure wind direction, thermometers to measure the ambient air temperature, and barometers to measure the air pressure [47]. Some use remote sensing instruments based on audio-frequency (SODAR) or laser light (LIDAR) technologies [48]. Figure 7 displays a cup anemometer (left) and a wind vane (right) [49].

Figure 7 Cup anemometer (left) and wind vane (right) [49].

In Algeria, the National Meteorological Office (ONM) mainly measures the wind speed using Cupules anemometers installed at 10 m AGL in open areas for long periods [16], [24]. the National Meteorological Office provides wind speed data on half-hourly, hourly, tri-horal, and daily resolutions and it is meant to primarily serve the transport industry, as most of the stations are located in the airfields or in urban sites [13]. The distribution of the meteorological stations in Algeria is shown in Figure 8 [15]. It can be noted that the number of the stations is relatively low in comparison to the country's high surface and the high dispersion of the stations in the Sahara might not capture its wind power potential effectively [15]. Another establishment that records the wind data specifically to serve developing renewable energy purposes in Algeria is the Renewable Energy Development Center (CDER). Some of their masts are installed at Adrar, Bousmail, Bouzaréah, Chlef, El-Hamdania, Ghardaia, and Laghouat. The time resolution of their wind velocity records ranges between 5 to 30 minutes and are

Chapter 2 Wind energy and the power system in Algeria

measured at 10 m AGL [29]. Moreover, the national electricity and gas enterprise Sonelgaz also measures wind speed data at 17 m AGL and averages it every ten minutes [30]. The only mast placed at 50 m AGL is located at Ksar-Chellala [16].

Figure 8 Distribution of meteorological stations over Algeria [15].

2.3 Wind energy conversion system

The wind turbine converts the kinetic energy of moving air mass to mechanical motion then to electricity. Equation (1) exhibits that the power in the wind P_w in watts (W) is a linear function to the air density ρ (kg/m^3) and the swept area of the rotating blades of the wind turbine A (m^2), and cubically dependent on the wind speed v in (m/s) [44].

$$P_w = \frac{1}{2} \rho A v^3 \text{ (watts)} \quad (1)$$

The air density ρ is the weight of air per unit volume and it decreases with increasing temperature and increasing altitude [50]. The air density is calculated as indicated in the following expression, where P is the air pressure in Pascal, R is the specific gas constant of air 287.05 J/Kg and T is the air temperature in degrees Kelvin [51]. In most practical cases

Chapter 2 Wind energy and the power system in Algeria

$\rho = 1.225 \text{ Kg/m}^3$ may be taken [49]. However Louassa et al. found that Adrar's meteorological station has an air density of 1.22 Kg/m^3 [52].

$$P = \frac{\rho}{RT} (\text{Kg/m}^3)$$

The swept area A is calculated as indicated in the following expression where l is the length of the wind turbine's blade and r is the radius of the hub [53]. Figure 9 shows the swept area of wind turbine blades [53].

$$A = \pi[(l + r)^2 - r^2] (\text{m}^2)$$

Figure 9 Swept area of wind turbine blades [53].

P_w describes the total power in the wind, however not all this power is going to be extracted as some power is left in the downstream air which continues to move with reduced speed [46]. The power coefficient C_p quantifies the efficiency of the wind turbine in extracting power from the wind to convert it into mechanical work. C_p has a theoretical maximum value that is called Betz limit and it equals 59,3% [46], [54]. Incremental improvements in the wind turbine design are continually pursued to increase C_p [45]. The C_p of modern wind turbines ranges between 45% and 50% [46].

A common index that evaluates the wind resource in a particular site is wind power density (WPD). It is defined as the available wind power in airflow through a perpendicular cross-

sectional unit area in a unit time period [53], it is given by the expression (2). Calculating WPD enables nominating the optimum wind turbine for the site [55].

$$WPD = \frac{P_w}{A} = \frac{1}{2} \rho v^3 \quad (\text{W/m}^2) \quad (2)$$

Equation (2) depends on the frequency of each velocity, for a specified theoretical probability distribution $f(v)$, therefore the mean WPD can be expressed as [56]

$$WPD = \frac{1}{2} \rho \int_0^{\infty} v^3 f(v) dv \quad (3)$$

The most probable wind speed (v_{mp}) is simply the mode of the wind speeds (M_o), while the maximum energy-carrying wind speed (v_{maxE}), which is also known as the optimum wind speed, is the speed that produces most of the energy. To guarantee maximum energy output, the selected wind turbine should have rated wind speed (v_r) close to v_{mp} and v_{maxE} [30], [51], [57].

The power curve of a wind turbine describes the relationship between its power output and wind speed [43]. The cut-in speed v_{ci} is the minimum speed at which the production of electricity begins, the generated electrical power increases gradually until it reaches a maximum value called the rated power P_r that corresponds the rated wind speed v_r [46]. High wind speeds can cause structural damage to the wind turbine so the rotor is brought to a standstill by a brake beyond a particular wind speed called the cut-out speed v_{co} [46]. Figure 10 and Table 3 show the power curve and the parameters of Gamesa G52 0.85 MW wind turbine used in Adrar's wind farm, which is the only Algerian wind farm [27].

Figure 10 Power curve for Gamesa G52 0.85 MW wind turbine [27].

Table 3 Gamesa G52 wind turbine parameters [27]

Model	Parameters	Gamesa G52
Rated power (kW)	P_r	850
Rotor diameter (m)	l	52
Hub height (m)	Z_2	55
Swept area of rotor (m ²)	A	2122
Cut-in wind speed (m/s)	v_{ci}	4
Rated wind speed (m/s)	v_r	15
Cut-out wind speed (m/s)	v_{co}	28

Maximum efficiency of a wind turbine can be achieved by matching v_{ci} , v_r and v_{co} wind speeds; and P_r to the site wind characteristics. However, this is not always applicable; therefore it is crucial to select these parameters to enlarge the delivered energy for a given amount of available wind energy. The capacity factor C_f measures the strength of the agreement between the wind turbine system and the environment [58]. C_f is the actual power output of a wind turbine over a period of time divided by its power output if the turbine has operated the entire time. As a thumb rule, a wind turbine that has $C_f \geq 25\%$ would be recommended to use as WECS in the investigated site [59]. The integral expressed in Equation (4) should be solved to find C_f [46]. The actual power produced by a wind turbine (P_{out}) is given Equation (5) [15]

$$C_f = \frac{1}{v_r^3} \int_{v_{ci}}^{v_r} v^3 f(v) dv + \int_{v_r}^{v_{co}} f(v) dv \quad (4)$$

$$P_{out} = P_r C_f \quad (5)$$

The wind turbine annual energy production (AEP) can be calculated as shown in equation (6) where $t = 8760 h$ [60].

$$AEP = P_{out} t \quad (6)$$

2.4 Wind turbines mechanics

Wind turbines are generally classified into two categories horizontal and vertical wind turbines, depending on whether the axis of rotation is horizontal or perpendicular to the ground. Horizontal wind turbines make the majority of the commercial wind turbines because they have low cut-in wind speed, easy furling, and have higher power coefficient C_p . Figure 11 outlines the classification of different wind turbines according to their efficiency measured by C_p . Horizontal wind turbines can be further sub-grouped according to the number of blades and the direction of receiving the wind. Nowadays three blades wind turbines are the most popular turbines used for generating electricity [49], [61].

Figure 11 Classification of wind turbines [61]

Chapter 2 Wind energy and the power system in Algeria

Wind turbines are usually aggregated to a cluster known as a wind farm or wind park. Electrically and commercially tying wind turbines together in a windy site maximizes the total wind energy produced and minimizes the maintenance and operation costs [47]. Figure 12 shows the major wind turbine components. The wind turbine consists of blades rotating around a hub to capture power from the wind and convert it to mechanical power, the hub is linked to the nacelle that houses a gearbox and a generator to convert the mechanical power to electricity. The gearbox acts as a rotational speed increaser while the generator is the electromechanical component responsible for producing alternating current electricity. The power electronic interface such as the frequency converter transforms the alternating current electricity to direct current electricity and feeds it to the local power grid [44], [46].

Figure 12 Major wind turbine components [44].

2.5 Wind shear

The variation of wind speed with altitude is known as wind shear [43]. Generally, the wind speed increases with height; this is why modern wind turbines are taller. Wind speed data are not always recorded at the hub height so it is imperative to estimate the vertical wind profile [47]. Several laws exist in the literature to extrapolate the wind speed at the desired height. The commonly used extrapolation laws in Algeria are the power law and the logarithmic law

Chapter 2 Wind energy and the power system in Algeria

expressed in Equations (7) and (8) respectively, where v_2 is the wind speed at the hub height Z_2 , v_1 is the measured wind speed at height Z_1 which is usually 10 m, the exponent m depends on the roughness of the surface and Z_0 is the roughness length [62]. $m = 1/7$ when no wind shear coefficient measurements are available this is known as the 1/7 wind power law [26], [30], [59]. An advantage of using W2 to model the wind speed data is the ability to adjust the shape (β) and the scale (α) parameters to any height other than the mast height [32], [54].

$$v_2 = v_1 \left(\frac{Z_2}{Z_1} \right)^m \quad (7)$$

$$v_2 = v_1 \frac{\ln(Z_2/Z_0)}{\ln(Z_1/Z_0)} \quad (8)$$

Table 4 shows the variations of Z_0 with the Algerian topography [16]. It can be seen that Z_0 varies between 0.00001 m in the Sahara to 0.5 m in the Tellian Atlas [16]. Among the non-exhaustive list of the assessed Algerian studies in Table 2, the power law is the most adopted law to extrapolate wind speed measurements to higher altitude [11], [15], [24], [34]; followed by the logarithmic law [16], [28], [30]; the 1/7 power law [26], [27] then the method that directly extrapolates W2 parameters [32].

Table 4 Roughness length (Z_0) according to the geography condition in Algeria [16]

Geography condition	Roughness length (Z_0)
Littoral/coast	0.01 – 0.04
Tellian Atlas	0.01 – 0.5
Tellian high plains	0.02 – 0.03
High steppe plains	0.03
Highlands	0.01
Saharan Atlas	0.01 – 0.08
Sahara	0.00001 – 0.1

2.6 Power variability

The mission of the power plants is to meet the electrical energy demand of the consumers. Ensuring balanced and reliable supply with load demand can be challenging when fueling the power plants by non-dispatchable renewables such as wind and solar PV given their stochastic

Chapter 2 Wind energy and the power system in Algeria

nature both in time and space. In the case of wind, the output of WECS is sensitive to the smallest changes in the wind speed because of the cubic dependency of the wind power to the wind velocity. This may have a detrimental effect on the power systems that are penetrated by the wind to a significant level, thus it is imperative to comprehend the short, medium, and long-term variations of the wind speed [43], [46]. There are three events that grid operators expect to run into when using wind as a power source, low wind meeting high electricity demand, high wind at times of low demand, and wind speed that swiftly fluctuates which is known as ramping events [63].

The wind power is indifferent to the changes in the wind speed beyond the rated speed v_r (15 – 25 m/s), however substantial power changes will result when the variations occur within the band cut-in v_{ci} and rated v_r speeds (4 – 15 m/s). Geographical dispersion of wind farms will ensure, to an extent, a stable and reliable power supply as the wind increments in one site decrements in another assuming the wind farms are installed in largely uncorrelated sites [64]. Wind speed exhibits more changes hourly and daily than from minute to minute due to shifting weather patterns. The effect of these changes on the power output can be substantially mitigated by interconnecting wind farms that are geographically dispersed because the average wind speed from all the wind farms is smoother than those measured individually [43].

Various sites in Algeria are characterized by having an annual average wind speed higher than 5 m/s at 10 m AGL such as Mechria, Bou-Chekif, Tiaret, Djelfa, and M'sila in the highlands; Hassi-R'mel in the Northern Sahara; Tindouf, Adrar, Timimoun in Western Sahara and; and In-Salah in the Central Sahara [16], [33]. The geographical dispersion of these sites can improve the integration of wind in the Algerian energy mix.

2.7 Electricity production and the national power grid

The annual electrical production in Algeria rose from 12.3 TWh in 1985 to 78.8 TWh in 2020 as displayed in Figure 13. This rapid growth comes to meet the increasing demand for electricity as it is expected to reach 126 TWh by 2028 [9]. Half of the demand for electricity in Algeria comes

Chapter 2 Wind energy and the power system in Algeria

from the residential sector because of the weak industry activity, growing population by 2% annually, the rising penetration rate of electricity, and gas and the increasing number of hot days per year which led to the profuse of air conditioners [65]. The state-owned company Sonelgaz is the main producer of electricity in Algeria. The installed cumulative power generation capacity by Sonelgaz and its subsidiaries reached 20963 MW in 2018, and it was powered by approximately 90% natural gas as previously illustrated in Figure 3 [10]. The price of electricity produced by Sonelgaz for domestic consumers is \$0.054/ kWh [59], [66], [67].

Figure 13 Electricity production between 1985 and 2020 in Algeria [68]

The Algerian power grid is composed of three networks. The national interconnected power grid (RIN) covers the Northern region and extends to Bechar, Ghardaia, and Hassi-Messaoud cities in the South. The national interconnected power grid (RIN) is supplied by 40 electricity power stations and connected via 220 kV and 400 kV lines as illustrated in Figure 14 [69]. The second network is the isolated pole network that connects the cities of In-Salah, Adrar, and Timimoun (PIAT). In-Salah and Adrar power stations power the PIAT pole. The third network is composed of small networks dispersed over 26 isolated Saharan sites (RIS) [10], [16]. The Algerian electricity market is considered important as it is expected to reach 36 GW in 2028

Chapter 2 Wind energy and the power system in Algeria

from 20 GW in 2018, and it grows by 6% annually [9], [10], [70]. The covering capacity for the electricity installations network in Algeria amounts to 96% [70].

Figure 14 The national interconnected power grid (RIN), 220 and 400 kV transmission lines [69]

Using wind to generate electricity in Algeria goes back to 1957 when the country was colonized by the French. A 100 kW wind turbine was installed at the Grands Vents site in Algiers [71]. However, the first significant project that exploits wind as a power source is the pilot project of a 10.2 MW wind farm located in Kaberten, 70 km north of Adrar city. The farm consists of one row of 12 wind turbines of Gamesa G52 0.85 MW facing the main wind direction. The distance between the turbines is four times the rotor diameter. A centralized system called SCADA is used to control and acquire the wind turbine production data that are recorded every 15 minutes. Gamesa G52 operates in a maximum ambient operating temperature of 46°C. The total investment cost was €24 million and it produces electricity at at €0.094/ kWh. Adrar's wind farm was installed in 2011 and became operational in late 2014. The only wind farm in Algeria secured 0.87% of the country's electrical needs in 2018 [10], [26], [31], [33], [72].

In this study, the site of In-Salah was chosen for two reasons. First, it is the windiest site in Algeria according to the latest wind atlas. The second reason is that In-Salah alongside Adrar

and Timimoun sites constitute an isolated pole network that is already familiar with the wind energy via Adrar's wind farm.

2.8 Economics of wind energy

Capital and investment cost, operation and maintenance (O&M) cost, and fuel cost are the three main components that affect the cost of electricity. Luckily the cost for fuel for wind is zero however capital and investment cost is high and considered as the most serious drawback [46]. Many factors influence the cost of wind-produced electricity like wind speed and topography of the site, infrastructure, closeness to transmission lines, grid connection, tax incentives, improved technology including taller towers and lighter blades and, the prices of competitive power sources for electricity such as coal and natural gas [46].

The Levelized Cost of Electricity (*LCOE*) is a useful metric to quantify the cost of electricity generated by different power sources. The levelized cost of electricity is given in equations (9) [31], [46]. I is the investment cost, C_{OMR} is the O&M and repair costs, maintenance and repair cost, i is the inflation rate, r is the interest rate, t is the lifetime of the machine (in years) and S is the scrap value. The levelized cost of electricity is defined as the present value of the price of the produced electrical energy considering the economic life of the plant and the costs incurred in the construction, operation and maintenance, and the fuel costs divided by the total annual energy production (*AEP*) during the lifetime of the plant (typically 20 years for wind generators) [46]. The cost of a wind turbine depends on its rated power P_r and the manufacturing company. It can be determined as the specific cost of the wind turbine times its rated power as shown in Table 5 [59]. I , C_{OMR} and S expenses are function to the initial cost of the wind turbine (I).

$$LCOE = \left[I + C_{OMR} \left(\frac{1+i}{r-i} \right) \left(1 - \left(\frac{1+i}{1+r} \right)^t \right) - S \left(\frac{1+i}{1+r} \right)^t \right] / AEP_{20} \quad (9)$$

Chapter 2 Wind energy and the power system in Algeria

Table 5 Range of specific cost of wind turbines based on the rated power [59]

Wind turbine size (kW)	Average specific cost (\$/kWh)
< 20	2600
20 – 200	1775
200 >	1150

Figure 15 shows the evolution of the capacity factor (C_f) and the levelized cost of electricity ($LCOE$) of renewable resources by type over the decade 2010 – 2020 in the world [73]. It was concluded from Figure 1 that even though wind and solar PV have almost similar shares in the installed renewable capacity (24.86% and 21.24% respectively) yet their contribution in the worldwide electricity generation differs tremendously (5.5% and 2.4% respectively). This is due to the difference in their capacity factors. Figure 15 (A) shows that onshore wind has higher capacity factor than solar PV, meaning that the extracted power from wind exceeds what can be generated from solar PV. However they both have low capacity factors in comparison to the other renewables because they are non-dispatchable renewables, thus continuous flow of power from wind or solar PV is hard to maintain. Nonetheless, the advantage of using wind to generate electricity is it has the minimum global weighted average utility-scale as is depicted in Figure 15 (B) [8].

Algeria counts on solar PV to produce most of its renewable electricity [72]. The installation of the aimed solar PV power capacity is going slow yet steady. Unfortunately, this cannot be said on the wind as there have not been any new installations since 2014 to deploy wind as a power source. The same importance should have been given to wind power projects as onshore wind produces more power at a lower cost than solar PV.

The number of solar PV power stations rose from the pilot project of 1.1 MW installed at Ghardaia in 2014 to 21 stations by June 2018 with a cumulative installed power capacity of 344.1 MW [10]. The PV solar power stations were dispersed as 10 stations in the highlands (265 MW) and 11 power stations in the Sahara (79.1 MW). Furthermore, another solar PV project of installing 50 MW at Biskra was approved in 2019. The project consists of installing five power

Chapter 2 Wind energy and the power system in Algeria

stations with 10 MW power capacity each at Biskra to be sold at a fixed price of 8.28 DA/kWh [72].

Figure 15 (A) Global weighted average utility scale capacity factor by technology 2010-2020 in the world and (B) Global weighted average utility scale LCOE by technology 2010-2020 in the world [8]

Table 6 displays the capacity factor (C_f) and the levelized cost of electricity ($LCOE$) for wind energy in Algeria. It is evident that C_f and $LCOE$ have an inverse relationship. The economic studies in these papers revealed that using WECS is economically feasible in Tiaret [24], Oran [30], Hassi-R'mel [15], Adrar [11], [28], [31], [34], [54], [59] and In-Salah [31] because the cost of electricity derived from wind in these sites is competitive in comparison to the tariff practiced by Sonelgaz (c\$5.4 /kWh).

Chapter 2 Wind energy and the power system in Algeria

Table 6 The capacity factor (C_f) and the levelized cost of electricity ($LCOE$) for wind energy in Algeria

Studies	Year	Sites	C_f (%)	$LCOE$ (c\$/kWh)
Belabes <i>et al.</i> [24]	2015	Milian, Oran, Setif, Skikda, Tiaret and Tlemcen	5.40 (Tlemcen) to 33.16 (Tiaret)	3.42 (Tiaret) to 21.05 (Tlemcen)
Boudia <i>et al.</i> [30]	2015	Oran	51.36	1.81
Boudia <i>et al.</i> [15]	2016	Adrar, Hassi-R'mel, In-Salah and Tindouf	18.2 (Adrar) to 31 (Hassi-R'mel)	2.8 (Hassi-R'mel) to 4.8 (Adrar)
Diaf <i>et al.</i> [59]	2013	Adrar, Bechar, Ghardaia, In-Amenas and Tamanrasset	10.72 (Tamanrasset) to 48.48 (Adrar)	2.04 (Adrar) to 9.23 (Tamanrasset)
Diaf <i>et al.</i> [54]	2013	13 sites	1.91 (Skikda) to 48.48 (Adrar)	1.79 (Adrar) to 45.46 (Skikda)
Himri <i>et al.</i> [11]	2008	Adrar, Timimoun and Tindouf	21 (Tindouf) to 32 (Adrar)	3.1 (Adrar) to 6.6 (Tindouf)
Himri <i>et al.</i> [34]	2020	Adrar	36	3.25
Mezidi <i>et al.</i> [31]	2020	Adrar and In-Salah	35.72 (Adrar) 55.66 (In-Salah)	4.97 – 6.42 (Adrar) 2.85 – 3.67 (In-Salah)
Saheb Koussa <i>et al.</i> [28]	2016	13 sites	16.6 (Bejaia) to 66 (Adrar)	3 (Adrar) to 22 (Bejaia)

2.9 Algerian Establishments to develop the renewable energies

The establishments that are involved in developing renewable energies in Algeria are:

- Sonelgaz is a state-owned company that the electricity industry revolves around. Until recently it was the only player in the electricity market. It has been established since 1947 to transport, transfer and distribute electricity; and transfer and distribute gas [12].
- CDER is the Renewable Energy Development Center. It was created in 1986 as a scientific and technological institution and it is situated in Algiers. However, it has three units, the solar equipment development unit located in Tipaza, the unit of research in applied renewable energies in Ghardaia, and the unit of research in renewable energies

Chapter 2 Wind energy and the power system in Algeria

in the Saharan regions in Adrar. CDER was created to apply scientific research and develop technology in the sector of renewable energies [10].

- SKTM is the Electricity & Renewable Energy Company. It is a power generation company and a subsidiary of Sonelgaz. It is based in Ghardaia and was created in 2013 to install the renewable energy program and exploit isolated electricity networks in the south. SKTM installed 22 PV power plants with total capacity of 343 MWp between 2015 and 2017 [10], [74].
- IAER is The Algerian Renewable Energy Institute. It is a public institute that was created as a result of collaboration between the Scientific Ministry for Higher Education and Scientific Research (MESRS) and the Renewable Energy Development Center. It is responsible for facilitating access to scientific and technical information in the field of renewables [12].

Conclusion

In this chapter, wind as a power source was discussed. Although generating electricity from wind has many attractive features yet its intermittent nature can be problematic. It was explained that to model the temporal variability of wind, it is better to use probability distribution functions like the two-parameter Weibull to describe its changes. For the variation of the wind speed with altitude or simply the wind shear, the laws that describe these variations were given, and in the case of Algeria the power law and the logarithmic law are the most utilized laws. On the other hand, it was explained that the geographical dispersion of wind farms can be useful to minimize wind power variability. The Algerian electricity market and the institution that works on developing renewable energies were also tackled.

Chapter 3 Modeling the wind speed

Introduction

The probabilistic approach is primordial for the wind power assessment as it provides cheap and fast initial information for the decision-makers throughout simulations and estimations. It was stressed that selecting the appropriate probability density functions and the right estimation methods is essential for the wind energy assessment. It is not enough to use the average wind speed as an indicator to calculate the energy production because it is possible to have different parameters for the same average wind speed. It was demonstrated that the calculated energy production can vary up to 80% for the same average wind speed of 3.75 m/s, and the rotor diameter of 90 m. Although the two-parameter Weibull and the maximum likelihood method of estimation are by far the most utilized probabilistic tools to model the wind speed, yet not all wind regimes are better fitted by this model. The characteristics of the suggested alternatives to the two-parameter Weibull are given. This includes the three-parameter Weibull, the bimodal Weibull, and the Weibull-length-biased; and as for the parameter estimation methods, other frequentist methods and the Bayesian approach of estimation are discussed. The last section discusses the goodness-of-fit metrics needed to identify the model that has the minimum errors in modeling the wind speed.

3.1 Probability density functions

3.1.1 The two-parameter Weibull distribution (W2)

The two-parameter Weibull distribution has been extensively used to model the wind speed data since the 1970s [36]. This is highlighted by the fact that several computer modeling packages such as HOMER, WAsP, and WindSim base their wind statistics results on W2 [29], [36]. The popularity of W2 can be traced to its simplicity with only two parameters to estimate i.e. the scale (α) and the shape (β) parameters; its flexibility as it can mimic quite the range of other PDFs like the exponential ($\beta = 1$), the Rayleigh ($\beta = 2$), the lognormal ($\beta = 2.5$), and the normal ($\beta = 3.6$) PDFs [75]; its ability to describe the occurrences of high wind speeds (when $\beta < 3.6$) as the wind speed is perceived to be a positively skewed phenomenon [42]. W2 has been serving multiple purposes in the wind energy industry such as estimating the energy

output and the capacity factor of a wind turbine, variation of wind speed with height, wind velocity time series stochastic forecasting, bivariate analysis of wind speed, and direction and wind turbine breakdown analysis [36]. Table 7 shows the probabilistic properties of the two-parameter Weibull (W2) and the three-parameter Weibull (W3) distributions [75] where V (m/s) is a random variable that designates wind velocity, α (m/s) is the scale parameter, β is the unitless shape parameter. The wind potential at a particular site can be assessed by these parameters [57]. A high value of α implies that the average wind speed is high while β points out how dispersed the wind speeds around the mean. A low value of β indicates that the percentage of low wind speeds is high [57], [76] as depicted in Figure 16.

Figure 16 Two-parameter Weibull (W2) probability distribution

The cumulative distribution function $F(v)$ is practical when it comes to obtaining the probability of the availability factor $P(v_{ci} \leq V \leq v_{co})$ which equals to $F(v_{co}) - F(v_{ci})$ this calculates the probability that the wind turbine is operational [77]. The average mean wind speed can be estimated by $E(V)$. The median Me separates the upper half of high wind speeds from the lower half, so a large value of Me indicates that the site is windy. The mode (Mo) denotes the most prevailing wind speed in the area under investigation, it is also known as the most probable wind speed v_{mp} in wind energy literature [30], [78]. To guarantee maximum energy output, the selected wind turbine should have rated wind speed v_r close to v_{mp} [30],

Chapter 3 Modeling the wind speed

[51], [57]. The standard deviation $\delta(V)$ and the coefficient of variation CV measure how the wind speeds vary around the mean $E(V)$. The asymmetry and the tailedness of the wind speed are measured by skewness γ_1 and kurtosis γ_2 respectively [29]. A positive γ_1 means that the wind speeds are tapering on the right side of the peak i.e. the right tail is longer than the left tail. Unlike skewness that depicts which tail is more important, kurtosis weights the tails. A high value of γ_2 (higher than 3) means that wind speed data have more extreme high and low wind velocities. Most of these probabilistic characteristics of wind speed cannot be calculated without the r^{th} raw moment $E(V^r)$. The third raw moment $E(V^3)$, in particular, plays an important role in the wind energy industry because of the cubic dependency of the wind power to the wind speed [79].

Table 7 Probabilistic properties of for the two- and the three- parameter Weibull distributions [75].

	Two-parameter Weibull (W2)	Three-parameter Weibull (W3)
PDF	$f(v; \alpha, \beta) = \frac{\beta}{\alpha} \left(\frac{v}{\alpha}\right)^{\beta-1} e^{-\left(\frac{v}{\alpha}\right)^\beta}, v > 0; \alpha, \beta > 0$	$f(v; \tau, \alpha, \beta) = \frac{\beta}{\alpha} \left(\frac{v-\tau}{\alpha}\right)^{\beta-1} e^{-\left(\frac{v-\tau}{\alpha}\right)^\beta}, v \geq \tau > 0; \alpha, \beta > 0$
CDF	$F(v) = 1 - e^{-\left(\frac{v}{\alpha}\right)^\beta}$	$F(v) = 1 - e^{-\left(\frac{v-\tau}{\alpha}\right)^\beta}$
The r^{th} moment	$E(V^r) = \alpha^r \Gamma_r$	$E(V^r) = \sum_{i=0}^r C_r^i \tau^i \alpha^{r-i} \Gamma_{r-i}$
Mean	$E(V) = \alpha \Gamma_1$	$E(V) = \alpha \Gamma_1 + \tau$
Median	$Me = \alpha (\ln 2)^{\frac{1}{\beta}}$	$Me = \alpha (\ln 2)^{\frac{1}{\beta}} + \tau$
Mode	$M_0 = \begin{cases} \alpha \left(1 - \frac{1}{\beta}\right)^{\frac{1}{\beta}} & \text{for } \beta > 1 \\ 0 & \text{for } 0 < \beta \leq 1 \end{cases}$	$M_0 = \begin{cases} \alpha \left(1 - \frac{1}{\beta}\right)^{\frac{1}{\beta}} + \tau & \text{for } \beta > 1 \\ \tau & \text{for } 0 < \beta \leq 1 \end{cases}$
Standard deviation	$\delta(V) = \alpha \sqrt{[\Gamma_2 - \Gamma_1^2]}$	$\delta(V) = \alpha \sqrt{[\Gamma_2 - \Gamma_1^2]}$
Coefficient of variation	$CV = \frac{\sqrt{[\Gamma_2 - \Gamma_1^2]}}{\Gamma_1}$	$CV = \frac{\alpha \sqrt{[\Gamma_2 - \Gamma_1^2]}}{\alpha \Gamma_1 + \tau}$
The 3 rd moment	$E(V^3) = \alpha^3 \Gamma_3$	$E(V^3) = \alpha^3 \Gamma_3 + 3\tau \alpha^2 \Gamma_2 + 3\tau^2 \alpha \Gamma_1 + \tau^3$
Skewness	$\gamma_1 = \frac{\Gamma_3 - 3\Gamma_2 \Gamma_1 + 2\Gamma_1^3}{(\Gamma_2 - \Gamma_1^2)^{3/2}}$	$\gamma_1 = \frac{\Gamma_3 - 3\Gamma_2 \Gamma_1 + 2\Gamma_1^3}{(\Gamma_2 - \Gamma_1^2)^{3/2}}$
Kurtosis	$\gamma_2 = \frac{\Gamma_4 - 3\Gamma_1^4 + 6\Gamma_2 \Gamma_1^2 - 4\Gamma_1 \Gamma_3}{(\Gamma_2 - \Gamma_1^2)^2}$	$\gamma_2 = \frac{\Gamma_4 - 3\Gamma_1^4 + 6\Gamma_2 \Gamma_1^2 - 4\Gamma_1 \Gamma_3}{(\Gamma_2 - \Gamma_1^2)^2}$

Note: $\Gamma(x) = \int_0^\infty e^{-u} u^{x-1} dx, \Gamma_1 = \Gamma\left(1 + \frac{1}{\beta}\right)$.

Despite that W2 is widely accepted to model wind speed, yet numerous studies showed it cannot fit all the wind regimes in the world [23], [36]. W2 has poor fitness results when modeling wind speeds that are characterized by being bimodal or having low speed or a small range of variation [23]. Thus the search for suitable alternatives was the subject for several analyses. It is worth noting from Table 2 that most of the studies that investigated the wind energy potential in Algeria have solely used W2 even though that Algeria is a large country with different climates and topography that undoubtedly affects the behavior of wind.

3.1.2 The three-parameter Weibull (W3)

The fluctuations in wind speed can be better forecasted by modeling long-term time series of wind speed using Weibull distribution [31]. It was suggested to use W3 to model the wind speed data since the added location parameter theoretically increases the fitness of W3 in comparison to W2. The added location parameter τ (m/s) assesses the lower threshold of the wind speed [80]. The probabilistic characteristics of W3 are given in Table 7. Enlarging (reducing) τ causes a movement of the density to the right (to the left) [81] as illustrated in Figure 17.

Figure 17 Three-parameter Weibull (W2) probability distribution

Using W3 to substitute W2 in modeling the wind speed was first done by Stewart and Essenwanger [36] where the authors found that W3 is superior than the regular W2. Indeed W3 has better results especially when the probability of the null wind is high [82]. However, the drawback is the added parameter imposes challenges in the estimation process [64], because it has to be positive when it is associated with random variables defined on \mathbb{R}^+ such as the lifetime of an object or the wind speed [75].

3.1.3 The five-parameter bimodal Weibull mixture (WW)

Seasonal, climatic, regional, and diurnal variability of the wind and other meteorological variables like temperature, pressure, humidity, and wind direction can cause the bimodal or multimodal behavior of the wind. Sites that have witnessed such effects include Lesvos and Mykonos sites in Greece, La Ventosa in Mexico, Santa Elena in Colombia, Gran Canaria in Spain, and the Butler Grade site in the US [42], [83]–[85]. Using unimodal PDFs to model the wind speed in such cases will lead to incorrect results in calculating C_f and AEP thus overestimation or underestimation of the true levelized cost of electricity and erroneous feasibility study [83]. In their review paper, Jung and Schindler [23] stated that WW is the most used bimodal PDF to represent the wind speed data in the case of bimodality. Among the 46 studies that they evaluated, WW was applied 13 times and recommended to be used five times in modeling the wind speed. It was found the suitability of WW is not restricted to the bimodal wind speed histograms but also extends to the unimodal cases [36]. In addition to the homogeneous bimodal Weibull (WW), heterogeneous bimodal Weibull that coupled W2 with other PDFs such as gamma, normal, and generalized extreme value were deployed in modeling the wind speed [23], [36]. It should be mentioned that bimodal PDFs have never been applied to estimate the wind power potential in Algeria.

Table 8 exhibits the probabilistic properties of WW where V_i ($i = 1,2$) are independently distributed as two parameter Weibull distribution $f(v; \alpha_i, \beta_i)$. A random variable V that is distributed as V_i with a mixing parameter ω_i (such that $\omega_1 + \omega_2 = 1, 0 \leq \omega_i \leq 1$) is said to have a two component mixture Weibull. WW depends on two scale parameters (α_1, α_2), two shape parameters (β_1, β_2) and a mixing parameter (ω) [36], [86] as shown in Figure 18.

Table 8 Probabilistic properties of the five-parameter homogeneous bimodal Weibull [36], [42], [83]–[86]

Five-parameter homogeneous bimodal Weibull (WW)	
PDF	$f(v; \alpha_1, \beta_1, \alpha_2, \beta_2, \omega) = \omega \left\{ \frac{\beta_1}{\alpha_1} \left(\frac{v}{\alpha_1} \right)^{\beta_1 - 1} e^{-\left(\frac{v}{\alpha_1} \right)^{\beta_1}} \right\} + (1 - \omega) \left\{ \frac{\beta_2}{\alpha_2} \left(\frac{v}{\alpha_2} \right)^{\beta_2 - 1} e^{-\left(\frac{v}{\alpha_2} \right)^{\beta_2}} \right\},$ $v > 0; \alpha_1, \beta_1, \alpha_2, \beta_2 > 0; 0 \leq \omega \leq 1$
CDF	$F(v; \alpha_1, \beta_1, \alpha_2, \beta_2, \omega) = \omega \left\{ 1 - e^{-\left(\frac{v}{\alpha_1} \right)^{\beta_1}} \right\} + (1 - \omega) \left\{ 1 - e^{-\left(\frac{v}{\alpha_2} \right)^{\beta_2}} \right\}$
The r^{th} moment	$E(V^r) = \omega \alpha_1^r \Gamma_r^1 + (1 - \omega) \alpha_2^r \Gamma_r^2$
Mean	$E(V) = \omega \alpha_1 \Gamma_1^1 + (1 - \omega) \alpha_2 \Gamma_1^2$
Mode	$M_0 = \begin{cases} \alpha_i \left(1 - \frac{1}{\beta_i} \right)^{\frac{1}{\beta_i}} & \text{for } \beta_i > 1; i = \overline{1,2} \\ 0 & \text{for } 0 < \beta_i \leq 1 \end{cases}$
Standard deviation	$\delta(V) = \omega \alpha_1 \sqrt{[\Gamma_2^1 - (\Gamma_1^1)^2]} + (1 - \omega) \alpha_2 \sqrt{[\Gamma_2^2 - (\Gamma_1^2)^2]}$
Coefficient of variation	$CV = \frac{\omega \alpha_1 \sqrt{[\Gamma_2^1 - (\Gamma_1^1)^2]} + (1 - \omega) \alpha_2 \sqrt{[\Gamma_2^2 - (\Gamma_1^2)^2]}}{\omega \alpha_1 \Gamma_1^1 + (1 - \omega) \alpha_2 \Gamma_1^2}$
The 3 rd moment	$E(V^3) = \omega \alpha_1^3 \Gamma_3^1 + (1 - \omega) \alpha_2^3 \Gamma_3^2$

Note: $\Gamma(x) = \int_0^\infty e^{-u} u^{x-1} dx$, $\Gamma_i^j = \Gamma\left(1 + \frac{j}{\beta_i}\right)$.

Figure 18 Five-parameter bimodal Weibull (W2) probability distribution

3.1.4 The Weibull – length – biased distribution (WLB)

Given the appealing properties of W2 that makes it one of the most used PDFs in engineering, hydrological, ecological, environmental, and energy studies [87]. There were many transformations over the years to W2 to suit predetermined purposes. Examples of these

modifications on W2 include the inverse Weibull, the truncated Weibull, the discrete Weibull, the reflected Weibull, the log-Weibull, and a variety of extensions of Weibull with four or five parameters [75]. In the wind power industry, Akgül *et al.* [87] compared the usual two-parameter Weibull with the two-parameter inverse Weibull. The authors found that the two-parameter inverse Weibull provided a better fit to six of the eight wind speed samples observed in Turkey. The authors explained the outperformed of the two-parameter inverse Weibull over W2 by the fact that it has a longer or heavier right tail. Similar to Akgül *et al.*, Kantar and Usta [88] employed the upper-truncated Weibull to model the wind speed data since observed wind speed occurrences are limited to a maximum value of wind speed value. The upper-truncated Weibull showed better performance than W2 in most of the samples of wind velocity dataset in three Turkish meteorological stations.

Like the inverse Weibull and the upper-truncated Weibull, the Weibull-length-biased distribution (WLB) is another transformation of W2. Length biased data occurs when every unit in the population does not have the same chance to be sampled [89]. Length biased distribution is a particular case of the more general weighted distributions which were first introduced by Fisher (1934) then developed by Rao (1965) [90]. Let X be a continuous nonnegative random variable with PDF $f(x)$, and let $w(X), x \geq 0$ be a positive function, and assume that the expectation of $w(X)$ is positive and finite.

$$0 < E(w(X)) := \int_0^{\infty} w(x)f(x) dx < \infty$$

The weighted random variable X_w is defined by specifying its PDF

$$f_w(x) = \frac{w(x)f(x)}{E(w(X))}, x \geq 0 \tag{10}$$

the weighted version of X $f_w(x)$ is as shown in Equation (10) where $E(w(X))$ is the expectation of $w(X)$ [91]. In addition to the well-known type I and type II errors, Type III error is the error made when an ordinary PDF is used instead of the length-biased version and it was studied by Gupta and Tripathi (1990) [92]. Length-biased PDFs have many applications in econometrics, survival analysis, renewal processes, biomedicine, and physics [93]. The reader is referred to reference [89] for more information on the length biased sampling.

Chapter 3 Modeling the wind speed

The length-biased version of Weibull gives the tails more weight than the base in comparison to the ordinary W2 [94]. This feature, in particular, might be useful in modeling the wind speed since it is usually heavily skewed to the right. The relationship between WLB and W2 is expressed in equation (11). The properties of WLB were studied by Boudrissa *et al.* [92] and presented in Table 9.

$$f_{WLB}(v) = \frac{vf_{W2}(v)}{E_{W2}(V)} \quad (11)$$

Table 9 probabilistic properties of the two-parameter Weibull-length-biased distribution [92]

Two-parameter Weibull-length-biased (WLB)	
PDF	$f(v; \lambda, \beta) = \beta^2 v^{\beta-1} e^{-\frac{v^\beta}{\lambda}} / \lambda^{1+\frac{1}{\beta}} \Gamma(\frac{1}{\beta}), v > 0; \lambda, \beta > 0$
CDF	$F(v) = \beta \gamma \left(1 + \frac{1}{\beta}, \frac{v^\beta}{\lambda}\right) / \Gamma(\frac{1}{\beta}), v > 0; \lambda, \beta > 0$
The r^{th} moment	$E(V^r) = (r+1) \lambda^{\frac{r}{\beta}} \Gamma(\frac{r+1}{\beta}) / \Gamma(\frac{1}{\beta})$
Mean	$E(V) = 2 \lambda^{\frac{1}{\beta}} \Gamma(\frac{2}{\beta}) / \Gamma(\frac{1}{\beta})$
Mode	$Mo = \left(\frac{1}{\lambda}\right)^{\frac{1}{\beta}}$
Standard deviation	$\delta(V) = \lambda^{\frac{1}{\beta}} \sqrt{\left[3\Gamma(\frac{3}{\beta}) \Gamma(\frac{1}{\beta}) - 4\Gamma^2(\frac{2}{\beta})\right]} / \Gamma(\frac{1}{\beta})$
Coefficient of variation	$CV = \sqrt{\left[3\Gamma(\frac{3}{\beta}) \Gamma(\frac{1}{\beta}) - 4\Gamma^2(\frac{2}{\beta})\right]} / 2 \lambda^{\frac{1}{\beta}} \Gamma(\frac{2}{\beta})$
The 3rd moment	$E(V^3) = 4 \lambda^{\frac{3}{\beta}} \Gamma(\frac{4}{\beta}) / \Gamma(\frac{1}{\beta})$
Skewness	$\gamma_1 = \left[4\Gamma(\frac{4}{\beta}) \Gamma^2(\frac{1}{\beta}) - 18\Gamma(\frac{3}{\beta}) \Gamma(\frac{2}{\beta}) \Gamma(\frac{1}{\beta}) + 16\Gamma^3(\frac{2}{\beta})\right] / \left[3\Gamma(\frac{3}{\beta}) \Gamma(\frac{1}{\beta}) - 4\Gamma^2(\frac{2}{\beta})\right]^{3/2}$
Kurtosis	$\gamma_2 = \left[\left(5\Gamma(\frac{5}{\beta}) \Gamma^3(\frac{1}{\beta}) - 32\Gamma(\frac{4}{\beta}) \Gamma(\frac{2}{\beta}) \Gamma^2(\frac{1}{\beta})\right) + \left(72\Gamma(\frac{3}{\beta}) \Gamma^2(\frac{2}{\beta}) \Gamma(\frac{1}{\beta}) - 48\Gamma^4(\frac{2}{\beta})\right) \right] / \left[3\Gamma(\frac{3}{\beta}) \Gamma(\frac{1}{\beta}) - 4\Gamma^2(\frac{2}{\beta})\right]^2$

Note: $\Gamma(x) = \int_0^\infty e^{-u} u^{x-1} du$, $\Gamma_1 = \Gamma\left(1 + \frac{1}{\beta}\right)$, $\lambda = \alpha^\beta$ and $\gamma(a, x) = \int_0^x t^{a-1} e^{-t} dt$.

As we can see from Table 9 and Figure 19, the coefficients of skewness and kurtosis are functions of the shape parameter β only. The WLB distribution is symmetric for $\beta = 3.448$, positively skewed with a tail to the right for values $\beta < 3.448$ which might be interesting for

wind power applications, and negatively skewed with a tail to the left for $\beta > 3.448$. The Kurtosis is positive for values of the shape parameter that are $\beta \leq 2.164$ or $\beta > 5.455$ [92].

Figure 19 Length-biased-Weibull (WLB) vs. two-parameter Weibull (W2) probability distribution

3.2 Frequentist estimation methods

The frequentist methods of estimation have been extensively analyzed and compared in the wind energy literature as shown in Figure 5. All the PEMs utilized in Algeria are classical methods as well as the PEMs reviewed by Carta *et al.* [36] and Jung and Schindler [23]. However, the most utilized PEMs are the maximum likelihood method (MLM), the least-squares estimation method (LSE), the method of moments (MOM) and, the L-moments method (LMOM).

3.2.1 The maximum likelihood method (MLM)

MLM is one of the most popular and reliable point estimation methods. This numerical method consists of finding the parameters' estimates that maximize the value of the probability of the randomly observed sample or the likelihood function $L(v; \theta)$ [36]. The likelihood of independent sample size n is expressed in Equation (12) where v_i is an observation of the wind speed with a density function $f(v_i; \theta)$ and a vector of unknown parameters θ [75]. The idea of MLM is to find the estimates of θ that maximize $L(v; \theta)$ or the log-likelihood function $LL(v; \theta)$

to ease the process of forming of the derivatives. The MLM estimates for the suggested PDFs are displayed in Table 10.

$$L(v; \theta) = \prod_{i=1}^n f(v_i; \theta) \tag{12}$$

$$LL(v; \theta) = \log(L(v; \theta)) \tag{13}$$

Table 10 Maximum likelihood method (MLM) to estimate the parameters of the two-parameter and the three-parameter Weibull distributions

PDF	Parameters	Estimates
$W2_{MLM}$	Scale ($\hat{\alpha}_{MLM}$), shape ($\hat{\beta}_{MLM}$)	$argmax_{\alpha, \beta} \left[n \ln \beta - n \ln \lambda + (\beta - 1) \sum_{i=1}^n \ln v_i - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n v_i^\beta}{\lambda} \right]$
$W3_{MLM}$	Scale ($\hat{\alpha}_{MLM}$), shape ($\hat{\beta}_{MLM}$), shift ($\hat{\tau}_{MLM}$)	$argmax_{\alpha, \beta, \tau} \left[n \ln \beta - n \ln \lambda + (\beta - 1) \sum_{i=1}^n \ln(v_i - \tau) - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (v_i - \tau)^\beta}{\lambda} \right]; v \geq \tau > 0$

Note: $\Gamma(x) = \int_0^\infty e^{-u} u^{x-1} dx$, $\Gamma_i = \Gamma\left(1 + \frac{i}{\beta}\right)$, $\lambda = \alpha^\beta$

Finding a suitable estimate to the location parameter τ is challenging as discussed by Carta *et al.* [36] and Stewart and Essenwanger [77]. Despite being widely used PEM, using the maximum likelihood method for W3 is problematic as there are no guarantees that τ will remain non-negative and stay below its upper bound $v_{(1)}$ [75], [95]–[97]. The major problem when using MLM to estimate the parameters of W3 is that the regularity conditions are not met because the domain of definition of random variable V is governed by the location parameter ($v \geq \tau$). Moreover, it was reported that MLM estimates become inconsistent when $\beta \leq 1$ as there may be more than one solution, the estimates may not be normal distributed when $1 < \beta \leq 2$, and the estimates are considered effective when $\beta > 2$ and the sample size is high [98].

Cohen & Whitten [99] proposed the modified maximum likelihood (MML), which has five types, and the modified moments (MM), which has three types, methods to overcome the problem caused by the maximum likelihood. The modified maximum likelihood and the modified moments are a combination between the maximum likelihood method and the method of moments and use some sample statistics. MML1, MML2, MM1 and MM2 are based on the minimum observed value (v_1), MML3 and MML4 are computed using the average (\bar{v}) and the

variance (S^2) of observed wind speed respectively, MML5 and MM3 use the median (v_{Me}) of the observed data. Some of the estimates produced by The modified maximum likelihood and the modified moments are easy to compute, less biased, and benefit from the pros and avoid the cons of the maximum likelihood method and the moments method [75], [100]. In this study only MML1 and MM2 were used as they gave the most satisfactory results.

Table 11 Modified maximum likelihood (MML) and modified moments (MM) methods to estimate the parameters of the three-parameter Weibull distributions

PDF	Parameters	Estimates
$W3_{MML}$	Scale ($\hat{\alpha}$), shape ($\hat{\beta}$), shift ($\hat{\tau}$)	$argmax_{\alpha,\beta} \left[\frac{n}{\beta} + \sum_{i=1}^n \ln(v_i - \tau) - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n \ln(v_i - \tau)(v_i - \tau)^\beta}{\lambda} = 0 \right]; 1 - e^{-\left(\frac{v(i) - \tau}{\alpha}\right)^\beta} = \frac{1}{n+1}$
$W3_{MM}$	Scale ($\hat{\alpha}$), shape ($\hat{\beta}$), shift ($\hat{\tau}$)	$\frac{[\Gamma_2 - \Gamma_1^2]}{\Gamma_1^2 [1 - n^{-1/\beta}]^2} = \frac{S^2}{(\bar{v} - v_{(1)})^2}; \alpha^2 [\Gamma_2 - \Gamma_1^2] = S^2; \alpha \Gamma_1 + \tau = \bar{v}$

Note: $\Gamma(x) = \int_0^\infty e^{-u} u^{x-1} dx$, $\Gamma_i = \Gamma\left(1 + \frac{i}{\beta}\right)$, $\lambda = \alpha^\beta$

3.2.2 The least-squares estimation method (LSE)

LSE is considered as an alternative to MLM, yet it has less optimum desirable characteristics than MLM. To find the least-squares estimates, the sum of the squares of the deviations of the cumulative distribution function $F(v)$ from the empirical cumulative distribution function $\hat{F}(v_{(i)})$ must be minimized [23]. There are many expressions to compute $\hat{F}(v_{(i)})$. However, they are based on the general expression $\hat{F}(v_{(i)}) = \frac{i-a}{n+b}$ where i is the rank of the ordered i^{th} observed wind speed $v_{(i)}$ ordered in ascending order $v_{(1)} \leq v_{(2)} \leq \dots \leq v_{(i)} \leq \dots \leq v_{(n)}$; while a and b are either constants or functions to the sample size (n). Equation (14) is usually used to calculate $\hat{F}(v_{(i)})$ [101], therefore it was adopted in this study. Table 12 displays the LSE estimates for the suggested PDFs.

$$\hat{F}(v_{(i)}) = \begin{cases} \frac{i-0.375}{n+0.25} & \text{for } n \leq 10 \\ \frac{i-0.5}{n+1} & \text{for } n \geq 10 \end{cases} \quad (14)$$

Table 12 Least-squares estimation (LSE) method to estimate the parameters of the two-parameter, the three-parameter Weibull and the Weibull-length-biased distributions

PDF	Parameters	Estimates
$W2_{LSE}$	Scale ($\hat{\alpha}$), shape ($\hat{\beta}$)	$argmin_{\alpha,\beta} [\ln[-\ln(1 - \hat{F}(v_{(i)}))] = \beta \ln v_i - \beta \ln \alpha]$
$W3_{LSE}$	Scale ($\hat{\alpha}$), shape ($\hat{\beta}$), shift ($\hat{\tau}$)	$argmin_{\alpha,\beta,\tau} [\ln[-\ln(1 - \hat{F}(v_{(i)}))] = \beta \ln(v_i - \tau) - \beta \ln \alpha]; v \geq \tau > 0$
WLB_{LSE}	Scale ($\hat{\alpha}$), shape ($\hat{\beta}$)	$argmin_{\alpha,\beta} \sum [\hat{F}(v_{(i)}) - \beta \gamma (1 + \frac{1}{\beta} \frac{v_{(i)}^\beta}{\lambda}) / \Gamma(\frac{1}{\beta})]^2$

Note: $\Gamma(x) = \int_0^\infty e^{-u} u^{x-1} dx$, $\Gamma_1 = \Gamma(1 + \frac{1}{\beta})$, $\lambda = \alpha^\beta$

3.2.3 The moments method (MOM)

The general idea behind the method of moments is to equate the population raw moments $E(V^r)$ to their peers from the sample $m_r = (1/n) \sum_{i=1}^n v_i^r$ where $r = \overline{1, n}$. The MOM estimators are determined by solving a number of equalities that depend on the number of the distribution's parameters yet it doesn't always yield acceptable solutions [84]. Contrary to the least-squares and the maximum likelihood methods, the estimates found by MOM are straightforward, easy to compute, and consistent but they are inefficient, can only be applied to uncensored samples, and do not use all the information from the sample [36], [75], [102].

Table 13 the method of moments (MOM) to estimate the parameters of the two-parameter Weibull and the Weibull-length-biased distributions

PDF	Parameter	Estimate
$W2_{MOM}$	Scale ($\hat{\alpha}$), shape ($\hat{\beta}$)	$m_r = \alpha^r \Gamma_r, r = \overline{1, 2}$
WLB_{MOM}	Scale ($\hat{\alpha}$), shape ($\hat{\beta}$)	$m_r = (r + 1) \lambda^{\frac{r}{\beta}} \Gamma(\frac{r+1}{\beta}) / \Gamma(\frac{1}{\beta}); r = \overline{1, 2}$

Note: $\Gamma(x) = \int_0^\infty e^{-u} u^{x-1} dx$, $\Gamma_1 = \Gamma(1 + \frac{1}{\beta})$, $\lambda = \alpha^\beta$

3.2.4 The linear moments method (LMOM)

LMOM is similar to MOM however the weighted moments are used instead of the raw moments. It is expected that LMOM estimates are more robust against outliers than those found by MOM. LMOM was introduced by Hosking (1990) and it is based on the linear combination of order statistics [23], [103]. On one hand, the population l-moments λ_r are based on the probability weighted moments ψ_r [29], [104]

$$\psi_r = \int_0^1 [v(F)] F^r dF, r > 0$$

$$\lambda_1 = \psi_0$$

$$\lambda_2 = 2\psi_1 - \psi_0$$

$$\lambda_5 = 70\psi_4 - 140\psi_3 + 90\psi_2 - 20\psi_1 + \psi_0$$

$$\lambda_3 = 6\psi_2 - 6\psi_1 + \psi_0$$

$$\lambda_4 = 20\psi_3 - 30\psi_2 + 12\psi_1 - \psi_0$$

And the l-moments ratios are

$$\zeta_1 = \lambda_3/\lambda_2$$

$$\zeta_2 = \lambda_4/\lambda_2$$

On the other hand b_r are the unbiased sample estimators of ψ_r can be computed from the wind speed data ordered in ascending order $v_{(1)} \leq v_{(2)} \leq \dots < v_{(i)} \leq \dots \leq v_{(n)}$.

$$b_r = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=r+1}^n \frac{(i-1)(i-2)\dots(i-r)}{(n-1)(n-2)\dots(n-r)} v_{(i)}, r > 0, b_0 = \bar{v}$$

The sample l-moments ℓ_r are calculated by replacing ψ_r by their sample estimates b_r

$$\ell_1 = b_0$$

$$\ell_2 = 2b_1 - b_0$$

$$\ell_5 = 70b_4 - 140b_3 + 90b_2 - 20b_1 + b_0$$

$$\ell_3 = 6b_2 - 6b_1 + b_0$$

$$\ell_4 = 20b_3 - 30b_2 + 12b_1 - b_0$$

And the sample l-moments ratios are

$$\hat{\zeta}_1 = \lambda_3/\lambda_2$$

$$\hat{\zeta}_2 = \lambda_4/\lambda_2$$

Table 14 the method of l-moments (LMOM) to estimate the parameters of the two-parameter Weibull distribution

PDF	Parameter	Estimate
$W2_{LMOM}$	Scale ($\hat{\alpha}$), shape ($\hat{\beta}$)	$\alpha\Gamma_1 = \bar{v}; \quad \beta = \frac{-\ln 2}{\ln(1-\widehat{CV}_{LMOM})}, \quad \widehat{CV}_{LMOM} = \frac{\frac{2}{n} \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} v_i}{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n v_i} - 1$

Note: $\Gamma(x) = \int_0^\infty e^{-u} u^{x-1} dx, \Gamma_1 = \Gamma\left(1 + \frac{1}{\beta}\right), \lambda = \alpha^\beta$

3.2.5 The power density method (PDM)

Akdag *et al.* [105] proposed PDM to accurately estimate the mean power density WPD since it is one of the most primordial factors that assess the wind power potential. PDM consists of equating the empirical energy pattern factor ($E_{pf} = \frac{\bar{v}^3}{v^3}$) with the estimated ($\frac{E(V^3)}{E(V)^3}$) energy pattern factor [29]. The implementation and the formulation of this PEM are easy and it requires less computational time [106]. The power density method sheds the light on the importance of the third raw moment in wind power applications.

Table 15 the power density method (PDM) to estimate the parameters of the two-parameter Weibull and the Weibull-length-biased distributions

PDF	Parameter	Estimate
$W2_{PDM}$	Scale ($\hat{\alpha}$), shape ($\hat{\beta}$)	$E_{pf} - \frac{\Gamma(1+\frac{3}{\beta})}{\Gamma^3(1+\frac{1}{\beta})} = 0; \alpha\Gamma_1 = \bar{v}$
WW_{PDM}	Scale ($\hat{\alpha}$), shape ($\hat{\beta}$)	$E_{pf} - \frac{\Gamma(\frac{4}{\beta})\Gamma^2(\frac{4}{\beta})}{2\Gamma^3(\frac{2}{\beta})} = 0; 2\alpha\Gamma(\frac{2}{\beta})/\Gamma(\frac{1}{\beta}) = \bar{v}$

Note: $\Gamma(x) = \int_0^\infty e^{-u}u^{x-1}dx, \Gamma_i = \Gamma(1 + \frac{i}{\beta}), \lambda = \alpha^\beta$

3.3 Bayesian estimation methods

Carta *et al.* (2009) [36] stated that the Bayesian approach is rarely employed in the wind power industry in their review article. A decade later, the same remark is still true as all the PEMs reviewed by Jung and Schindler (2019) [23] are classical PEMs in the sense that they treat the parameters to be estimated as constant unknowns. The reluctance in the implementation of the Bayesian method was linked to the difficulty in specifying appropriate priors [96].

The Bayesian method can strengthen the fitness of the probability density functions in modeling the long-term wind speed records by treating the vector of parameters θ as unknown, but variate with a given prior distribution $\pi(\theta)$ [75]. The prior density function $\pi(\theta)$ is the cornerstone of the Bayesian inference as it translates the subjective information available on θ . What distinguishes the Bayesian inference from the frequentist inference is that the first rests on the posterior density $\pi(\theta; v)$ on which the estimation of the parameters is based upon. In other words, the posterior model updates the initial beliefs on θ represented by $\pi(\theta)$ given the sample wind speed data expressed by the likelihood function $L(v; \theta)$. If the sample data supports the subjective opinion about the parameters then the posterior model should strengthen the confidence in the subjective information otherwise the posterior model should intermediate between the sample information $L(v; \theta)$ and the subjective information $\pi(\theta)$ [75]. The readers are referred to the excellent references [75], [107] for detailed information on the Bayesian inference. The posterior model $\pi(\theta; v)$ is formed by using Bayes' theorem and employing $L(v; \theta)$ and $\pi(\theta)$ as inputs and it is calculated as follows [35].

$$\pi(\theta; v) \propto \pi(\theta) L(v; \theta) \tag{15}$$

3.3.1 The prior density function

The prior density function $\pi(\theta)$ is the probability distribution that represents the knowledge or the beliefs about the parameters [35]. The usefulness of $\pi(\theta)$ relies on the quality of the inputs provided by experts or collected from inspection reports [40]. In cases where there is no information on the parameters to build the prior upon, the non-informative Jeffrey’s prior can be useful; it is expressed as $\pi(\theta) = [I(\theta)]^{1/2}$ where $I(\theta)$ is the expected Fisher information. In this analysis the prior information on the shape parameter β is sourced from the map of distribution of the shape factor produced by Boudia *et al.* [15] represented in Figure 16, while the prior information on the scale parameter α is based on the mean wind speed (\bar{v}) of the measured data.

Table 16 candidate distribution models for the prior distributions of their parameters

PDF	$\pi(\theta)$	Posterior estimate type	Abbreviation	Type of $\pi(\theta)$	Source of $\pi(\theta)$
Two-parameter Weibull (W2)	$\pi(\xi) \sim Gamma(v, 0.1)$ $\pi(\beta) \sim Gamma(0.39, 0.14)$	Mean	$W2_{BM}$	Informative prior	Boudia <i>et al.</i> [15]
		Median	$W2_{BD}$		
		Mode	$W2_{BMD}$		
Weibull-length-biased (WLB)	$\pi(\xi) \sim Gamma(v, 0.1)$ $\pi(\beta) \sim Gamma(0.39, 0.14)$	Mean	WLB_{BM}		
		Median	WLB_{BD}		
		Mode	WLB_{BMD}		
Bimodal Weibull (WW)	$\pi(\xi_1) \sim Gamma(v, 0.1)$ $\pi(\beta_1) \sim Gamma(0.39, 0.14)$ $\pi(\xi_2) \sim Gamma(v, 0.1)$ $\pi(\beta_2) \sim Gamma(0.39, 0.14)$ $\pi(\omega) \sim Uniform[0,1]$	Mean	WW_{BM}		
		Median	WW_{BD}		
		Mode	WW_{BMD}		
Three-parameter Weibull (W3)	$\pi(\xi) \propto 1/\xi$ $\pi(\beta) \propto 1/\beta$ $\pi(\tau) \sim Uniform[0, v_{(1)}]$	Mean	$W3_{BM}$	Non-informative prior	Green <i>et al.</i> [97]

$$\xi = \alpha^{-\beta}; v = \bar{v}^{(-\beta/S)}$$

Table 16 shows candidate distribution models to represent the prior distribution $\pi(\theta)$. The range of the variations in the shape parameter β is limited in wind power applications [38] therefore it was assumed that $\beta \in [2, 3.5]$. This information is based on Figure 20 which depicts

the annual distribution of shape factor (β) in Algeria at 10 m height and it was produced by Boudia *et al.* [15]. A random sample of 10000 observations of plausible values of $\beta \in [2, 3.5]$ was generated in “RStudio” then fitted to Gamma distribution the output was $\pi(\beta) \sim \text{Gamma}(0.39, 0.14)$. It is well known that the scale parameter is attached to the expected mean $E(V)$ therefore $\pi(\xi) \sim \text{Gamma}(v, 1)$ where $\xi = \alpha^{-\beta}$ is an expedient transformation to ease the computation, and $v = \bar{v}^{(-\bar{v}/S)}$ where \bar{v} and S are the empirical mean and the empirical standard deviation respectively. These informative priors were applied on W2, WLB and WW. Green *et al.* [97] estimated the shape, the scale, and the shift (τ) parameters of W3 using vague priors $\pi(\xi) \propto 1/\xi$, $\pi(\beta) \propto 1/\beta$ and uniform prior $U_{[0, v_{(1)}]}$ for τ as the location parameter is bound to be positive and less than the sample minimum wind speed v_1 . They found that the Bayesian model fitted the distribution of tree diameters in forest stands better than the maximum likelihood and guaranteed positive estimates of τ .

Figure 20 The distribution of annual shape factor (β) in Algeria at 10 m height (dimensionless) [15]

3.3.2 The loss function

Bayesian point estimation is attached to a loss function $l(\hat{\theta}, \theta)$ that expresses the expected loss when the estimate $\hat{\theta}$ deviates from the true θ [75]. The quadratic loss function and the linear absolute loss function are widely used. These loss functions are expressed in Equations (15) and (16) respectively. Both loss functions equate between overestimation and underestimation θ [107]. In this analysis, the posterior mean (BM), the posterior median (BD), and the posterior mode (BMD) are considered as the Bayesian estimators of θ as indicated in Table 15.

$$l(\hat{\theta}, \theta) = (\hat{\theta} - \theta)^2 \quad (15)$$

$$l(\hat{\theta}, \theta) = |\hat{\theta} - \theta| \quad (16)$$

3.3.3 Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) and Gibbs sampling

Historically, Bayesian analysis was limited because it usually involves complicated and intractable models with complicated integrals in calculating the posterior probability distribution $\pi(\theta; \nu)$ [35], [37], [108]. However, these calculations became possible with the Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) method. MCMC is Monte Carlo integration using Markov chains. Monte Carlo integration enables drawing samples from the posterior distribution, this is done by running suitable Markov chains [37]. Gibbs sampler is a useful tool to construct these chains [37], [108], [109]. Gibbs sampling is used when the joint distribution $\pi(\theta; \nu)$ is not known explicitly while the full conditional distribution of each random variable is known and tractable. By inputting initial values of θ and data ν the sampler samples a value for each parameter given the data and all other variables. Once all the parameters have been sampled, then the process is started over. After a sufficient “burn-in” to remove the effect of initial sampled values, the rest is considered to be dependent and identically distributed sample from the joint distribution [110]. “JAGS” which stands for Just Another Gibbs Sampler is utilized to perform the Bayesian analysis, alongside “RStudio”. The open-source software “JAGS” accepts a model string written in an R-like syntax that compiles and generates MCMC samples from the model using Gibbs sampling. Packages like “R2jags” and “rjags” facilitate using “JAGS” through “RStudio”.

3.4 Goodness-of-fit metrics

The goodness-of-fit (GoF) metrics are used to determine the optimal estimates that modeled the data with the least error. The Bayesian information criterion (BIC), the coefficient of determination (R^2), the mean absolute error (MAE), the root mean squared error (RMSE), and the power density error (WPE) were picked to find the fittest model among the models based on the combination of W2, W3, WW, and WLB probability distribution functions; and MLM, LSE, MOM, LMOM, MMLM, MMOM, PDM, BM, BD, and BMD parameter estimation methods. It was stated that using multiple goodness-of-fit metrics diminish the biasness in the results [19]. BIC is based on the log-likelihood function $LL(v; \theta)$, the number of parameters (k), and the sample size (n) and it is characterized by penalizing the usage of complex PDFs, i.e., a high number of parameters [111]. R^2 , MAE (m/s), and RMSE (m/s) measure the difference between the empirical frequencies calculated from the data and the frequencies calculated using PDFs for the bins. R^2 and WPE take values between 0 and 1 [112]. The aforementioned GoF metrics are expressed in Table 17.

Table 17 classical goodness-of-fit metrics

Metric	Expression
Bayesian information criterion	$BIC = -2LL(v; \theta) + k \ln(n)$
Coefficient of determination related to WPD	$R^2_{power} = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (m_3 - E(V^3))^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n (m_3 - \bar{m}_3)^2}$
Mean absolute error related to the PDF	$MAE_{PDF} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n f(v_i) - \hat{f}(v_i) $
Mean absolute error related to the PP plot	$MAE_{PP} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \hat{F}(v_i) - F(v_i) $
Root mean squared error related to the PDF	$RMSE_{PDF} = \left[\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (\hat{f}(v_i) - f(v_i))^2 \right]^{1/2}$
Root mean squared error related to the PP plot	$RMSE_{PP} = \left[\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (\hat{F}(v_i) - F(v_i))^2 \right]^{1/2}$
Wind power error	$WPE = \frac{m_3 - E(V^3)}{m_3}$

Figure 21 gives an overview of the frequency of application of the GoF metrics in the studies evaluated by Jung and Schindler [23]. It is remarked that $RMSE_{PP}$ and MAE_{PP} are used to quantify the difference between the empirical cumulative distribution function $\hat{F}(v_i)$ and the probabilistic cumulative distribution function $F(v_i)$. On the other hand $RMSE_{PDF}$ and MAE_{PDF}

quantify the difference between the empirical probability distribution function $\hat{f}(v_i)$ and the PDF $f(v_i)$, while R^2_{power} and WPE measure the difference between the empirical third raw moment (m_3) and the population $E(V^3)$ third raw moments. MAE and RMSE are bin-specific tests and depend on the selected bin size. To objectively determine the best bin size (BS), Equation (21) is used where $v_{(n)}$ (m/s) is the maximum measured wind speed [20], [113]. The preferred model is the one with the lowest BIC, MAE_{PDF} , MAE_{PP} , $RMSE_{PDF}$, $RMSE_{PP}$, WPE and the highest R^2_{power} [23], [112].

$$BS = v_{(n)} / (3.3 \log(n) + 1) \tag{16}$$

Figure 21 Share of goodness-of-fit (GoF) metrics used in the evaluated studies [23]

Conclusion

A set of probabilistic tools was used to model wind speed, the most important factor that impacts wind power. Historically, W2 has been used to serve this purpose. However, there are cases where this distribution fits poorly the wind speed data which may lead to erroneous feasibility studies to the wind farm projects. It was proposed to deploy the three-parameter Weibull, the Weibull-length-biased, and the bimodal Weibull PDFs as alternatives. The characteristics of these PDFs and the frequentist and Bayesian methods to estimate their parameters were discussed.

Chapter 4 Results and interpretation

Introduction

The hourly records of the wind speed usually satisfy assessing the wind power potential requirement. For this reason, two years of the hourly wind speed data from January 2015 to December 2016 (14510 observations) measured at 10 m height were used to evaluate the wind energy potential in In-Salah. Since the site has been identified as the windiest station in Algeria and because its isolated power network (In-Salah – Adrar – Timimoun pole) is already familiar with wind energy via Adrar’s wind farm, it is necessary to accurately assess its wind power potential. The performance of W2, W3, WW, and WLB in modeling this data was checked. Successful usage of the probability distribution functions relies immensely on estimating their parameters accurately, therefore frequentist methods like MLM, LSE, MOM, LMOM, MML, MM, and PDM; and Bayesian methods were used. The Bayesian analysis was performed on the time series then the convergence of the Markov Chain Monte Carlo method was checked using diagnostic tests. Afterward, a comprehensive comparison was conducted between the Bayesian and frequentist estimates of the parameters using BIC, MAE, R^2 , RMSE, and WPE as judgment criterion tools. The Bayesian and the frequentist PEMs were also compared in terms of assessing the wind power density. Finally, some key statistics were calculated using the best PEM to unlock the features of wind energy in In-Salah.

4.1 Statistical description of the data

Many factors influence the capability of PDFs in modeling accurately the wind speed. This might include the nature and topography of the candidate site (onshore or offshore), the height taken for measuring the observations, the type of the device used to measure the wind speed (anemometer, SODAR, LIDAR, or else), the temporal resolution of the observations (averaged every 10 minutes, every hour...etc.) and the sample size. In-Salah is an onshore site located in the heart of the Algerian Sahara. In-Salah has been identified as the windiest site in Algeria. Table 18 and Figure 22 show the geographical coordinates, and measurement information and the location of In-Salah station respectively.

Table 18 geographical coordinates, and measurement information of In-Salah station

Site	Longitude (°)	Latitude (°)	Altitude (m)	Length of time series Period
In-Salah	2.5	27.75	280	01/01/2015 - 31/12/2016

Figure 22 The location of In-Salah in Algeria.

The wind velocity time series is measured by the National Meteorological Office using anemometers installed at 10 m height above the ground level [16]. The data was partitioned into 12 months to predict the monthly behavior of the wind speed in In-Salah. Table 19 presents the monthly and the annual variation of some the descriptive statistics measures such as the minimum ($v_{(1)}$), the first quartile (Q_1), the mode (v_{Mo}), the mean (\bar{v}), the median (v_{Me}), the third quartile (Q_3), the standard deviation (S), the coefficient of variation (CV), skewness (Sk), kurtosis (Kr) and the maximum ($v_{(n)}$) of the wind velocity in In-Salah from January 2015 to December 2016 at 10 m AGL.

The wind speed in In-Salah varies between 0.1 and 21.6 m/s for the period 2015-2016. The minimum monthly value of Q_1 is 4.1 m/s which might suggest the suitability of In-Salah to site large-scale wind farms since the cut-in wind speed (v_{ci}) of most WECS is 4 m/s at higher altitudes. Moreover, the wind blows on average at high speed from May to August but not in a

uniform pattern. The annual mode is less than the median and less than the mean, which indicates that the wind speed in In-Salah is positively skewed, this is confirmed by the positive value of skewness. The usage of Weibull models in In-Salah is admitted by those findings. The kurtosis of the wind speed in In-Salah is slightly less than 3; this is an indicator of the presence of extreme values.

Table 19 monthly and annual descriptive statistics of In-Salah for the period from 01/01/2015 to 31/12/2016 at 10 m AGL

Time-series	n	$v_{(1)}$ (m/s)	Q_1 (m/s)	v_{Mo} (m/s)	\bar{v} (m/s)	v_{Me} (m/s)	Q_3 (m/s)	S (m/s)	CV (%)	Sk	Kr	$v_{(n)}$ (m/s)
Jan	1129	1	5.1	5.1	6.93	6.2	8.8	2.77	40.01	0.51	2.70	15.4
Feb	1047	1	5.1	5.1	6.86	6.2	8.2	2.77	40.44	0.75	3.26	16.5
Mar	1161	1	5.1	5.1	7.11	7.2	8.8	2.73	38.43	0.54	2.90	16
Apr	1022	1.5	4.1	5.1	6.42	5.7	8.2	2.95	45.91	0.99	3.78	18.5
May	1345	1	5.1	5.1	7.12	7.2	9.3	2.89	40.67	0.28	2.32	15.4
Jun	1285	0.5	5.1	5.1	7.11	6.7	9.3	3.09	43.43	0.59	2.84	18.5
Jul	1344	1.5	5.1	5.1	7.60	7.7	9.3	2.74	36.13	0.15	2.45	15.4
Aug	1362	1	5.1	6.2	7.19	7.2	8.8	2.68	37.34	0.49	3.10	17.5
Sep	1276	0.5	5.1	5.1	6.54	6.2	8.2	2.47	37.71	0.99	5.57	21.6
Oct	1069	2.1	4.1	4.1	6.24	5.7	7.7	2.48	39.68	0.94	3.61	15.4
Nov	1138	0.1	5.1	5.1	6.96	6.2	8.8	2.88	41.39	0.47	3.06	15.4
Dec	1332	0.1	6.2	10.3	8.59	8.8	10.3	2.87	33.43	- 0.05	2.81	17.5
Annual	14510	0.1	5.1	5.1	7.09	6.7	9.3	2.85	40.12	0.52	2.92	21.6

4.2 Analysis of the Bayesian estimates

Trace and The Brooks-Gelman-Rubin (BGR) statistic convergence diagnostics are respectively informal and formal methods that monitor the performance of the Markov Chain and make sure that Gibbs sampler reached stationary distribution within an acceptable error [109], [114]. The posterior density was simulated by two chains with 10000 iterations each. Trace and BGR plots are generated using “JAGS” and “RStudio”. The trace plot of the scale and the shape parameters of W2 (A and B) and WLB (C and D) in Figure 23 depicts that the two chains for both parameters converged as they overlapped and are stationary, where the red and blue lines represent chains 1 and 2 respectively. This is confirmed by the BGR statistic shown in Figure 24 as it converges to one when the number of iterations increases.

Figure 23 Trace diagnostic plot for (A and B) scale and shape parameters of W2 and (C and D) scale and shape parameters of WLB using the wind speed data measured at In-Salah at 10 m AGL. Chains 1 and 2 are represented by red and blue lines respectively

Figure 24 BGR convergence diagnostics plotting for (A) W2 parameters and (B) WLB parameters using the wind speed data in In-Salah at 10 m AGL

Chapter 4 Results and interpretation

Similar to W2 and WLB, The trace plots of WW in Figure 25 overlap for all the five parameters and the BGR statistic shown in Figure 26 as it converges to one as the number of iterations increases.

Figure 25 Trace diagnostic plot of WW scale, shape, and mixing parameters using the wind speed data in In-Salah at 10 m AGL. Chains 1 and 2 are represented by red and blue lines respectively

Figure 26 BGR convergence diagnostics plotting for (two left) W2 parameters and (two right) WLB parameters using the wind speed data in In-Salah at 10 m AGL.

Figures 27 and 28 show the posterior densities of the scale, the shape parameters of W2 (Figure 27, top), WLB (Figure 27, bottom), and WW (Figure 27). The distribution of the Bayesian estimates of α for both W2 and WLB is negatively skewed but positively skewed for WW, while the posterior distribution of β has almost symmetric for W2 and WLB but negatively skewed for WW. The posterior density of the mixing parameter is negatively skewed. The mean, the median, and the mode of the posterior model constitute the Bayesian estimates of the parameters.

Figure 27 The posterior densities of the scale (α) and the shape (β) parameters of W2 (top) and WLB (bottom) using the wind speed data in In-Salah at 10 m AGL.

Figure 28 The posterior densities of the scale (α_1 and α_2), the shape (β_1 and β_2) and the mixing (ω , $1 - \omega$) parameters of WW using the wind speed data in In-Salah at 10 m AGL.

4.3 Analysis of the Weibull parameters

Tables 20 and 21 display the estimates of the two-parameter Weibull distribution (W_2). The scale and the shape parameters were calculated using five frequentist PEMs (MLM, MOM, LMOM, and PDM) and three Bayesian PEMs (BM, BD, and BMD). The monthly estimates of α_{W_2} range between 6.76 m/s (October) evaluated using BMD and 10.01 m/s (December) calculated using LSE. Most of the minimum values of α_{W_2} are found using the least-squares method while most of its maximum values are found using BMD. It was found that the shape parameter β_{W_2} varies from 1.96 (November) to 3.32 (December) by using LSE and PDM respectively. Contrarily to the scale parameter, most of the highest values were obtained by employing LSE, and the lowest values were obtained using PDM. In general, the annual values of α_{W_2} and β_{W_2} are between 7.97 m/s to 8 m/s and 2.64 to 2.77 respectively. This indicates that the wind in In-Salah is somewhat uniform and blows at high speed on average.

Table 20 Frequentist and Bayesian estimation of the two-parameter Weibull scale parameter (α_{W_2}) using the wind speed data in In-Salah at 10 m AGL.

α_{W_2} (m/s)	Frequentist PEMs					Bayesian PEMs		
	MLM	LSE	MOM	LMOM	PDM	BM	BD	BMD
Jan	7.80	7.74	7.79	7.79	7.79	7.81	7.81	7.79
Feb	7.73	7.65	7.72	7.71	7.72	7.73	7.73	7.82
Mar	8.00	7.94	7.99	7.98	7.99	8.00	8.00	8.10
Apr	7.26	7.17	7.24	7.24	7.24	7.27	7.27	7.40
May	8.02	7.98	8.01	8.01	8.01	8.02	8.02	7.93
Jun	8.03	7.96	8.01	8.01	8.02	8.04	8.04	8.00
Jul	8.51	8.50	8.51	8.51	8.50	8.51	8.51	8.58
Aug	8.07	8.01	8.06	8.05	8.06	8.07	8.07	8.07
Sep	7.34	7.28	7.34	7.32	7.35	7.34	7.34	7.25
Oct	7.04	6.96	7.02	7.01	7.03	7.04	7.04	6.76
Nov	7.80	8.31	7.84	7.83	7.84	7.81	7.81	7.72
Dec	9.55	10.01	9.58	9.58	9.58	9.55	9.55	9.62
Annual	7.99	7.99	7.98	7.97	7.98	7.99	7.99	8.00

Chapter 4 Results and interpretation

Table 21 Frequentist and Bayesian estimation of the two-parameter Weibull shape parameter (β_{W2}) using the wind speed data in In-Salah at 10 m AGL.

β_{W2}	Frequentist PEMs					Bayesian PEMs		
	MLM	LSE	MOM	LMOM	PDM	BM	BD	BMD
Jan	2.69	2.93	2.69	2.71	2.66	2.70	2.70	2.69
Feb	2.63	2.99	2.66	2.74	2.59	2.63	2.63	2.58
Mar	2.80	3.08	2.82	2.85	2.77	2.79	2.79	2.81
Apr	2.32	2.70	2.31	2.41	2.23	2.33	2.33	2.36
May	2.68	2.76	2.65	2.63	2.65	2.67	2.67	2.64
Jun	2.47	2.70	2.46	2.48	2.42	2.48	2.48	2.43
Jul	3.04	3.07	3.02	3.01	3.02	3.03	3.03	3.09
Aug	2.88	3.12	2.91	2.95	2.86	2.88	2.88	2.88
Sep	2.76	3.22	2.88	3.02	2.75	2.76	2.75	2.77
Oct	2.67	3.14	2.72	2.84	2.61	2.66	2.66	2.62
Nov	2.51	1.96	2.59	2.63	2.57	2.52	2.51	2.46
Dec	3.26	2.49	3.29	3.31	3.32	3.25	3.25	3.25
Annual	2.67	2.77	2.69	2.71	2.65	2.67	2.67	2.64

The estimators of the Weibull-length-biased scale and the shape parameters are shown in Tables 22 and 23. Similar to the two-parameter Weibull the highest and the lowest values of α_{WLB} are obtained by LSE and BMD respectively. However, these two PEMs also gave in this order the least and the highest values of β_{WLB} . According to WLB, the distribution of the wind velocity in In-Salah is positively skewed in all the 13 samples since the maximum value of $\beta_{WLB} = 2.76$ and yet is less than 3.44; and leptokurtic i.e. the tails are close to the peak in the months of February, April, May and June and the annual data as $\beta_{WLB} \leq 2.164$.

Table 22 Frequentist and Bayesian estimation of the Weibull-length-biased scale parameter (α_{WLB}) using the wind speed data in In-Salah at 10 m AGL.

α_{WLB} (m/s)	Frequentist PEMs			Bayesian PEMs		
	LSE	MOM	PDM	BM	BD	BMD
Jan	6.13	6.30	6.29	6.34	6.34	6.43
Feb	6.08	6.21	6.16	6.23	6.23	6.22
Mar	6.44	6.59	6.56	6.60	6.60	6.69
Apr	5.29	5.41	5.32	5.49	5.50	5.59
May	6.20	6.43	6.46	6.47	6.47	6.36
Jun	5.97	6.20	6.19	6.25	6.25	6.39
Jul	7.17	7.20	7.22	7.24	7.24	7.16
Aug	6.68	6.73	6.71	6.73	6.73	6.78
Sep	6.07	6.10	6.02	6.08	6.08	6.00
Oct	5.54	5.71	5.63	5.70	5.71	5.75
Nov	6.20	6.23	6.23	6.15	6.15	6.15
Dec	8.43	8.34	8.37	8.31	8.32	8.32
Annual	6.29	6.45	6.43	6.45	6.45	6.53

Table 23 Frequentist and Bayesian estimation of the Weibull-length-biased scale parameter (β_{WLB}) using the wind speed data in In-Salah at 10 m AGL.

β_{WLB}	Frequentist PEMs			Bayesian PEMs		
	LSE	MOM	PDM	BM	BD	BMD
Jan	2.03	2.15	2.13	2.17	2.17	2.19
Feb	2.13	2.12	2.07	2.13	2.13	2.08
Mar	2.16	2.27	2.24	2.27	2.27	2.30
Apr	1.81	1.79	1.74	1.84	1.84	1.88
May	1.88	2.10	2.13	2.13	2.13	2.07
Jun	1.79	1.93	1.92	1.96	1.96	2.01
Jul	2.35	2.46	2.48	2.49	2.49	2.43
Aug	2.33	2.35	2.33	2.35	2.35	2.27
Sep	2.41	2.32	2.22	2.29	2.29	2.32
Oct	2.19	2.17	2.09	2.17	2.17	2.20
Nov	2.04	2.05	2.05	2.00	2.00	2.03
Dec	2.68	2.72	2.76	2.70	2.70	2.72
Annual	2.03	2.14	2.12	2.14	2.14	2.17

Tables 24 to 26 represent the estimates of the three-parameter Weibull scale (α_{W3}), the shape (β_{W3}) and, the shift (τ_{W3}) parameters obtained by using MLM, LSE, modified maximum likelihood (MML), and modified moments (MM) as frequentist methods in addition to BM. It was noticed from Table 26 that $\hat{\tau}_{W3} < 0$ in four samples. For September the negative estimates of the shift parameter are produced by MML and MM while all the PEMs have negative estimators for τ_{W3} in November and December. For the annual data, it was found that α_{W3} takes values between 8.02 m/s (BM) and 8.32 m/s (MLM) while β_{W3} moves between 2.68 (BM) and 3.03 (LSE) and τ_{W3} varies between -0.31 (MLM) and -0.03 (BM). This implies that the wind speed is uniform and has in high speed on average.

Chapter 4 Results and interpretation

Table 24 Frequentist and Bayesian estimation of the three-parameter Weibull scale parameter (α_{W3}) using the wind speed data in In-Salah at 10 m AGL.

α_{W3} (m/s)	Frequentist PEMs				Bayesian PEMs
	MLM	LSE	MML	MM	BM
Jan	7.01	6.98	7.15	7.07	6.89
Feb	6.95	6.91	7.06	6.98	6.77
Mar	7.15	7.12	7.45	7.36	7.05
Apr	5.73	5.71	5.68	5.63	5.63
May	7.18	7.18	7.33	7.24	7.19
Jun	7.68	7.63	7.95	7.85	7.58
Jul	7.53	7.55	7.37	7.29	7.80
Aug	7.37	7.34	7.54	7.45	7.18
Sep	7.12	7.08	7.41	7.41	6.88
Oct	5.03	5.01	4.77	4.75	4.85
Nov	9.45	9.41	8.46	8.39	8.55
Dec	12.10	12.07	9.51	11.19	11.36
Annual	8.32	8.27	8.14	8.10	8.02

Table 25 Frequentist and Bayesian estimation of the three-parameter Weibull shape parameter (β_{W3}) using the wind speed data in In-Salah at 10 m AGL.

β_{W3}	Frequentist PEMs				Bayesian PEMs
	MLM	LSE	MML	MM	BM
Jan	2.40	2.50	2.45	2.41	2.35
Feb	2.36	2.57	2.40	2.37	2.29
Mar	2.48	2.63	2.59	2.56	2.44
Apr	1.82	1.93	1.80	1.76	1.78
May	2.35	2.32	2.41	2.36	2.36
Jun	2.36	2.53	2.45	2.40	2.32
Jul	2.64	2.53	2.58	2.52	2.75
Aug	2.61	2.73	2.68	2.66	2.54
Sep	2.68	3.09	2.79	2.91	2.59
Oct	1.90	2.01	1.78	1.76	1.82
Nov	3.14	3.38	2.79	2.81	2.82
Dec	4.28	4.36	3.23	3.96	4.00
Annual	2.79	3.03	2.73	2.74	2.68

Chapter 4 Results and interpretation

Table 26 Frequentist and Bayesian estimation of the three-parameter Weibull shift parameter (τ_{W3}) using the wind speed data in In-Salah at 10 m AGL.

τ_{W3} (m/s)	Frequentist PEMs				Bayesian PEMs	$v_{(1)}$ (m/s)
	MLM	LSE	MML	MM	BM	
Jan	0.72	0.73	0.59	0.66	0.83	1
Feb	0.71	0.71	0.61	0.67	0.87	1
Mar	0.78	0.78	0.51	0.58	0.88	1
Apr	1.34	1.34	1.38	1.40	1.41	1.5
May	0.77	0.77	0.63	0.70	0.75	1
Jun	0.32	0.32	0.07	0.15	0.41	0.5
Jul	0.91	0.92	1.05	1.13	0.66	1.5
Aug	0.65	0.65	0.49	0.56	0.81	1
Sep	0.20	0.20	- 0.07	- 0.07	0.42	0.5
Oct	1.80	1.80	2.01	2.02	1.95	2.1
Nov	- 1.50	- 1.49	- 0.58	- 0.51	- 0.66	0.1
Dec	- 2.42	- 2.40	0.04	- 1.54	- 1.71	0.1
Annual	- 0.31	- 0.31	- 0.14	- 0.12	- 0.03	0.1

The values in bold indicate the negative estimates of τ_{W3}

The Bayesian estimates of the bimodal Weibull scale parameters (α_1 m/s, α_2 m/s), shape parameters (β_1 and β_2) and the mixing parameter (ω) are shown in Table 27. It was remarked that in most of the samples the first mode is more significant than the second mode. ω displays quite the range of bimodality as it varies between 0.09 to 0.84.

Table 27 Bayesian estimation of the bimodal Weibull parameters using the wind speed data in In-Salah at 10 m AGL

WW	BM					BD					BMD				
	α_1 (m/s)	β_1	α_2 (m/s)	β_2	ω	α_1 (m/s)	β_1	α_2 (m/s)	β_2	ω	α_1 (m/s)	β_1	α_2 (m/s)	β_2	ω
Jan	9.11	3.23	5.82	3.45	0.58	9.11	3.23	5.82	3.45	0.57	9.01	3.03	5.97	3.06	0.63
Feb	9.57	3.32	5.84	3.87	0.48	9.56	3.30	5.84	3.88	0.48	9.90	3.39	5.89	3.62	0.44
Mar	8.92	3.30	5.28	4.11	0.72	8.90	3.29	5.21	4.14	0.73	9.00	3.43	4.81	4.18	0.76
Apr	9.04	2.93	4.91	3.87	0.55	9.03	2.93	4.90	3.87	0.55	9.28	3.00	5.15	3.37	0.51
May	9.03	3.44	4.59	4.12	0.75	9.02	3.42	4.59	4.11	0.75	8.83	3.21	4.54	3.99	0.79
Jun	9.09	3.01	4.63	4.12	0.74	9.08	3.00	4.60	4.15	0.75	9.11	3.10	4.43	4.35	0.76
Jul	8.99	3.35	5.76	3.53	0.83	8.97	3.34	5.74	3.52	0.84	9.19	3.51	5.52	3.52	0.80
Aug	9.13	3.17	6.60	3.45	0.56	9.12	3.17	6.56	3.45	0.57	8.79	3.21	6.31	3.76	0.74
Sep	10.49	2.91	6.87	3.26	0.13	10.37	2.89	6.88	3.25	0.12	10.67	2.73	7.06	3.20	0.09
Oct	8.83	3.49	5.16	4.47	0.48	8.83	3.48	5.16	4.46	0.48	8.78	3.51	5.19	4.47	0.47
Nov	8.42	2.57	6.69	2.76	0.62	8.39	2.57	6.69	2.74	0.65	8.35	2.66	5.69	3.17	0.80
Dec	8.42	2.56	6.78	2.73	0.59	8.38	2.56	6.85	2.70	0.61	9.33	2.63	7.54	2.72	0.22
Annual	8.82	3.05	5.31	3.92	0.74	8.82	3.04	5.31	3.92	0.74	8.79	3.06	5.14	3.98	0.75

4.4 Fitness evaluation of the chosen probability distribution functions

Table 28 presents the computed goodness-of-fit indicators for each probability distribution function associated with the used parameter estimation method to evaluate the proposed models in terms of fitting the annual wind speed data in In-Salah measured at 10 m AGL. The estimates of W2 parameters were calculated by using five frequentist and three Bayesian PEMs. The Weibull-length-biased distribution estimates were calculated using three frequentist and three Bayesian methods. The three-parameter Weibull was excluded from the goodness-of-fit evaluation since all the PEMs gave inadequate estimates of the shift parameter (τ_{W3}) i.e. negative estimates. Only Bayesian methods were applied to the bimodal Weibull. The utilized goodness-of-fit metrics are the Bayesian information criterion (BIC), the root mean squared error ($RMSE_{PP}$ and $RMSE_{PDF}$), and the mean absolute error (MAE_{PP} and MAE_{PDF}).

Table 28 goodness-of-fit metrics to evaluate the fitness of W2, WLB and WW to model the wind speed data in In-Salah measured at 10 m AGL.

PDFs	PEMs	BIC	$RMSE_{PP}$ (m/s)	MAE_{PP} (m/s)	$RMSE_{PDF}$ (m/s)	MAE_{PDF} (m/s)	
W2	Frequentist PEMs	$W2_{MLM}$	70904.09	0.02405	0.01457	0.03281	0.01919
		$W2_{LSE}$	70944.55	0.02425	0.01445	0.03372	0.01945
		$W2_{MOM}$	70905.58	0.02407	0.01455	0.03297	0.01921
		$W2_{LMOM}$	70912.12	0.02411	0.01452	0.03320	0.01927
		$W2_{PDM}$	70906.20	0.02402	0.01462	0.03262	0.01916
	Bayesian PEMs	$W2_{BM}$	70904.09	0.02405	0.01457	0.03281	0.01919
		$W2_{BD}$	70904.09	0.02405	0.01457	0.03281	0.01919
		$W2_{BMD}$	70909.05	0.02404	0.01462	0.03253	0.01916
	WLB	Frequentist PEMs	WLB_{LSE}	54522.97	0.02923	0.01983	0.03217
WLB_{MOM}			54501.91	0.02795	0.01888	0.03299	0.01883
WLB_{PDM}			54502.12	0.02810	0.01900	0.03284	0.01881
Bayesian PEMs		WLB_{BM}	54501.91	0.02794	0.01888	0.03298	0.01883
		WLB_{BD}	54501.91	0.02794	0.01887	0.03298	0.01883
		WLB_{BMD}	54503.57	0.02743	0.01850	0.03309	0.01891
WW	Bayesian PEMs	WW_{BM}	70561.68	0.02302	0.01388	0.03219	0.01656
		WW_{BD}	70561.62	0.02302	0.01388	0.03218	0.01656
		WW_{BMD}	70572.18	0.02302	0.01384	0.03214	0.01670

Note: The bold values indicate the best fit estimators for each metric.

Several remarks can be drawn from Table 28. The first one is that BIC chose WLB_{BM} as the fittest model, the second remark is MAE_{PP} and $RMSE_{PDF}$ favor WW_{BMD} over the rest of the models, while $RMSE_{PP}$ and MAE_{PDF} favor WW_{BM} and WW_{BD} respectively. This implies that the proposed alternative PDFs the Weibull-length-biased and the bimodal Weibull seem to

model better the wind speed data than the widely used two-parameter Weibull, and the Bayesian methods outperform the classical methods. However, to see if these results are going to hold and also to include W3 in the comparison, the 12 months samples are included in the analysis alongside the annual data. The evaluation results for the 12 months are given in the appendix.

Figure 29 Boxplots of BIC values related to the employed combination PDF/PEM for the wind speed data in In-Salah measured at 10 m AGL.

Figure 29 displays the fitness evaluation of the models based on the Bayesian information criterion (BIC) for the annual and the monthly samples of the wind speed data in In-Salah measured at 10 m AGL. Figure 30 (A) ranks the four PDFs in ascending order according to their median BIC values. The same process is applied on the frequentist and the Bayesian parameter estimation methods in Figure 30 (B). WLB_{PDM} , WLB_{BM} , WLB_{BD} , WLB_{BMD} and WLB_{MOM} ranked the top because they have the lowest BIC values while $W2_{BMD}$, $W2_{MOM}$, $W2_{LMOM}$, $W2_{LSE}$ and $W3_{MML}$ ranked the last. The Bayesian methods (BM, BD and BMD) have a median BIC of 5458.31 which is slightly less than 5477.55 of the frequentist methods (MLM, LSE, MOM, LMOM, PDM, MLM and MM).

Figure 30 Boxplots of (A) the used PDFs, (B) the frequentist and the Bayesian PEMs ordered by ascending median BIC to the wind speed data in In-Salah measured at 10 m AGL.

Figure 31 (A) and Figure 31 (B) show the performance of the models according to the root mean squared error of the empirical cumulative distribution ($RMSE_{PP}$) and the root mean squared error of the probability density function ($RMSE_{PDF}$) respectively. Figures 32 (A) and (C) rank the four PDFs in ascending order according to their median values of $RMSE_{PP}$ and $RMSE_{PDF}$ respectively, while Figures 32 (B) and (D) rank the frequentist and the Bayesian parameter estimation methods in ascending order according to their median values of $RMSE_{PP}$ and $RMSE_{PDF}$ respectively.

It can be seen that indeed the interpretation of the results depends on the used goodness-of-fit metric because, in contrast to BIC, the models based on WLB ranked the last according to $RMSE_{PP}$ as shown in Figure 32 (A). The cumulative distribution function of WW matches the best the empirical CDF as WW_{BD} has the lowest median $RMSE_{PP}$ of 0.0290 (m/s) followed by WW_{BM} then WW_{BMD} . Although $RMSE_{PDF}$ has the same formula as $RMSE_{PP}$ yet they rank the four PDFs differently. The first stated that the models based on W3 and WLB are the closest to the empirical frequency distribution of the data, while the latter showed that WW and W2

Chapter 4 Results and interpretation

deviated the least from the empirical cumulative distribution function. However, the two metrics both agree on the outperformance of the Bayesian methods.

Figure 31 Boxplots of (A) $RMSE_{PP}$ (B) $RMSE_{PDF}$ values related to the models based on the combination PDF/PEM for the wind speed data in In-Salah measured at 10 m AGL.

Figure 32 Boxplots of (A, C) the used PDFs, (B, D) the frequentist and the Bayesian PEMs ordered by ascending median $RMSE_{PP}$ and ascending median $RMSE_{PDF}$ to the wind speed data in In-Salah measured at 10 m AGL.

Chapter 4 Results and interpretation

Figure 33 (A) and Figure 33 (B) show the performance of the models according to the mean absolute error of the empirical cumulative distribution (MAE_{PP}) and the mean absolute error of the probability density function (MAE_{PDF}) respectively. Figures 34 (A) and (C) rank the four PDFs in ascending order according to their median values of MAE_{PP} and MAE_{PDF} respectively, while Figures 34 (B) and (D) rank the frequentist and the Bayesian parameter estimation methods in ascending order according to their median values of MAE_{PP} and MAE_{PDF} respectively.

Unlike $RMSE_{PP}$ and $RMSE_{PDF}$, the two mean absolute error metrics agree on that WW_{BD} , WW_{BMD} then WW_{BM} are the fittest models; on that the models that used the bimodal Weibull distribution have the minimum distance to the empirical CDF and the empirical wind speed frequency distribution as it has the lowest median MAE_{PP} (0.0202 m/s) and the lowest MAE_{PDF} (0.0239 m/s); and on the better performance of the Bayesian methods. However, MAE_{PP} considers $W3_{MLM}$ and $W3_{BM}$ the next best models while MAE_{PDF} considers WLB_{LSE} and WLB_{PDM} the next best models. This difference between the two metrics is clear in Figures 34 (A) and (C).

Figure 33 Boxplots of (A) MAE_{PP} (B) MAE_{PDF} values related to the models based on the combination PDF/PEM for the wind speed data in In-Salah measured at 10 m AGL.

Figure 34 Boxplots of (A, C) the used PDFs, (B, D) the frequentist and the Bayesian PEMS ordered by ascending median MAE_{PP} and ascending median MAE_{PDF} to the wind speed data in In-Salah measured at 10 m AGL.

4.5 Assessing the wind power density

The wind power density (WPD) is an important metric that evaluates the wind power potential in a particular site. This metric is indifferent to the type of wind turbine as it quantifies in W/m^2 . For this reason, it is imperative to check the suitability of W2, WLB, W3, and WW using frequentist and Bayesian methods of estimation in predicting the wind power output. To this end two goodness-of-fit are used, the wind power error (WPE) and the coefficient of determination (R^2). Figure 35 displays the fitness evaluation of the models based on the wind power error (WPE) for the annual and the monthly samples of the wind speed data in In-Salah measured at 10 m AGL. Figure 36 (A) and Figure 36 (B) rank the four PDFs and the frequentist and the Bayesian parameter estimation methods in ascending order according to their median WPE values respectively. Figure 37 shows the scatterplots of WPD computed values via W2, WLB, W3, and WW versus those computed by the wind speed data in In-Salah measured at 10 m height ranked by descending R^2 .

Chapter 4 Results and interpretation

Most of the models underestimated WPD, the only exceptions are WW_{BD} , WW_{BM} , WLB_{BMD} and $W2_{BMD}$. On the other hand $W2_{PDM}$ and WLB_{LSE} have the lowest and the widest range of values. However, even though $W2_{PDM}$ has the smallest range of WPE values yet WLB_{PDM} ranked first because it has the lowest median. Overall, the models that involve PDM deviated the least from the empirical WPD while the models based on LSE deviated the most from the empirical WPD. This is clearly illustrated in Figure 37 as WLB_{PDM} and $W2_{PDM}$ are the top two; and WLB_{LSE} , $W3_{LSE}$ and $W2_{LSE}$ are the bottom three. According to WPE, the Weibull-length-biased ranked the first with -0.20%, followed closely by followed by the five-parameter bimodal Weibull with 0.25%, then the two-parameter Weibull with -0.47%, and finally the three-parameter Weibull with -0.68%. Similar to the previous goodness-of-fit metrics, WPE stated that the Bayesian methods are better than the frequentist methods as they have median values of -0.11% and -0.42% respectively.

Figure 35 Boxplots of WPE values related to the models based on the combination PDF/PEM for the wind speed data in In-Salah measured at 10 m AGL.

Figure 36 Boxplots of (A) the used PDFs, (B) the frequentist and the Bayesian PEMs ordered by ascending median WPE to the wind speed data in In-Salah measured at 10 m AGL.

Figure 37 Scatterplots of WPD computed values via W2, WLB, W3 and WW versus those computed by the wind speed data in In-Salah measured at 10 m height ranked by descending R^2 .

4.6 Wind power indicators

Figures 30, 32, 34, and 36 indicated that the five-parameter bimodal Weibull ranked as the best PDF three times ($RMSE_{PP}$, MAE_{PP} , and MAE_{PDF}), followed by the two-parameter Weibull-length-biased which was the top PDF two times (BIC and WPE) then the three-parameter Weibull which classified the first according to $RMSE_{PDF}$. The widely used two-parameter Weibull never was the best PDF and at best it was the second-best PDF ($RMSE_{PP}$ and WPE). The ranks of the best models for each metric are summarized in Table 29. These ranks were used to decide which model should be used to calculate the wind energy indicators of In-Salah at 10 m AGL. It was remarked that WLB_{PDM} , WW_{BD} and WW_{BMD} ranked as the top model twice unlike the rest. However, it seems that WW_{BD} is the most favored model.

Table 29 Ranking of the best models

Best models	Wind speed					Power density	
	BIC	$RMSE_{PP}$	$RMSE_{PDF}$	MAE_{PP}	MAE_{PDF}	WPE	R ²
$W2_{PDM}$	17	5	8	12	15	2	1
WLB_{PDM}	1	21	7	21	6	1	2
WW_{BD}	11	1	11	1	2	6	3
WW_{BMD}	13	3	1	3	1	15	21

Note: The bold values indicate the best fit models for each metric.

Figures 38 to 41 illustrate the histograms of the annual and the monthly wind speed data superimposed by the fittest models listed in Table 29 in addition to the second and third top models for each goodness-of-fit metric. The visual inspection of Figure 38 reveals that the Weibull-length-biased (WLB) distribution fits better the annual wind speed frequency distribution in In-Salah better than the two-parameter Weibull (W2). However, both distributions are preceded by the five-parameter bimodal Weibull (WW) as it accurately locates the mode. The three-parameter Weibull (W3) is absent in this figure due to the strenuous estimates of the location parameter. Figures 39, 40, and 41 depicts that the supremacy of WW is evident in fitting the wind speed frequency distribution of February, April, September, and October, and it fitted January, March, June, August, and November wind speed data slightly

better than the other PDFs. Moreover, WLB represented better the data of May, July, and December.

Figure 38 Histogram with the best fitted models for the used annual wind speed data

Figure 39 Histograms with the best fitted models for the wind speed data of (A) January, (B) February, (C) March and (D) April

Figure 40 Histograms with the best fitted models for the data of (A) May, (B) June, (C) July and (D) August

Figure 41 Histograms with the best fitted models for the data of (A) September, (B) October, (C) November and (D) December

The most probable wind speed V_{mp} or simply the mode (Mo) and the wind speed carrying maximum energy V_{MaxE} are important statistics that help pick the optimal wind turbine. Jaramillo and Borja [85] stated that for a bimodal wind distribution, it must be considered the right distribution where most wind turbines generate their maximum power. The most probable wind speed and the wind speed carrying maximum energy can be expressed by

$$V_{mp} = \alpha_2 \left(1 - \frac{1}{\beta_2}\right)^{\frac{1}{\beta_2}} \quad (18)$$

$$V_{MaxE} = \alpha_2 \left(1 + \frac{2}{\beta_2}\right)^{\frac{1}{\beta_2}} \quad (19)$$

The annual and seasonal values of some of the wind power indicators are detailed in Table 30. These indicators include the median posterior estimates of the five-parameter bimodal Weibull distribution (α_1 , β_1 , α_2 , β_2 and ω), the mean average speed (\bar{V}), the standard deviation wind speed (δ), the most probable wind speed (Mo), the wind speed carrying maximum energy (V_{MaxE}) and the mean wind density power (WPD). It can be seen that V_{mp} , V_{maxE} and \bar{V} have

Chapter 4 Results and interpretation

an increasing trend over the years. It is clear that V_{mp} , and V_{maxE} display seasonal variability where their monthly values are at its highest during the autumn and the winter. The monthly V_{mp} , V_{maxE} and \bar{V} are confined in the range 4.29 – 8.30 m/s, 5.05 – 10.71 m/s and 6.24 – 8.55 m/s respectively. It can be noticed that WPD exceeds 300 W/m² during the period between May and August and reach a maximum of 473.34 W/m².

Table 30 Wind power indicators

Time-series	α_1 (m/s)	β_1	α_2 (m/s)	β_2	ω	\bar{V} (m/s)	δ (m/s)	Mo (m/s)	V_{MaxE} (m/s)	WPD (W/m ²)
Jan	9.11	3.23	5.82	3.45	0.57	6.91	2.31	5.27	6.64	281.93
Feb	9.56	3.30	5.84	3.88	0.48	6.85	2.16	5.41	6.50	279.14
Mar	8.90	3.29	5.21	4.14	0.73	7.11	2.30	4.87	5.73	299.16
Apr	9.03	2.93	4.90	3.87	0.55	6.42	2.22	4.54	5.46	257.03
May	9.02	3.42	4.59	4.11	0.75	7.11	2.25	4.29	5.05	306.74
Jun	9.08	3.00	4.60	4.15	0.75	7.11	2.49	4.31	5.06	326.27
Jul	8.97	3.34	5.74	3.52	0.84	7.59	2.49	5.22	6.53	343.60
Aug	9.12	3.17	6.56	3.45	0.57	7.18	2.42	5.94	7.49	301.10
Sep	10.37	2.89	6.88	3.25	0.12	6.54	2.25	6.15	7.98	232.51
Oct	8.80	3.46	5.16	4.44	0.48	6.24	1.84	4.87	5.61	210.66
Nov	8.40	2.56	6.80	2.71	0.61	6.90	2.84	5.75	8.34	292.01
Dec	9.86	3.24	9.27	3.29	0.45	8.55	2.88	8.30	10.71	473.34
Annual	8.82	3.04	5.31	3.92	0.74	7.09	2.45	4.92	5.90	331.69

Table 31 depicts the posterior predictive distribution of the mean wind speed (\bar{V}) and the mean wind power density (WPD). The mean wind speed in In-Salah at 10 m AGL has a posterior predictive distribution of mean 7.11 m/s and standard deviation of 2.41 m/s, and there is a 95% posterior chance that \bar{V} is in the credible interval of [2.45, 11.95]. Similarly to \bar{V} , the mean wind power density in In-Salah at 10 m AGL has a posterior predictive distribution of mean 331.70 W/m² and standard deviation of 15 W/m²; and there is 95% posterior chance that WPD is in the credible interval of [302.07, 360.68]. Figures 42 and 43 illustrate the posterior predictive distributions of \bar{V} and WPD respectively.

Table 31 Posterior predictive distribution of the mean wind speed and the mean wind power density in In-Salah at 10 m AGL

Posterior predictive distribution	Mean	Standard deviation	Median	Lower 2.5%	Upper 97.5%
Mean wind speed (m/s)	7.11	2.41	7.08	2.45	11.95
Mean wind power density (W/m ²)	331.70	15.00	331.80	302.08	360.67

Figure 42 Posterior predictive distribution of the annual mean wind speed \bar{V} in In-Salah at 10 m AGL

Figure 43 Posterior predictive distribution of the annual mean wind power density WPD in In-Salah at 10 m AGL

4.7 Limitations of the study

It can be stated that the utilized dataset is recent (2015-2016) and its temporal resolution is among the best as the wind speed data were averaged every hour unlike the tri-horal or the daily data used in most of the studies in Table 2. However, when comparing this dataset to the

ones used in the universal studies reviewed by Jung and Schindler [24], it can be remarked that the hourly temporal resolution is not enough. This was highlighted by Jung and Schindler [24] as they gave a null score for the temporal resolution to any study that based its results on a wind speed dataset that was averaged every hour or more (Table 1). Another limitation about this dataset is it was measured at a single height, and the anemometer height is below 2/3 of the usual wind turbines hub height i.e. at 10 m AGL. Again Jung and Schindler [24] gave zero for the height score to any study that based its results on a wind speed dataset measured below 50 m AGL (Table 1). Unfortunately, these are common characteristics in Algerian studies as the main provider of the meteorological data is the National Meteorological Office (ONM). However, it should be stated that the wind speed data measured by the National Meteorological Office is intended to serve the aeronautics market. Another limitation that should be highlighted is that the yearly valid number of observations from this data is 83.27% in 2015 and 82.13% in 2016. This means that the yearly data losses are approximately 16.73% and 17.67%. However, this doesn't detract from the value of this study as the data losses are below 20%.

Finally, the Bayesian analysis using "JAGS" via "RStudio" using the packages "R2jags" and "rjags" is way time-consuming in comparison to the frequentist methods. It was noticed that the sample size, the number of the parameters to be estimated, and the type of the distribution impact the computation time to calculate the Bayesian estimates. It was noticed that

- The Bayesian estimation process took less time for the two-parameter Weibull and the two-parameter Weibull-length-biased than the three-parameter Weibull and the five-parameter bimodal Weibull.
- The Weibull-length-biased is more computationally expensive than the two-parameter Weibull even though they have the same number of parameters.

This might be problematic because, unlike survival analysis studies, wind-industry related studies do not suffer from a shortage in the observed data nor need censoring.

4.8 Discussion

Two years of hourly wind speed measurements at In-Salah at 10 m AGL were subject to this comparative study that aimed to assess the wind power potential accurately. In addition to the

widely used two-parameter Weibull, three PDFs were used namely the three-parameter Weibull, the Weibull-length-biased, and the bimodal Weibull. The parameter estimation process included Frequentist and Bayesian methods. The judgment process contained metrics that are bin-free like the Bayesian information criterion and other bin-specific metrics. However, some of these metrics measure the deviation of the models from the empirical frequency distribution of the data such as $RMSE_{PDF}$ and MAE_{PDF} , some quantify the deviation of the models from the empirical cumulative distribution of the data such as $RMSE_{PP}$ and MAE_{PP} and others measure how accurately was the wind power density measured like R^2_{power} and WPE.

Screening the data revealed that the wind speed data in In-Salah exhibit a positive skewness behavior, thus using Weibull models is admissible. Informative priors were utilized to get the posterior estimates of the parameters of W2, WLB, and WW. These priors are based on the annual distribution of the shape parameter in Algeria at 10 m AGL. Trace plot and Brooks-Gelman-Rubin statistic stated that the usage of these priors seems successful as the posterior model for the three PDFs seems stationary as depicted in Figures 23 to 26. The frequentist and the Bayesian estimates of W2, WLB, W3, and WW were listed in Tables 20 to 27. It was noticed from Table 26 that all the estimates of the location parameter τ_{W3} are negative for the annual wind speed data and also for the monthly distribution in November and December. This might be explained by the low value of the minimum wind speed $v_{(1)}$ which was 0.1 m/s in the three samples. In other words, the PEMs could not confine τ_{W3} in the interval $[0, v_{(1)}]$. The only exception was the modified maximum likelihood (MML) as it estimated τ_{W3} to be 0.04 m/s. The monthly and the annual left distribution of the wind speed is mostly more significant than the right distribution according to the annual and the monthly values of the mixing parameter in Table 27. This is expected since the wind speed is skewed to the right phenomenon.

As stated by the goodness-of-fit statistics in Table 28, the models based on the Weibull-length-biased, the bimodal Weibull distributions, and the Bayesian method of estimation are the fittest. This was confirmed by running a global study that involved the monthly samples. The

results of the goodness-of-fit analysis are illustrated in Figures 25 to 33. The bimodal Weibull fitted the annual and the monthly wind speed data better than the other metrics according to $RMSE_{PP}$, MAE_{PP} , MAE_{PDF} and WPE. No doubt that having five parameters made WW more flexible than the other PDFs. WW was outrun by WLB and W2 in terms of predicting the wind power density as indicated by R^2_{power} . As discussed by [80], this might be because WW provides a good fit to the entire data histogram in general, but it might under-predict the upper tail of the wind speed distribution. The three-parameter Weibull classified the last yet only once (WPE), and ranked as the top PDF once ($RMSE_{PDF}$). This might be explained by the fact that when the minimum wind speed is close to zero, both frequentist and Bayesian PEMs struggle to assure a positive estimate of the location parameter.

The Weibull-length-biased deviated the least from the wind speed data based on BIC, was the second-best PDF according to $RMSE_{PDF}$ and MAE_{PDF} , and gave the most accurate estimations to the empirical wind power density according to WPE. This distribution gives more weight to the tails which might suit skewed distributions like the wind speed as it usually skewed to the right. The ordinary two-parameter Weibull often classified the worst among the four used PDFs (BIC, MAE_{PDF} and WPE) and as the third best PDF ($RMSE_{PDF}$ and MAE_{PP}). This is an indicator that these modifications i.e. mixing it with another Weibull, using the length-biased version, or adding a location parameter indeed did enhance the performance of Weibull. Bayesian methods have the upper hand over the frequentist methods for all the goodness-of-fit measures. This might due to the advantage of using the informative prior of the annual distribution of the shape parameter in Algeria.

Getting the posterior predictive distribution of the mean wind speed and the mean wind power density is undoubtedly far more informative than getting just a single statistic that describes them. The mean wind speed has a posterior predictive distribution of mean 7.11 m/s and the credible interval is [2.45, 11.95]. This is useful in predicting the probability of the annual mean wind speed that exceeds or below a certain value. This information is valuable as it allows

knowing when the wind turbine is operational on average or when the wind turbine is under pressure which can be useful in estimating the life expectancy of the wind turbine.

Conclusion

In this chapter, a robust comparative study was undertaken to optimize the wind power assessment in In-Salah, Algeria's windiest site, which was previously done using the ordinary two-parameter Weibull, and its shape and scale parameters were estimated using frequentist methods. W2 and the frequentist estimation methods were compared with the three-parameter Weibull, the Weibull-length-biased and the bimodal Weibull distributions, and the Bayesian method of estimation. The analysis revealed the meager performance of W2 as it frequently ranked the last, and the supremacy of the bimodal Weibull and the Weibull-length-biased distribution according to the used goodness-of-fit metrics. The analysis also revealed that the Bayesian estimates were more accurate than their frequentist analogs. The posterior predictive distributions of the mean wind speed and the mean wind power density have means of 7.09 m/s and 331.68 W/m² respectively. The uncertainty in these calculations is expressed in their respective credible intervals of [2.35, 11.95], and [301.98, 360.67].

Chapter 5 General conclusion

Decarbonizing the power systems can help mitigate the negative effects of global warming. Wind as one of the cheapest renewable power sources might be suitable to decrease the heavy dependency of the Algerian power system on natural gas. To this aim, Algeria is to rump up the wind power capacity to 5 GW from the current 10.2 MW. A literature review analysis was undertaken to give an image of the probabilistic tools used to assess the wind power potential in the country. It was found from the non-exhaustive list of the Algerian studies that discussed this subject, almost all of them used solely the two-parameter Weibull (W2) and 43.75% utilized the maximum likelihood method to estimate the scale and the shape parameters.

Although the use of the two-parameter Weibull to model the wind speed is just because of its attractive properties that made and under the recommendation of the International Electrotechnical Commission. However, it cannot be expected that the wind regimes in a large country like Algeria are not bimodal, multimodal, do not blow in low speed, or do not have a small range of variation since many studies have shown that two-parameter Weibull fit poorly these types of wind regimes. Nevertheless, instead of using entirely different probability density functions why not just modify the two-parameter Weibull to enhance its performance. In this study, it was suggested to utilize the Weibull-length-biased which is the length-biased version of W2, the three-parameter Weibull (W3) which adds a location parameter to W2, and the five-parameter bimodal Weibull (WW) which mixes W2 with another W2.

It was illustrated in chapter two that it is essential to predict well the intermittent nature of wind to increase the reliability of the electricity generated from wind. Using suitable laws makes it easier to predict the variability with height. Therefore, the power law and logarithmic law are the commonly used laws in Algeria. On the other hand, to minimize the wind power variability, it was explained that the geographical dispersion of the wind farms can be useful. In the case of Algeria, several sites have been identified to be adequate for siting large-scale wind farms such as Mechria, Bou-Chekif, Tiaret, Djelfa, and M'sila in the highlands; Hassi-R'mel in the Northern Sahara; Tindouf, Adrar, Timimoun in the Western Sahara and; In-Salah in the Central

Sahara. The variability of wind speed over time might be the most challenging aspect of using wind as a power source. It is a common practice to use a probabilistic distribution to model the stochastic variation of wind, as this can facilitate the calculation of the amount of the annual wind power for a specific area.

Chapter three discussed the employed probabilistic tools to model the wind speed. This contained, on one hand, the following PDFs the widely used two-parameter Weibull (W2) and a set of alternative probability distribution functions that included the three-parameter Weibull (W3), the five-parameter bimodal Weibull (WW), and the two-parameter Weibull-length-biased (WLB), and on the other hand, the Bayesian and frequentist parameter estimation methods. The employed parameter estimation methods involved frequent methods of such as the maximum likelihood method (MLM), the least-squares estimation method (LSE), the moments method (MOM) and the method of linear moments (LMOM). In addition to the power density method (PDM) since it has attractive feature of minimizing the distance between the empirical and the population energy pattern factor; the modified maximum likelihood (MML) and the modified moments method (MM) to address the problem of finding suitable estimates to the location parameter of W3.

Using multiple goodness-of-fit metrics decreases the biasness in the results. The chosen goodness-of-fit metrics in this study quantify the modeling error differently. The Bayesian information criterion (BIC) is a bin-free statistic and disfavors complicated probability distribution functions with a high number of parameters to estimate. Two types of the root mean squared error and the absolute mean error were used. One that measures the deviation of the model's cumulative frequency distribution from the empirical cumulative frequency distribution of the wind speed ($RMSE_{PP}$ and MAE_{PP}), and the other calculates the difference between the model's frequency distribution and the empirical cumulative frequency distribution of the wind speed ($RMSE_{PDF}$ and MAE_{PDF}). The list also included the wind power error (WPE) and the coefficient of determination (R^2_{power}) goodness-of-fit indicators as they

compute the error in estimating the mean wind power density (WPD) which is a useful metric that evaluates the wind power potential in a particular site.

Algeria's windiest site was the subject of the comprehensive comparison analysis in chapter four. A dataset of 14510 hourly wind speed observations measured from January 2015 to December 2016 in In-Salah at 10 m AGL were fitted by the four aforementioned PDFs employing the Bayesian and the frequentist methods of estimation. The data was portioned into monthly samples to predict the behavior of wind throughout the year. The usage of the Weibull models was admissible since the annual and the monthly had positive skewness. The implementation of the proposed priors seemed successful since the resulting posterior models were stationary. The mean, the median, and the mode of the posterior distributions were taken as the Bayesian estimates of the parameters.

It was concluded from the goodness-of-fit analysis that the bimodal Weibull is the most accurate among the four used PDFs, as it had the least error in modeling the wind speed according to the root mean absolute error ($RMSE_{PP}$), the mean absolute error (MAE_{PP} and MAE_{PDF}), and the wind power error (WPE). It was followed by the Weibull-length-biased, the three-parameter Weibull, and lastly the two-parameter Weibull respectively. All the utilized goodness-of-fit metrics stated that the Bayesian estimates are more accurate than the frequentists estimates. The only metric that depicted otherwise is R^2_{power} . Moreover, the estimates based on the posterior median performed better than the posterior mean and the posterior mode estimates. However, an advantage of using the Bayesian approach is that the posterior density function uses all the Bayesian estimates, which in this case 20000 Bayesian estimates for each parameter of the bimodal Weibull. It was found that the posterior predictive distributions of the mean wind speed and the mean wind power density have means of 7.09 m/s and 331.68 W/m² respectively. The uncertainty in these calculations is expressed in their respective credible intervals of [2.35, 11.95], and [301.98, 360.67]. Indeed the wind power potential in In-Salah is quite promising, and the site should be prioritized for large-scale wind

Chapter 5 General conclusion

farm installations especially that it is interconnected with the isolated pole network (PIAT) that is already penetrated by wind energy via Adrar's wind farm.

,

References

- [1] B. Dancygier, "Causes and consequences of global warming," *Int. J. Sci. Biotechnol. Pharma Res.*, vol. 1, no. 1, pp. 91–118, 2012.
- [2] J. M. Rey-Hernández, C. Yousif, D. Gatt, E. Velasco-Gómez, J. San José-Alonso, and F. J. Rey-Martínez, "Modelling the long-term effect of climate change on a zero energy and carbon dioxide building through energy efficiency and renewables," *Energy Build.*, vol. 174, pp. 85–96, 2018.
- [3] J. Peter, "How does climate change affect electricity system planning and optimal allocation of variable renewable energy?," *Appl. Energy*, vol. 252, no. February, p. 113397, 2019.
- [4] M. Ortega-Izquierdo and P. del Río, "An analysis of the socioeconomic and environmental benefits of wind energy deployment in Europe," *Renew. Energy*, vol. 160, pp. 1067–1080, 2020.
- [5] R. Saidur, M. R. Islam, N. A. Rahim, and K. H. Solangi, "A review on global wind energy policy," *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.*, vol. 14, no. 7, pp. 1744–1762, 2010.
- [6] Kusch-Brandt, *Urban Renewable Energy on the Upswing: A Spotlight on Renewable Energy in Cities in REN21's "Renewables 2019 Global Status Report,"* vol. 8, no. 3. 2019.
- [7] REN21, *Renewables 2020 Global Status Report*. 2020.
- [8] IRENA, *Renewable capacity statistics 2020 International Renewable Energy Agency*. 2020.
- [9] M. Ouki, *Algerian Gas in Transition : Domestic transformation and changing gas export potential*, no. October. 2019.
- [10] A. Bouraiou *et al.*, "Status of renewable energy potential and utilization in Algeria," *J. Clean. Prod.*, vol. 246, p. 119011, 2020.
- [11] Y. Himri, S. Rehman, B. Draoui, and S. Himri, "Wind power potential assessment for three locations in Algeria," *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.*, vol. 12, no. 9, pp. 2495–2504, 2008.
- [12] A. Boudghene Stambouli, "Algerian renewable energy assessment: The challenge of sustainability," *Energy Policy*, vol. 39, no. 8, pp. 4507–4519, 2011.
- [13] F. Chellali, A. Khellaf, A. Belouchrani, and A. Recioui, "A contribution in the actualization of wind map of Algeria," *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.*, vol. 15, no. 2, pp. 993–1002, 2011.
- [14] M. Djamai and N. Kasbadji Merzouk, "Wind farm feasibility study and site selection in Adrar, Algeria," *Energy Procedia*, vol. 6, pp. 136–142, 2011.
- [15] S. M. Boudia, A. Benmansour, and M. A. Tabet Hellal, "Wind resource assessment in Algeria," *Sustain. Cities Soc.*, vol. 22, pp. 171–183, 2016.
- [16] H. Daaou Nedjari, S. K. Haddouche, A. Balehouane, and O. Guerri, "Optimal windy sites in Algeria: Potential and perspectives," *Energy*, vol. 147, pp. 1240–1255, 2018.
- [17] G. Kim and J. Hur, "Probabilistic modeling of wind energy potential for power grid expansion planning," *Energy*, vol. 230, p. 120831, 2021.
- [18] V. E. L. A. Duca, T. C. O. Fonseca, and F. L. Cyrino Oliveira, "A generalized dynamical model for wind speed forecasting," *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.*, vol. 136, no. September 2020, p. 110421, 2021.
- [19] J. Zhou, E. Erdem, G. Li, and J. Shi, "Comprehensive evaluation of wind speed distribution models: A case study for North Dakota sites," *Energy Convers. Manag.*, vol. 51, no. 7, pp. 1449–1458, 2010.
- [20] T. P. Chang, "Performance comparison of six numerical methods in estimating Weibull parameters for wind energy application," *Appl. Energy*, vol. 88, no. 1, pp. 272–282, 2011.
- [21] P. Tiam Kapen, M. Jeutho Gouajio, and D. Yemélé, "Analysis and efficient comparison of ten numerical methods in estimating Weibull parameters for wind energy potential: Application to the city of Bafoussam, Cameroon," *Renew. Energy*, vol. 159, pp. 1188–1198, 2020.
- [22] M. A. Saeed, Z. Ahmed, and W. Zhang, "Wind energy potential and economic analysis with a

- comparison of different methods for determining the optimal distribution parameters," *Renew. Energy*, vol. 161, pp. 1092–1109, 2020.
- [23] C. Jung and D. Schindler, "Wind speed distribution selection – A review of recent development and progress," *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.*, vol. 114, no. July, p. 109290, 2019.
- [24] B. Belabes, A. Youcefi, O. Guerri, M. Djamai, and A. Kaabeche, "Evaluation of wind energy potential and estimation of cost using wind energy turbines for electricity generation in north of Algeria," *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.*, vol. 51, pp. 1245–1255, 2015.
- [25] F. Chellali, A. Khellaf, A. Belouchrani, and R. Khanniche, "A comparison between wind speed distributions derived from the maximum entropy principle and Weibull distribution. Case of study; Six regions of Algeria," *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.*, vol. 16, no. 1, pp. 379–385, 2012.
- [26] Y. Himri, S. Rehman, A. Agus Setiawan, and S. Himri, "Wind energy for rural areas of Algeria," *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.*, vol. 16, no. 5, pp. 2381–2385, 2012.
- [27] S. M. Boudia and J. A. Santos, "Assessment of large-scale wind resource features in Algeria," *Energy*, vol. 189, 2019.
- [28] D. Saheb Koussa, M. Koussa, and S. Hadji, "Assessment of various WTG (wind turbine generators) production in different Algerian's climatic zones," *Energy*, vol. 96, pp. 449–460, 2016.
- [29] N. Aries, S. M. Boudia, and H. Ounis, "Deep assessment of wind speed distribution models : A case study of four sites in Algeria," *Energy Convers. Manag.*, vol. 155, no. August 2017, pp. 78–90, 2018.
- [30] S. M. Boudia and O. Guerri, "Investigation of wind power potential at Oran, northwest of Algeria," *Energy Convers. Manag.*, vol. 105, pp. 81–92, 2015.
- [31] A. Mezidi, O. Guerri, S. M. Boudia, and K. Mohammedi, "Influence of wind data temporal variation in wind resource assessment. two case studies in the southern part of Algeria," *Energy Sources, Part A Recover. Util. Environ. Eff.*, vol. 42, no. 2, pp. 161–175, 2020.
- [32] S. M. Boudia, A. Benmansour, N. Ghellai, M. Benmedjahed, and M. A. Tabet Hellal, "Monthly and seasonal assessment of wind energy potential in Mechria region, occidental highlands of Algeria," *Int. J. Green Energy*, vol. 9, no. 3, pp. 243–255, 2012.
- [33] D. Abdeslame, N. Kasbadji Merzouk, S. Mekhtoub, M. Abbas, and M. Dehmas, "Estimation of power generation capacities of a wind farms installed in windy sites in Algerian high plateaus," *Renew. Energy*, vol. 103, pp. 630–640, 2017.
- [34] Y. Himri, M. Merzouk, N. Kasbadji Merzouk, and S. Himri, "Potential and economic feasibility of wind energy in south West region of Algeria," *Sustain. Energy Technol. Assessments*, vol. 38, no. January, p. 100643, 2020.
- [35] G. Li and J. Shi, "Applications of Bayesian methods in wind energy conversion systems," *Renew. Energy*, vol. 43, pp. 1–8, 2012.
- [36] J. A. A. Carta *et al.*, "A review of wind speed probability distributions used in wind energy analysis. Case studies in the Canary Islands," *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.*, vol. 13, no. 5, pp. 933–955, 2009.
- [37] W.-K. Pang, J. J. Forster, and M. D. Troutt, "Estimation of Wind Speed Distribution Using Markov Chain Monte Carlo Techniques," *J. Appl. Meteorol.*, vol. 40, no. 8, pp. 1476–1484, 2002.
- [38] P. Erto, A. Lanzotti, and A. Lepore, "Wind speed parameter estimation from one-month sample via Bayesian approach," *Qual. Reliab. Eng. Int.*, vol. 26, no. 8, pp. 853–862, 2010.
- [39] J. A. Carta, S. Velázquez, and J. M. Matías, "Use of Bayesian networks classifiers for long-term mean wind turbine energy output estimation at a potential wind energy conversion site," *Energy Convers. Manag.*, vol. 52, no. 2, pp. 1137–1149, 2011.
- [40] T. Adedipe, M. Shafiee, and E. Zio, "Bayesian Network Modelling for the Wind Energy Industry: An Overview," *Reliab. Eng. Syst. Saf.*, vol. 202, no. May, p. 107053, 2020.
- [41] A. Schlosser, C. Fant, B. Gunturu, and A. Schlosser, "Characterizing wind power resource

- reliability in southern Africa Characterizing wind power resource reliability in southern Africa," *Appl. Energy*, vol. 161, no. April 2016, pp. 565–573, 2015.
- [42] N. Y. Yürüşen and J. J. Melero, "Probability density function selection based on the characteristics of wind speed data," *J. Phys. Conf. Ser.*, vol. 753, no. 3, 2016.
- [43] L. Freris and D. Infield, *Renewable energy in power systems*. 2008.
- [44] M. H. Ali, *Wind energy systems: Solutions for power quality and stabilization*. 2012.
- [45] T. Burton, D. Sharpe, N. Jenkins, and E. Bossanyi, *WIND ENERGY HANDBOOK*. 2001.
- [46] T. M. Letcher, *Wind Energy Engineering: A Handbook for Onshore and Offshore Wind Turbines*. Academic Press, 2017.
- [47] J. F. Manwell and J. McGowan, *Wind Energy Explained Theory, Design and Application*. University of Massachusetts, Amherst, USA: John Wiley & Sons, LTD, 2002.
- [48] V. Warudkar, S. Ahmed, and P. K. Chaurasiya, "Application of Remote Sensing in Wind Resource Assessment," *Ref. Modul. Mater. Sci. Mater. Eng.*, no. November, 2019.
- [49] Sathyajith Mathew, *Wind Energy Fundamentals, Resource Analysis and Economics*, 1st ed. Springer-Verlag Berlin Heidelberg, 2006.
- [50] A. R. Jha, *Wind Turbine Technology*. Taylor & Francis Group, 2011.
- [51] M. A. Baseer, J. P. Meyer, S. Rehman, and M. M. Alam, "Wind power characteristics of seven data collection sites in Jubail, Saudi Arabia using Weibull parameters," *Renew. Energy*, vol. 102, pp. 35–49, 2017.
- [52] S. Louassa, O. Guerri, A. Kaabeche, and N. Yassaa, "Effects of local ambient air temperatures on wind park performance: case of the Kaberten wind park," *Energy Sources, Part A Recover. Util. Environ. Eff.*, pp. 1–14, 2019.
- [53] W. Tong, *Wind Power Generation and Wind Turbine Design*, vol. 44, no. 12. Southhampton, Boston, 2010.
- [54] S. Diaf and G. Notton, "Technical and economic analysis of large-scale wind energy conversion systems in Algeria," *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.*, vol. 19, pp. 37–51, 2013.
- [55] K. Mohammadi, O. Alavi, A. Mostafaeipour, N. Goudarzi, and M. Jalilvand, "Assessing different parameters estimation methods of Weibull distribution to compute wind power density," *Energy Convers. Manag.*, vol. 108, pp. 322–335, 2016.
- [56] T. P. Chang, "Estimation of wind energy potential using different probability density functions," *Appl. Energy*, vol. 88, no. 5, pp. 1848–1856, 2011.
- [57] A. Keyhani, M. Ghasemi-Varnamkhasti, M. Khanali, and R. Abbaszadeh, "An assessment of wind energy potential as a power generation source in the capital of Iran, Tehran," *Energy*, vol. 35, no. 1, pp. 188–201, 2009.
- [58] M. S. Adaramola and O. M. Oyewola, "Evaluating the performance of wind turbines in selected locations in Oyo state, Nigeria," *Renew. Energy*, vol. 36, no. 12, pp. 3297–3304, 2011.
- [59] S. Diaf and G. Notton, "Evaluation of electricity generation and energy cost of wind energy conversion systems in southern Algeria," *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.*, vol. 23, pp. 379–390, 2013.
- [60] T. R. Ayodele, A. A. Jimoh, J. L. Munda, and J. T. Agee, "Wind distribution and capacity factor estimation for wind turbines in the coastal region of South Africa," *Energy Convers. Manag.*, vol. 64, pp. 614–625, 2012.
- [61] ABB, "Technical Application Papers No.13 Wind power plants," no. 13, p. 136, 2011.
- [62] W. David, *Small Wind Turbines Analysis, Design and Application*. University of Calgary, Canada: Springer, 2012.
- [63] The Royal Academy of Engineering, *Wind energy: Implications of large-scale deployment on the GB electricity system*, no. April. 2014.
- [64] W. Katzenstein, "Wind power variability, its cost, and effect on power plant emissions," *Diss. Abstr. Int. B Sci. Eng.*, vol. 71, no. 11, p. 6862, 2011.

- [65] N. Chabouni, Y. Belarbi, and W. Benhassine, "Electricity load dynamics , temperature and seasonality Nexus in," *Energy*, vol. 200, p. 117513, 2020.
- [66] M. Benmemdejehed and S. Mouhadjer, "Evaluation of wind energy cost and site selection for a wind-farm in the south of Algeria," *AIP Conf. Proc.*, vol. 1758, 2016.
- [67] M. Benmedjahed, N. Ghellai, A. Benmansour, S. M. Boudai, and M. A. Tabet Hellal, "Assessment of wind energy and energy cost in Algeria," *Int. J. Renew. Energy*, vol. 9, no. 1, 2014.
- [68] "bp-stats-review-2021-all-data.xlsx." [Online]. Available: <https://view.officeapps.live.com/op/view.aspx?src=https%3A%2F%2Fwww.bp.com%2Fcontent%2Fdam%2Fbp%2Fbusiness-sites%2Fen%2Fglobal%2Fcorporate%2Fxlsx%2Fenergy-economics%2Fstatistical-review%2Fbp-stats-review-2021-all-data.xlsx&wdOrigin=BROWSELINK>. [Accessed: 26-Apr-2022].
- [69] H. Smail, R. Alkama, and A. Medjdoub, "Impact of large scale power plant connection on congestion in the algerian electricity transmission system," *Energy*, vol. 159, pp. 115–120, 2018.
- [70] B. Brand, A. Boudghene Stambouli, and D. Zejli, "The value of dispatchability of CSP plants in the electricity systems of Morocco and Algeria," *Energy Policy*, vol. 47, pp. 321–331, 2012.
- [71] L. Wang, K. Kerrouche, A. Mezouar, A. Van Den Bossche, A. Draou, and L. Boumediene, "Feasibility Study of Wind Farm Grid-Connected Project in Algeria under Grid Fault Conditions Using D-Facts Devices," *Appl. Sci.*, vol. 8, no. 11, p. 2250, 2018.
- [72] N. YASSAA and M. KHELIF, "Transition Energétique en Algérie Edition Leçons, Etat des Lieux et Perspectives pour un Développement Accéléré des Energies Renouvelables," 2020.
- [73] IRENA, *Renewable Power Generation Costs in 2020*. Abu Dhabi, 2020.
- [74] P. Díaz-cuevas, B. Haddad, and M. Fernandez-nunez, "Energy for the future : Planning and mapping renewable energy . The case of Algeria," *Sustain. Energy Technol. Assessments*, vol. 47, p. 101445, 2021.
- [75] H. Rinne, *The Weibull Distribution Handbook*. Justus-Liebig-University, Giessen, Germany: Taylor & Francis Group, 2013.
- [76] A. Mostafaeipour, A. Sedaghat, A. A. Dehghan-Niri, and V. Kalantar, "Wind energy feasibility study for city of Shahrabak in Iran," *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.*, vol. 15, no. 6, pp. 2545–2556, 2011.
- [77] D. A. Stewart and O. M. Essenwanger, "Frequency Distribution of Wind Speed Near The Surface," *Am. Meteorol. Soc.*, no. 78, pp. 1633–1642, 1978.
- [78] X. Chen, A. Foley, Z. Zhang, K. Wang, and K. O'Driscoll, "An assessment of wind energy potential in the Beibu Gulf considering the energy demands of the Beibu Gulf Economic Rim," *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.*, vol. 119, no. September 2018, p. 109605, 2020.
- [79] P. K. Chaurasiya, S. Ahmed, and V. Warudkar, "Comparative analysis of Weibull parameters for wind data measured from met-mast and remote sensing techniques," *Renew. Energy*, vol. 115, pp. 1153–1165, 2018.
- [80] E. C. Morgan, M. Lackner, R. M. Vogel, and L. G. Baise, "Probability distributions for offshore wind speeds," *Energy Convers. Manag.*, vol. 52, no. 1, pp. 15–26, 2011.
- [81] M. Ramakrishnan. and N. Viswanathan., "Comparing the methods of Estimation of Three-Parameter Weibull distribution," *IOSR J. Math.*, vol. 13, no. 01, pp. 41–45, 2017.
- [82] P. Wais, "Two and three-parameter Weibull distribution in available wind power analysis," *Renew. Energy*, vol. 103, pp. 15–29, 2017.
- [83] M. A. Elfarra and M. Kaya, "Comparison of optimum spline-based probability density functions to parametric distributions for the wind speed data in terms of annual energy production," *Energies*, vol. 11, no. 11, 2018.
- [84] J. A. Carta and P. Ramirez, "Analysis of two-component mixture Weibull statistics for estimation of wind speed distributions," *Renew. Energy*, vol. 32, no. 3, pp. 518–531, 2007.

-
- [85] O. A. Jaramillo and M. A. Borja, "Wind speed analysis in La Ventosa, Mexico: A bimodal probability distribution case," *Renew. Energy*, vol. 29, no. 10, pp. 1613–1630, 2004.
- [86] X. Qin, J. S. Zhang, and X. D. Yan, "Two improved mixture weibull models for the analysis of wind speed data," *J. Appl. Meteorol. Climatol.*, vol. 51, no. 7, pp. 1321–1332, 2012.
- [87] T. Arslan, F. Gül, S. Birdal, F. G. Akgül, B. Şenoglu, and T. Arslan, "An alternative distribution to Weibull for modeling the wind speed data: Inverse Weibull distribution," *Energy Convers. Manag.*, vol. 114, pp. 234–240, 2016.
- [88] Y. M. Kantar and I. Usta, "Analysis of the upper-truncated Weibull distribution for wind speed," *Energy Convers. Manag.*, vol. 96, pp. 81–88, 2015.
- [89] J. Qin, *Biased Sampling, Over-identified Parameter Problems and Beyond*. .
- [90] A. Saghir, A. Khadim, and Z. Lin, "The Maxwell length-biased distribution: Properties and estimation," *J. Stat. Theory Pract.*, vol. 11, no. 1, pp. 26–40, 2017.
- [91] J. Kersey and B. Oluyede, "Theoretical properties of the length-biased inverse Weibull distribution," *Involv. a J. Math.*, vol. 5, no. 4, pp. 379–391, 2012.
- [92] S. A. Shaban and N. Boudrissa, "THE WEIBULL LENGTH BIASED DISTRIBUTION -PROPERTIES AND ESTIMATION-," *Am. Math. Soc.*, pp. 1–26, 2000.
- [93] V. Fakoor, M. B. Ghalibaf, and H. A. Azarnoosh, "Asymptotic behaviors of the Lorenz curve and Gini index in sampling from a length-biased distribution," *Stat. Probab. Lett.*, vol. 81, no. 9, pp. 1425–1435, 2011.
- [94] T. Bae and B. Ko, "On the mixtures of length-biased Weibull distributions for loss severity modeling," *J. Korean Stat. Soc.*, vol. 49, no. 2, pp. 422–438, 2020.
- [95] M. Akram and A. Hayat, "Comparison of estimators of the Weibull distribution," *J. Stat. Theory Pract.*, vol. 8, no. 2, pp. 238–259, 2014.
- [96] R. L. Smith and J. C. Naylor, "A Comparison of Maximum Likelihood and Bayesian Estimators for the three parameter Weibull Distribution," *Appl. Stat.*, vol. 36, no. 3, pp. 358–369, 1987.
- [97] E. J. Green, F. A. Roesch, A. F. M. Smith, and W. E. Strawderman, "Bayesian Estimation for the Three-Parameter Weibull Distribution with Tree Diameter Data," *Biometrics*, vol. 50, no. 1, p. 254, 2006.
- [98] D. Cousineau, "Fitting the three-parameter Weibull distribution: Review and evaluation of existing and new methods," *IEEE Trans. Dielectr. Electr. Insul.*, vol. 16, no. 1, pp. 281–288, 2009.
- [99] C. A. Cohen and B. Whitten, "Modified maximum likelihood and modified moment estimators for the three-parameter Weibull distribution," *Commun. Stat. - Theory Methods*, vol. 11:23, no. 2631–2656, pp. 37–41, 1982.
- [100] A. C. Cohen, B. J. Whitten, and Y. Ding, "Modified Moment Estimation for the Three-Parameter Weibull Distribution.," *J. Qual. Technol.*, vol. 16, no. 3, pp. 159–167, 1984.
- [101] C. Park, "A Note on the Existence of the Location Parameter Estimate of the Three-Parameter Weibull Model Using the Weibull Plot," *Math. Probl. Eng.*, vol. 2018, pp. 1–6, 2018.
- [102] Y. M. Kantar and B. Şenoğlu, "A comparative study for the location and scale parameters of the Weibull distribution with given shape parameter," *Comput. Geosci.*, vol. 34, no. 12, pp. 1900–1909, 2008.
- [103] T. Arslan, Y. M. Bulut, and A. Altin Yavuz, "Comparative study of numerical methods for determining Weibull parameters for wind energy potential," *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.*, vol. 40, pp. 820–825, 2014.
- [104] C. Jung and D. Schindler, "Global comparison of the goodness-of-fit of wind speed distributions," *Energy Convers. Manag.*, vol. 133, pp. 216–234, 2017.
- [105] S. A. Akdağ and A. Dinler, "A new method to estimate Weibull parameters for wind energy applications," *Energy Convers. Manag.*, vol. 50, no. 7, pp. 1761–1766, 2009.
- [106] P. K. Chaurasiya, S. Ahmed, and V. Warudkar, "Study of different parameters estimation methods

- of Weibull distribution to determine wind power density using ground based Doppler SODAR instrument," *Alexandria Eng. J.*, vol. 57, no. 4, pp. 2299–2311, 2018.
- [107] J. O. Berger, *Statistical Decision Theory Foundations, Concepts, and Methods*, 1st editio. New York: Springer Science+Business Media, 1980.
- [108] F. Noor and M. Aslam, "Bayesian inference of the inverse Weibull mixture distribution using type-I censoring," *J. Appl. Stat.*, vol. 40, no. 5, pp. 1076–1089, 2013.
- [109] G. Li and J. Shi, "Application of Bayesian model averaging in modeling long-term wind speed distributions," *Renew. Energy*, vol. 35, no. 6, pp. 1192–1202, 2010.
- [110] S. A. Shaban and N. Boudrissa, "Bayesian Estimation of the parameters of the Weibull-Weibull Length-Biased mixture distributions using time censored data."
- [111] E. Gómez-Lázaro *et al.*, "Probability density function characterization for aggregated large-scale wind power based on Weibull mixtures," *Energies*, vol. 9, no. 2, pp. 1–15, 2016.
- [112] J. Zhou, E. Erdem, G. Li, and J. Shi, "Comprehensive evaluation of wind speed distribution models: A case study for North Dakota sites," *Energy Convers. Manag.*, vol. 51, no. 7, pp. 1449–1458, 2010.
- [113] T. P. Chang, "Wind energy assessment incorporating particle swarm optimization method," *Energy Convers. Manag.*, vol. 52, no. 3, pp. 1630–1637, 2011.
- [114] A. T. Jebb and S. E. Woo, "A Bayesian Primer for the Organizational Sciences: The 'Two Sources' and an Introduction to BugsXLA," *Organ. Res. Methods*, vol. 18, no. 1, pp. 92–132, 2015.

Appendix

Goodness-of-fit metrics to evaluate the fitness of W2, WLB and WW to model the wind speed data in In-Salah measured during in January at 10 m AGL.

PDFs	PEMs	BIC	$RMSE_{PP}$ (m/s)	MAE_{PP} (m/s)	$RMSE_{PDF}$ (m/s)	MAE_{PDF} (m/s)	
W2	Frequentist PEMs	$W2_{MLM}$	5458.27	0.0315	0.0233	0.0424	0.0289
		$W2_{LSE}$	5477.56	0.0318	0.0233	0.0449	0.0299
		$W2_{MOM}$	5458.31	0.0315	0.0233	0.0425	0.0289
		$W2_{LMOM}$	5458.49	0.0315	0.0233	0.0427	0.0290
		$W2_{PDM}$	5458.64	0.0314	0.0233	0.0421	0.0288
	Bayesian PEMs	$W2_{BM}$	5458.28	0.0315	0.0233	0.0425	0.0290
		$W2_{BD}$	5458.29	0.0315	0.0233	0.0425	0.0290
		$W2_{BMD}$	5458.31	0.0314	0.0233	0.0425	0.0289
WLB	Frequentist PEMs	WLB_{LSE}	4197.92	0.0372	0.0283	0.0417	0.0276
		WLB_{MOM}	4196.04	0.0357	0.0269	0.0425	0.0281
		WLB_{PDM}	4196.07	0.0358	0.0270	0.0424	0.0280
	Bayesian PEMs	WLB_{BM}	4196.13	0.0354	0.0266	0.0427	0.0282
		WLB_{BD}	4196.12	0.0354	0.0266	0.0427	0.0282
		WLB_{BMD}	4196.25	0.0349	0.0263	0.0427	0.0286
W3	Frequentist PEMs	$W3_{MLM}$	5443.33	0.0311	0.0227	0.0425	0.0279
		$W3_{LSE}$	5447.88	0.0312	0.0226	0.0437	0.0284
		$W3_{MLM}$	5446.67	0.0312	0.0228	0.0425	0.0281
		$W3_{MM}$	5444.89	0.0311	0.0228	0.0424	0.0279
	Bayesian PEMs	$W3_{BM}$	5441.38	0.0311	0.0226	0.0425	0.0277
WW	Bayesian PEMs	WW_{BM}	5439.14	0.0306	0.0218	0.0424	0.0277
		WW_{BD}	5439.00	0.0306	0.0218	0.0424	0.0277
		WW_{BMD}	5440.59	0.0306	0.0221	0.0416	0.0277

Note: The bold values indicate the best fit estimators for each metric

Goodness-of-fit metrics to evaluate the fitness of W2, WLB and WW to model the wind speed data in In-Salah measured during in February at 10 m AGL.

PDFs	PEMs		BIC	$RMSE_{PP}$ (m/s)	MAE_{PP} (m/s)	$RMSE_{PDF}$ (m/s)	MAE_{PDF} (m/s)
W2	Frequentist PEMs	$W2_{MLM}$	5056.62	0.0333	0.0233	0.0402	0.0278
		$W2_{LSE}$	5101.16	0.0340	0.0239	0.0437	0.0282
		$W2_{MOM}$	5056.97	0.0333	0.0233	0.0404	0.0277
		$W2_{LMOM}$	5060.25	0.0334	0.0235	0.0411	0.0277
		$W2_{PDM}$	5057.25	0.0333	0.0234	0.0398	0.0278
	Bayesian PEMs	$W2_{BM}$	5056.62	0.0333	0.0233	0.0402	0.0278
		$W2_{BD}$	5056.62	0.0333	0.0233	0.0402	0.0278
$W2_{BMD}$		5058.85	0.0335	0.0233	0.0398	0.0281	
WLB	Frequentist PEMs	WLB_{LSE}	3899.78	0.0369	0.0283	0.0401	0.0261
		WLB_{MOM}	3899.53	0.0363	0.0280	0.0400	0.0265
		WLB_{PDM}	3898.52	0.0370	0.0285	0.0395	0.0265
	Bayesian PEMs	WLB_{BM}	3899.87	0.0361	0.0278	0.0401	0.0265
		WLB_{BD}	3899.84	0.0362	0.0278	0.0401	0.0265
		WLB_{BMD}	3898.77	0.0366	0.0282	0.0397	0.0266
W3	Frequentist PEMs	$W3_{MLM}$	5034.85	0.0320	0.0218	0.0390	0.0256
		$W3_{LSE}$	5053.07	0.0323	0.0220	0.0412	0.0256
		$W3_{MLM}$	5038.44	0.0321	0.0219	0.0391	0.0258
		$W3_{MM}$	5036.27	0.0320	0.0219	0.0391	0.0256
	Bayesian PEMs	$W3_{BM}$	5030.25	0.0318	0.0217	0.0389	0.0252
WW	Bayesian PEMs	WW_{BM}	4994.53	0.0309	0.0202	0.0400	0.0242
		WW_{BD}	4994.53	0.0309	0.0202	0.0400	0.0242
		WW_{BMD}	4998.37	0.0308	0.0204	0.0390	0.0238

Note: The bold values indicate the best fit estimators for each metric

Goodness-of-fit metrics to evaluate the fitness of W2, WLB and WW to model the wind speed data in In-Salah measured during in March at 10 m AGL.

PDFs	PEMs	BIC	$RMSE_{PP}$ (m/s)	MAE_{PP} (m/s)	$RMSE_{PDF}$ (m/s)	MAE_{PDF} (m/s)	
W2	Frequentist PEMs	$W2_{MLM}$	5592.85	0.0278	0.0182	0.0382	0.0265
		$W2_{LSE}$	5619.31	0.0285	0.0182	0.0414	0.0279
		$W2_{MOM}$	5593.07	0.0278	0.0182	0.0385	0.0266
		$W2_{LMOM}$	5593.89	0.0279	0.0182	0.0388	0.0267
		$W2_{PDM}$	5593.10	0.0278	0.0183	0.0380	0.0263
	Bayesian PEMs	$W2_{BM}$	5592.85	0.0278	0.0182	0.0382	0.0265
		$W2_{BD}$	5592.85	0.0278	0.0182	0.0382	0.0265
$W2_{BMD}$		5594.14	0.0280	0.0181	0.0382	0.0267	
WLB	Frequentist PEMs	WLB_{LSE}	4334.18	0.0327	0.0252	0.0375	0.0249
		WLB_{MOM}	4335.58	0.0313	0.0240	0.0384	0.0255
		WLB_{PDM}	4334.93	0.0316	0.0243	0.0381	0.0253
	Bayesian PEMs	WLB_{BM}	4335.67	0.0313	0.0240	0.0384	0.0255
		WLB_{BD}	4335.65	0.0313	0.0240	0.0384	0.0255
		WLB_{BMD}	4336.58	0.0307	0.0235	0.0386	0.0258
W3	Frequentist PEMs	$W3_{MLM}$	5574.44	0.0273	0.0177	0.0382	0.0253
		$W3_{LSE}$	5582.66	0.0277	0.0175	0.0399	0.0262
		$W3_{MLM}$	5582.65	0.0275	0.0179	0.0382	0.0258
		$W3_{MM}$	5580.25	0.0274	0.0179	0.0382	0.0257
	Bayesian PEMs	$W3_{BM}$	5572.30	0.0273	0.0176	0.0381	0.0251
WW	Bayesian PEMs	WW_{BM}	5575.82	0.0263	0.0172	0.0370	0.0221
		WW_{BD}	5575.33	0.0263	0.0173	0.0368	0.0221
		WW_{BMD}	5575.88	0.0264	0.0173	0.0369	0.0225

Note: The bold values indicate the best fit estimators for each metric

Goodness-of-fit metrics to evaluate the fitness of W2, WLB and WW to model the wind speed data in In-Salah measured during in April at 10 m AGL.

PDFs	PEMs		BIC	$RMSE_{PP}$ (m/s)	MAE_{PP} (m/s)	$RMSE_{PDF}$ (m/s)	MAE_{PDF} (m/s)
W2	Frequentist PEMs	$W2_{MLM}$	5000.83	0.0343	0.0222	0.0369	0.0245
		$W2_{LSE}$	5065.02	0.0350	0.0217	0.0399	0.0258
		$W2_{MOM}$	5000.89	0.0342	0.0222	0.0368	0.0244
		$W2_{LMOM}$	5004.43	0.0343	0.0219	0.0374	0.0247
		$W2_{PDM}$	5003.87	0.0342	0.0224	0.0365	0.0242
	Bayesian PEMs	$W2_{BM}$	5000.85	0.0343	0.0222	0.0370	0.0246
		$W2_{BD}$	5000.86	0.0343	0.0222	0.0370	0.0246
$W2_{BMD}$		5002.65	0.0347	0.0225	0.0374	0.0251	
WLB	Frequentist PEMs	WLB_{LSE}	3825.22	0.0411	0.0297	0.0361	0.0225
		WLB_{MOM}	3825.95	0.0405	0.0290	0.0360	0.0231
		WLB_{PDM}	3829.12	0.0417	0.0300	0.0358	0.0229
	Bayesian PEMs	WLB_{BM}	3824.62	0.0394	0.0281	0.0364	0.0233
		WLB_{BD}	3824.61	0.0394	0.0281	0.0364	0.0233
		WLB_{BMD}	3824.63	0.0383	0.0271	0.0368	0.0237
W3	Frequentist PEMs	$W3_{MLM}$	4918.84	0.0317	0.0187	0.0352	0.0204
		$W3_{LSE}$	4926.97	0.0318	0.0186	0.0360	0.0210
		$W3_{MLM}$	4916.76	0.0317	0.0187	0.0351	0.0203
		$W3_{MM}$	4916.49	0.0316	0.0186	0.0350	0.0203
	Bayesian PEMs	$W3_{BM}$	4915.63	0.0316	0.0186	0.0351	0.0202
WW	Bayesian PEMs	WW_{BM}	4918.75	0.0291	0.0183	0.0329	0.0189
		WW_{BD}	4918.77	0.0291	0.0182	0.0329	0.0188
		WW_{BMD}	4927.14	0.0302	0.0195	0.0336	0.0203

Note: The bold values indicate the best fit estimators for each metric

Goodness-of-fit metrics to evaluate the fitness of W2, WLB and WW to model the wind speed data in In-Salah measured during in May at 10 m AGL.

PDFs	PEMs	BIC	$RMSE_{PP}$ (m/s)	MAE_{PP} (m/s)	$RMSE_{PDF}$ (m/s)	MAE_{PDF} (m/s)	
W2	Frequentist PEMs	$W2_{MLM}$	6621.17	0.0294	0.0218	0.0428	0.0309
		$W2_{LSE}$	6624.54	0.0297	0.0218	0.0440	0.0314
		$W2_{MOM}$	6621.47	0.0293	0.0217	0.0425	0.0308
		$W2_{LMOM}$	6621.92	0.0293	0.0217	0.0423	0.0307
		$W2_{PDM}$	6621.41	0.0294	0.0217	0.0425	0.0308
	Bayesian PEMs	$W2_{BM}$	6621.17	0.0294	0.0218	0.0428	0.0309
		$W2_{BD}$	6621.18	0.0294	0.0218	0.0427	0.0309
$W2_{BMD}$		6622.53	0.0294	0.0217	0.0427	0.0307	
WLB	Frequentist PEMs	WLB_{LSE}	5093.54	0.0356	0.0269	0.0404	0.0295
		WLB_{MOM}	5072.16	0.0337	0.0242	0.0431	0.0303
		WLB_{PDM}	5071.07	0.0335	0.0239	0.0434	0.0305
	Bayesian PEMs	WLB_{BM}	5070.90	0.0334	0.0238	0.0434	0.0305
		WLB_{BD}	5070.87	0.0334	0.0238	0.0434	0.0305
		WLB_{BMD}	5073.94	0.0341	0.0247	0.0428	0.0301
W3	Frequentist PEMs	$W3_{MLM}$	6614.37	0.0287	0.0206	0.0421	0.0289
		$W3_{LSE}$	6614.72	0.0286	0.0206	0.0418	0.0288
		$W3_{MLM}$	6615.66	0.0287	0.0207	0.0421	0.0291
		$W3_{MM}$	6615.12	0.0287	0.0206	0.0419	0.0289
	Bayesian PEMs	$W3_{BM}$	6614.43	0.0287	0.0206	0.0421	0.0289
WW	Bayesian PEMs	WW_{BM}	6584.33	0.0288	0.0211	0.0420	0.0277
		WW_{BD}	6584.39	0.0288	0.0211	0.0420	0.0277
		WW_{BMD}	6588.21	0.0287	0.0211	0.0416	0.0278

Note: The bold values indicate the best fit estimators for each metric

Goodness-of-fit metrics to evaluate the fitness of W2, WLB and WW to model the wind speed data in In-Salah measured during in June at 10 m AGL.

PDFs	PEMs		BIC	$RMSE_{PP}$ (m/s)	MAE_{PP} (m/s)	$RMSE_{PDF}$ (m/s)	MAE_{PDF} (m/s)
W2	Frequentist PEMs	$W2_{MLM}$	6455.23	0.0309	0.0219	0.0353	0.0225
		$W2_{LSE}$	6478.47	0.0316	0.0222	0.0374	0.0235
		$W2_{MOM}$	6455.32	0.0309	0.0219	0.0352	0.0225
		$W2_{LMOM}$	6455.32	0.0309	0.0220	0.0353	0.0226
		$W2_{PDM}$	6456.12	0.0308	0.0219	0.0349	0.0225
	Bayesian PEMs	$W2_{BM}$	6455.24	0.0310	0.0219	0.0353	0.0226
		$W2_{BD}$	6455.24	0.0310	0.0219	0.0353	0.0226
$W2_{BMD}$		6456.02	0.0308	0.0219	0.0349	0.0225	
WLB	Frequentist PEMs	WLB_{LSE}	4975.24	0.0383	0.0273	0.0340	0.0219
		WLB_{MOM}	4961.71	0.0359	0.0254	0.0350	0.0220
		WLB_{PDM}	4962.29	0.0361	0.0255	0.0349	0.0220
	Bayesian PEMs	WLB_{BM}	4960.36	0.0355	0.0250	0.0352	0.0221
		WLB_{BD}	4960.32	0.0355	0.0250	0.0352	0.0221
		WLB_{BMD}	4958.93	0.0344	0.0242	0.0356	0.0222
W3	Frequentist PEMs	$W3_{MLM}$	6449.47	0.0307	0.0216	0.0351	0.0222
		$W3_{LSE}$	6463.54	0.0312	0.0218	0.0367	0.0229
		$W3_{MLM}$	6459.27	0.0309	0.0219	0.0352	0.0225
		$W3_{MM}$	6456.35	0.0308	0.0218	0.0351	0.0224
	Bayesian PEMs	$W3_{BM}$	6446.60	0.0306	0.0215	0.0351	0.0221
WW	Bayesian PEMs	WW_{BM}	6414.58	0.0284	0.0193	0.0325	0.0188
		WW_{BD}	6414.38	0.0283	0.0192	0.0324	0.0188
		WW_{BMD}	6420.35	0.0283	0.0194	0.0321	0.0194

Note: The bold values indicate the best fit estimators for each metric

Goodness-of-fit metrics to evaluate the fitness of W2, WLB and WW to model the wind speed data in In-Salah measured during in July at 10 m AGL.

PDFs	PEMs		BIC	$RMSE_{PP}$ (m/s)	MAE_{PP} (m/s)	$RMSE_{PDF}$ (m/s)	MAE_{PDF} (m/s)
W2	Frequentist PEMs	$W2_{MLM}$	6508.40	0.0283	0.0214	0.0422	0.0274
		$W2_{LSE}$	6508.73	0.0284	0.0214	0.0426	0.0276
		$W2_{MOM}$	6508.53	0.0283	0.0214	0.0420	0.0273
		$W2_{LMOM}$	6508.63	0.0283	0.0214	0.0420	0.0273
		$W2_{PDM}$	6508.49	0.0283	0.0214	0.0421	0.0273
	Bayesian PEMs	$W2_{BM}$	6508.42	0.0283	0.0214	0.0422	0.0274
		$W2_{BD}$	6508.42	0.0283	0.0214	0.0422	0.0274
$W2_{BMD}$		6509.23	0.0284	0.0214	0.0424	0.0275	
WLB	Frequentist PEMs	WLB_{LSE}	5079.38	0.0329	0.0248	0.0413	0.0273
		WLB_{MOM}	5078.55	0.0326	0.0239	0.0425	0.0277
		WLB_{PDM}	5078.61	0.0324	0.0237	0.0427	0.0278
	Bayesian PEMs	WLB_{BM}	5078.67	0.0323	0.0236	0.0427	0.0279
		WLB_{BD}	5078.66	0.0323	0.0236	0.0427	0.0279
		WLB_{BMD}	5078.59	0.0329	0.0243	0.0423	0.0276
W3	Frequentist PEMs	$W3_{MLM}$	6511.26	0.0278	0.0205	0.0417	0.0266
		$W3_{LSE}$	6515.71	0.0278	0.0206	0.0406	0.0261
		$W3_{MLM}$	6512.48	0.0279	0.0205	0.0417	0.0266
		$W3_{MM}$	6513.68	0.0279	0.0205	0.0416	0.0266
	Bayesian PEMs	$W3_{BM}$	6510.88	0.0278	0.0206	0.0416	0.0265
WW	Bayesian PEMs	WW_{BM}	6527.60	0.0284	0.0214	0.0423	0.0273
		WW_{BD}	6525.32	0.0283	0.0214	0.0420	0.0270
		WW_{BMD}	6527.80	0.0282	0.0214	0.0412	0.0266

Note: The bold values indicate the best fit estimators for each metric

Goodness-of-fit metrics to evaluate the fitness of W2, WLB and WW to model the wind speed data in In-Salah measured during in August at 10 m AGL.

PDFs	PEMs		BIC	$RMSE_{PP}$ (m/s)	MAE_{PP} (m/s)	$RMSE_{PDF}$ (m/s)	MAE_{PDF} (m/s)
W2	Frequentist PEMs	$W2_{MLM}$	6523.97	0.0335	0.0211	0.0400	0.0256
		$W2_{LSE}$	6546.30	0.0337	0.0212	0.0419	0.0254
		$W2_{MOM}$	6524.41	0.0335	0.0210	0.0402	0.0256
		$W2_{LMOM}$	6525.88	0.0335	0.0209	0.0405	0.0255
		$W2_{PDM}$	6524.04	0.0335	0.0211	0.0399	0.0256
	Bayesian PEMs	$W2_{BM}$	6523.97	0.0335	0.0211	0.0400	0.0256
		$W2_{BD}$	6523.97	0.0335	0.0211	0.0400	0.0256
$W2_{BMD}$		6523.97	0.0335	0.0211	0.0400	0.0256	
WLB	Frequentist PEMs	WLB_{LSE}	5069.86	0.0375	0.0266	0.0401	0.0247
		WLB_{MOM}	5070.67	0.0371	0.0263	0.0402	0.0248
		WLB_{PDM}	5069.74	0.0373	0.0265	0.0400	0.0248
	Bayesian PEMs	WLB_{BM}	5070.55	0.0371	0.0263	0.0402	0.0248
		WLB_{BD}	5070.52	0.0371	0.0263	0.0402	0.0248
		WLB_{BMD}	5068.28	0.0373	0.0264	0.0395	0.0251
W3	Frequentist PEMs	$W3_{MLM}$	6511.20	0.0326	0.0199	0.0393	0.0240
		$W3_{LSE}$	6517.46	0.0327	0.0198	0.0402	0.0239
		$W3_{MLM}$	6515.44	0.0327	0.0200	0.0392	0.0242
		$W3_{MM}$	6513.53	0.0327	0.0199	0.0393	0.0241
	Bayesian PEMs	$W3_{BM}$	6508.14	0.0326	0.0199	0.0393	0.0238
WW	Bayesian PEMs	WW_{BM}	6522.73	0.0331	0.0203	0.0402	0.0240
		WW_{BD}	6522.84	0.0331	0.0203	0.0402	0.0240
		WW_{BMD}	6525.47	0.0331	0.0205	0.0398	0.0242

Note: The bold values indicate the best fit estimators for each metric

Goodness-of-fit metrics to evaluate the fitness of W2, WLB and WW to model the wind speed data in In-Salah measured during in September at 10 m AGL.

PDFs	PEMs		BIC	$RMSE_{PP}$ (m/s)	MAE_{PP} (m/s)	$RMSE_{PDF}$ (m/s)	MAE_{PDF} (m/s)
W2	Frequentist PEMs	$W2_{MLM}$	5899.39	0.0291	0.0154	0.0297	0.0154
		$W2_{LSE}$	5986.06	0.0299	0.0137	0.0321	0.0142
		$W2_{MOM}$	5904.71	0.0291	0.0149	0.0301	0.0147
		$W2_{LMOM}$	5924.36	0.0293	0.0145	0.0307	0.0144
		$W2_{PDM}$	5899.49	0.0292	0.0155	0.0297	0.0155
	Bayesian PEMs	$W2_{BM}$	5899.40	0.0291	0.0154	0.0297	0.0154
		$W2_{BD}$	5899.40	0.0291	0.0154	0.0297	0.0154
$W2_{BMD}$		5901.05	0.0290	0.0152	0.0297	0.0149	
WLB	Frequentist PEMs	WLB_{LSE}	4576.97	0.0348	0.0219	0.0306	0.0131
		WLB_{MOM}	4566.99	0.0349	0.0222	0.0300	0.0137
		WLB_{PDM}	4557.21	0.0362	0.0234	0.0296	0.0143
	Bayesian PEMs	WLB_{BM}	4563.34	0.0353	0.0226	0.0299	0.0139
		WLB_{BD}	4563.36	0.0353	0.0226	0.0299	0.0139
		WLB_{BMD}	4566.64	0.0358	0.0228	0.0301	0.0134
W3	Frequentist PEMs	$W3_{MLM}$	5895.24	0.0290	0.0152	0.0297	0.0150
		$W3_{LSE}$	5964.41	0.0297	0.0137	0.0319	0.0140
	Bayesian PEMs	$W3_{BM}$	5884.86	0.0289	0.0149	0.0296	0.0148
WW	Bayesian PEMs	WW_{BM}	5836.61	0.0296	0.0134	0.0313	0.0129
		WW_{BD}	5835.84	0.0296	0.0134	0.0314	0.0129
		WW_{BMD}	5840.70	0.0296	0.0133	0.0315	0.0128

Note: The bold values indicate the best fit estimators for each metric

Goodness-of-fit metrics to evaluate the fitness of W2, WLB and WW to model the wind speed data in In-Salah measured during in October at 10 m AGL.

PDFs	PEMs	BIC	$RMSE_{PP}$ (m/s)	MAE_{PP} (m/s)	$RMSE_{PDF}$ (m/s)	MAE_{PDF} (m/s)	
W2	Frequentist PEMs	$W2_{MLM}$	4918.97	0.0434	0.0293	0.0517	0.0350
		$W2_{LSE}$	4999.15	0.0446	0.0294	0.0568	0.0376
		$W2_{MOM}$	4920.09	0.0434	0.0293	0.0522	0.0352
		$W2_{LMOM}$	4929.69	0.0437	0.0293	0.0534	0.0359
		$W2_{PDM}$	4919.89	0.0433	0.0293	0.0512	0.0347
	Bayesian PEMs	$W2_{BM}$	4918.97	0.0434	0.0293	0.0517	0.0350
		$W2_{BD}$	4918.97	0.0434	0.0293	0.0517	0.0350
$W2_{BMD}$		4929.83	0.0427	0.0291	0.0513	0.0344	
WLB	Frequentist PEMs	WLB_{LSE}	3776.59	0.0452	0.0323	0.0517	0.0333
		WLB_{MOM}	3775.40	0.0446	0.0317	0.0515	0.0338
		WLB_{PDM}	3771.40	0.0455	0.0325	0.0507	0.0335
	Bayesian PEMs	WLB_{BM}	3775.09	0.0447	0.0317	0.0515	0.0338
		WLB_{BD}	3775.16	0.0447	0.0317	0.0515	0.0338
		WLB_{BMD}	3777.22	0.0443	0.0313	0.0518	0.0341
W3	Frequentist PEMs	$W3_{MLM}$	4799.36	0.0409	0.0264	0.0507	0.0307
		$W3_{LSE}$	4806.68	0.0412	0.0266	0.0521	0.0311
		$W3_{MLM}$	4793.53	0.0405	0.0258	0.0506	0.0298
		$W3_{MM}$	4794.61	0.0404	0.0257	0.0505	0.0297
	Bayesian PEMs	$W3_{BM}$	4792.71	0.0406	0.0260	0.0506	0.0301
WW	Bayesian PEMs	WW_{BM}	4795.33	0.0387	0.0258	0.0492	0.0277
		WW_{BD}	4795.28	0.0386	0.0258	0.0492	0.0277
		WW_{BMD}	4798.32	0.0392	0.0258	0.0499	0.0284

Note: The bold values indicate the best fit estimators for each metric

Goodness-of-fit metrics to evaluate the fitness of W2, WLB and WW to model the wind speed data in In-Salah measured during in November at 10 m AGL.

PDFs	PEMs	BIC	$RMSE_{PP}$ (m/s)	MAE_{PP} (m/s)	$RMSE_{PDF}$ (m/s)	MAE_{PDF} (m/s)	
W2	Frequentist PEMs	$W2_{MLM}$	5666.08	0.0353	0.0259	0.0443	0.0307
		$W2_{LSE}$	5811.78	0.0378	0.0280	0.0421	0.0339
		$W2_{MOM}$	5668.04	0.0353	0.0258	0.0447	0.0309
		$W2_{LMOM}$	5670.41	0.0353	0.0258	0.0450	0.0309
		$W2_{PDM}$	5667.01	0.0353	0.0258	0.0445	0.0309
	Bayesian PEMs	$W2_{BM}$	5666.08	0.0353	0.0259	0.0443	0.0307
		$W2_{BD}$	5666.08	0.0353	0.0259	0.0443	0.0307
		$W2_{BMD}$	5667.46	0.0354	0.0260	0.0442	0.0305
WLB	Frequentist PEMs	WLB_{LSE}	4274.25	0.0407	0.0295	0.0449	0.0302
		WLB_{MOM}	4274.03	0.0405	0.0293	0.0448	0.0303
		WLB_{PDM}	4274.08	0.0405	0.0294	0.0448	0.0303
	Bayesian PEMs	WLB_{BM}	4275.80	0.0412	0.0299	0.0446	0.0301
		WLB_{BD}	4275.79	0.0412	0.0299	0.0446	0.0301
		WLB_{BMD}	4274.79	0.0410	0.0298	0.0448	0.0301
WW	Bayesian PEMs	WW_{BM}	5685.42	0.0351	0.0257	0.0444	0.0303
		WW_{BD}	5685.46	0.0351	0.0257	0.0443	0.0304
		WW_{BMD}	5687.37	0.0352	0.0257	0.0443	0.0306

Note: The bold values indicate the best fit estimators for each metric

Goodness-of-fit metrics to evaluate the fitness of W2, WLB and WW to model the wind speed data in In-Salah measured during in December at 10 m AGL.

PDFs	PEMs	BIC	$RMSE_{PP}$ (m/s)	MAE_{PP} (m/s)	$RMSE_{PDF}$ (m/s)	MAE_{PDF} (m/s)	
W2	Frequentist PEMs	$W2_{MLM}$	6650.94	0.0288	0.0194	0.0356	0.0219
		$W2_{LSE}$	6831.56	0.0317	0.0242	0.0338	0.0252
		$W2_{MOM}$	6651.23	0.0287	0.0193	0.0357	0.0219
		$W2_{LMOM}$	6651.56	0.0287	0.0193	0.0358	0.0219
		$W2_{PDM}$	6651.69	0.0287	0.0192	0.0358	0.0219
	Bayesian PEMs	$W2_{BM}$	6650.96	0.0288	0.0194	0.0356	0.0219
		$W2_{BD}$	6650.96	0.0288	0.0194	0.0356	0.0219
		$W2_{BMD}$	6651.83	0.0288	0.0196	0.0353	0.0219
WLB	Frequentist PEMs	WLB_{LSE}	5258.04	0.0335	0.0231	0.0356	0.0223
		WLB_{MOM}	5258.31	0.0339	0.0233	0.0362	0.0222
		WLB_{PDM}	5258.84	0.0336	0.0229	0.0364	0.0223
	Bayesian PEMs	WLB_{BM}	5258.16	0.0341	0.0235	0.0362	0.0222
		WLB_{BD}	5258.19	0.0341	0.0235	0.0362	0.0222
		WLB_{BMD}	5258.32	0.0340	0.0234	0.0363	0.0223
W3	Frequentist PEMs	$W3_{MLM}$	6668.82	0.0283	0.0187	0.0349	0.0211
WW	Bayesian PEMs	WW_{BM}	6675.31	0.0289	0.0194	0.0357	0.0220
		WW_{BD}	6673.78	0.0288	0.0194	0.0357	0.0220
		WW_{BMD}	6675.71	0.0289	0.0193	0.0360	0.0221

Note: The bold values indicate the best fit estimators for each metric